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Report on the Tools for NBS Design and Implementation

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Preface

The general agenda of COEVOLVERS is to explore conceptual, theoretical and practical pathways to creating more resilient and inclusive communities of human and non-human beings. Work package 2 is the arena where these three aspects are reflected as an integrated package, while adopting a strategic perspective: COEVOLVERS as a project is not just describing and diagnosing coevolutionary phenomena for immediate action on the ground, but is part and parcel of a coevolutionary process that unfolds in the LLs and that extends the period of formal project implementation. In other words, concepts, theories and practices coevolve in the ongoing research. In its focus on conceptual and theoretical work, WP 2 takes a strategic stance towards practices: In which sense can we interpret current practices as harbingers of future socioecological transformations and innovations?

Deliverable 2.3. explores how the coevolutionary approach is implemented in LL practices, and how this practice informs theory development. Other COEVOLVERS deliverables provide detailed accounts of Living Lab (LL) practices and experiences, including the presentation of tools of design and implementation. This complementary WP2 report completes a "hop, step, and jump" movement, beginning with an outline of coevolutionary theory in D.2.1, progressing to its methodological implications in D.2.2, and now examining LL practices. Throughout this process, we maintain a strong focus on theory development, which is central to WP2. The main distinction from previous applications of theory is that we identify a set of key medium-level theoretical concepts that highlight common threads across LLs while remaining relevant to practical applications. These concepts are the trays by which we organise the toolbox of NBS design and implementation, with the tools being those actually used in LLs (in D.2.2., we also presented many others that can be deduced from the general theoretical framework).

When relating to LLs, we select aspects that apply broadly, if not universally, across many LLs, and thus these may be considered umbrella concepts within COEVOLVERS. These concepts align well with the coevolutionary approach to

“actionable knowledge” (Räsänen et al., 2024), which focuses on the complex interactions among evolving assemblages of actors and media that have different ontological statuses. In earlier deliverables, this includes:

- The coevolution of the material structures of NBS as infrastructure along with the practices and habits of the local community.
- The coevolution of human and non-human practices mediated by NBS, which promotes cohabitation.
- The coevolution of research methodologies and practices within communities of learning.
- The coevolution of grey and green elements of NBS in multispecies design.

In the current deliverable, we approach the medium-level concepts as directly relating to specific material constituents of NBS conceived as assemblages, such as, for example, treating “maps” as material objects that are elements of assemblages of humans and non-humans, living and non-living. Tools are elements of such assemblages that bring them into being and keep them working.

While D.2.2 uses a deductive approach to establish methods and research practices, D.2.3 utilises an inductive approach, against the backdrop of the theoretical concepts developed in earlier deliverables. We collected the material for the inductive procedure from a series of interviews with LL members.* The interviews not only identified and addressed the challenges faced in each LL, but also provided early access to the tools and methods that the LLs are developing, testing, and employing in their respective regions. In combining deductive and inductive approaches, we follow the logic of abduction—a key concept in Peirce's pragmatism, which is central to the COEVOLVER research philosophy. This approach suggests that while there is a pre-existing general framework of coevolution, there is also significant flexibility within it to accommodate emerging LL solutions. By gaining early insights into the solutions being utilised and those planned for the future, we have created a general typology

* Initially, we planned to conduct a series of participatory workshops led by WP2 involving LLs. However, we discovered that participation fatigue is a common challenge when implementing co-creative methods. Since the LLs already host their own participatory workshops in various formats, we decided to draw on their experiences through interviews instead. We wanted to avoid overwhelming the LL workshops by introducing an additional series of events led by WP2.

consisting of five major sections outlined in D.2.3. Each of these sections is deeply intertwined with the coevolutionary approach, allowing for adaptability based on LL inputs. We further developed the coevolutionary approach through the lens of these five sections, employing a cross-pollination method that draws from both LL practice and current theoretical frameworks. As a result, we successfully completed D.2.3.

To retake the example of maps, we found that maps play a significant role in all LLs, appearing in various forms such as mapping the locations of stories or highlighting the affordances of a place for non-human entities. Therefore, we aim to systematise these diverse uses of maps and interpret mapping through the lens of the broader multi-species niche construction framework established in D.2.1 and D.2.2. Additionally, following recent advancements in the science of cartography, we view mapping not only as a scientific tool but also as an aesthetic practice and a form of artwork within communities. Thus, mapping as a co-creative activity is a crucial element in transdisciplinary LL practices. We conceptualise these practices as “crafting coevolving assemblages.”

The new theoretical aspect of D.2.3 is the integration of coevolutionary theory with assemblage theory. Assemblage theory serves as an effective epistemic tool connecting the concepts derived from LL practices with the broader coevolutionary concepts established in previous deliverables. This approach helps address the issue of recognising non-human agency in NBS. By employing assemblage theory, we can attribute agency to combinations of both human and non-human elements, such as in the formation of multi-species stakeholder assemblages. We emphasise that assemblage theory is not a substitute for theories that we have deployed, in earlier WP 2 deliverables, such as niche construction theory. The concept of assemblage dovetails smoothly with these other concepts since it allows for a more detailed view on structures and dynamics of coevolutionary processes while keeping basic tenets intact. The key contribution of assemblage theory on the fundamental level is to equip coevolutionary theory with a unified ontology that overcomes dualisms such as human/non-human. As we show in this deliverable, this has the far-reaching consequence that we orchestrate a frame switch from “Nature-based solutions” to “Nature-based assemblages.”

As discussed in D.2.2 (pp. 186ff), we adopt a distinct reporting format to illustrate this interaction between practice and theory. We include the original voices of LL members in boxes alongside the main text, allowing them to report and reflect on their practices in their own words, and presenting vignettes on their practices. Our theoretical argument unfolds in tandem with these recordings. This collaboration leads to the identification of five core medium-level concepts: multispecies stakeholder assemblage (MSA), mapping and countermapping, narratives and stories, nature-based entrepreneurship, and Nature-based assemblage (NBA). The five main chapters detail these concepts. Chapter 1 outlines the general methodological perspective of assemblage theory that we take in the process of grounding theory in practices. In this chapter, we draw the radical conclusion from LL practices: We argue that the concept of NBS must be complemented, if not substituted, by the concept of NBA. Chapter 6 adds more flesh to the bones of this argument.

Chapter 1: Introducing the concept of “Nature-based assemblage”

1.0. Chapter summary

This chapter introduces the concept of Nature-based assemblage (NBA) as a complementary, if not alternative, idea to Nature-based solution (NBS). NBS is defined as an “idea” that assumes a linear causality between an intervention, the problem it addresses, and the solution it provides; this idea motivates the initial human intervention. In contrast, the NBA reflects the real-world complexities that follow an emergent, circular, and co-evolutionary logic after the idea is put into practice by a human intervention. The concept of NBA is informed by assemblage theory, which serves as a bridge between general co-evolutionary theory and Living Lab practices. Using assemblage theory, we develop five intermediary theoretical concepts derived from Living Lab practices: “multispecies stakeholder assemblages,” “mapping and countermapping,” “narratives and stories,” “nature-based entrepreneurship, and “careful crafting of NBAs.” This chapter provides an overview of these concepts and presents a preliminary illustration of the Barcelona “Wildfire Eaters” Living Lab.

1.1. From designing Nature-based solutions to crafting Nature-based assemblages

One background concept stands out in this deliverable, which was not articulated with the same emphasis in the previous deliverables: the concept of “assemblage.” We draw on the meanings articulated by Deleuze and Guattari (Deleuze and Guattari, 2009) and DeLanda (DeLanda, 2016, 2006), though we will not delve into their specific terminologies. An assemblage refers to the confluence and scaffolding of causal powers that emerge from a combination of elements, each of which retains its autonomous identity—this idea is more explicitly captured in the French term “agencement.” This concept stands in contrast to “system,” as seen in terms like “ecosystem.” Systems have defined boundaries and operate according to an internal logic that governs their reactions to external influences. In contrast, assemblages lack fixed boundaries because their components maintain partially autonomous relationships with outside entities. Rather, they serve as nodes where multiple, often conflicting mechanisms converge, without a dominant internal logic dictating their interactions.

In sustainability science, assemblage theory has been embraced as a way to operationalise the concept of relationality in analytical work, modeling, and the design of governance institutions (Schlüter et al., 2025). Our approach aligns with these developments. The assemblage perspective is particularly suited to the unique challenges of designing and implementing NBS, thus also showcasing how the choice of theories is shaped by the specific challenges met in ecosocial transformation (Schlüter et al. 2022, Morgado et al. 2025). NBS often address situations of disequilibrium, where systemic mechanisms are disrupted, such as the increasing frequency of flooding. For instance, creating watersheds and other natural elements for water management cannot be compared to constructing grey infrastructure, where the starting and ending points are clearly defined, and the engineering design is entirely controlled by humans. In contrast, a coevolutionary approach views NBS as an open process with ambiguous boundaries and multiple goals that are not solely determined by human engineers.

An NBS is an assemblage rather than a system. An engine designed by humans is considered a system. While an NBS can also be conceptualised as a technology to address problems faced by humans, it evolves through complex interactions with various internal and external factors. Similarly, the actors related to NBS form assemblages that are not clearly defined groups or organisations. This is a result of the imperatives of co-creation and co-production. A cart pulled by a motorised vehicle functions as a system, while a cart drawn by a mule is more like an assemblage, as the animal may not always agree with the human owner's intentions. Although the owner can impose their will through sheer force, a more effective approach would be to cultivate a workable form of relationship between the two. Mule and human may engage in embodied relationality.

The cart, the mule, and the human together represent a simple, pre-modern form of NBS where the human sets narrow goals, while also being obliged to heed attention to the interests of the non-human partner. A modern iteration of this type of animal-human relationship can be found in nature-based tourism (Kuenzi and McNeely, 2008), where human entrepreneurs must develop sophisticated strategies to manage interactions with animals providing services (Hoarau-Heemstra and Kline, 2022). They

also need to adapt to the ever-changing dynamics with tourists, who seek to form connections with these animals. Humans actively participate in creating interactions among multiple species, attributing specific causal powers to each party involved. This is especially evident when these interactions are not just for leisure but also have therapeutic purposes. In this context, we can refer to it as a healing NBS, like the COEVOLVERS example of a healing garden (see Chapter 6).

In general, NBS are multi-species assemblages, or “Nature-based assemblages” NBA: This deliverable suggests a new view of NBS as “ideas” that guide the crafting of nature-based assemblages in a complex and continuously changing environment. To accurately describe NBAs, we need distinct methods, which we examine in this deliverable about emerging COEVOLVERS LLs tools. For instance, the dynamic nature of the multiple interaction flows and events that sustain an NBA and drive its causal impacts is best represented through narratives rather than standard scientific reports (D.2.2., pp. 186ff). One essential aspect is that narratives (Chapter 4) can integrate diverse perspectives of assemblage members and avoid imposing a linear scientific account of causation, which is typically dominant in research projects, despite other rhetoric (Adelle et al., 2020). Assemblages are dynamic because they are influenced by the unpredictable actions of their members, which can be understood within a generalised notion of entrepreneurship (Chapter 5), especially concerning human actors. In this deliverable, we do not present full narratives of LLs, as these are done by them at other places, but provide vignettes through interviews (on the concept of vignette, see D.2.2., pp. 132f). The interview snippets that we present in the boxes show the ongoing work in the LLs and no results or practices that are already consolidated.

We use the term “craft” to describe the actions that bring NBS into existence and sustain them over time. This concept of “craft” differentiates a specific form of skill-based productive activity from the traditional linear approach to applying scientific knowledge in practical contexts (Sennett, 2009). As outlined in D.2.2 (Chapter 5), the prevalent idea of “actionable knowledge” typically follows this linear model, transforming “knowing that” into “knowing how.” In contrast, engaging in a craft is a deeply contextualised action that activates shared forms of implicit and tacit

knowledge (“knowing how”) within communities of craftspeople, even when the production occurs individually. Therefore, we use the term to encompass a wide range of practices often described using various “co-concepts,” such as co-production or co-creation (Sarkki et al., 2025). Most of these concepts align with a participatory approach, highlighting the political dimensions of NBS and inadvertently marginalising non-human entities. Conversely, the notion of “craft” emphasises a key concern for COEVOLVERS: conceptualising NBS as an aesthetic practice of cultural niche construction by humans (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2023; Rouse, 2023). For instance, mapping serves as an aesthetic tool to engage with the NBS as implemented within a local NBA, guiding place-shaping practices increasingly recognised as essential for creating sustainable NBS (Raymond et al., 2023) (on place-shaping, see D.2.1, pp. 55ff). We explore an important consequence of this view in Chapter 6, namely that we conceptualize “care” as a correlate to “craft” and hence as an aesthetic attitude with ethical commitments (Saitō, 2023).

We summarise our general framework in Figure 1.1. The transition from NBS to NBA represents a fundamental paradigm shift. This new approach moves away from the linear causation framework of NBS, which implies a straightforward sequence of actions from design to implementation. However, experiences with NBS have shown that, in real-world scenarios, such linear frameworks often fall short due to the complexity of stakeholder relationships or the unpredictability of ecological conditions in the face of climate change. These challenges have led to a widely recognized need for various "co-" approaches, such as co-production (Sarkki et al., 2025). However, we contend that these approaches do not fully address the issue since the underlying linear causation framework remains intact. Instead, the "co-" concepts can be more effectively grounded in assemblage theory.

Figure 1.1. Shifting the paradigm: From NBS to NBA

We differentiate between the concept of NBS as an idea, plan, or vision that inspires initial human intervention, and the actual co-evolving assemblage of various constituents—both human and non-human, living and non-living. While the idea of NBS suggests a linear relationship from problem to solution, real-world interventions acknowledge the complex dynamics of emergent circular causation. In co-evolving NBAs, numerous phenomena arise that planners could not have anticipated. As we have systematically argued in previous deliverables, these phenomena facilitate adaptation to rapidly changing ecological conditions via creating affordances for multi-species co-habitation. These solutions are not solely designed by humans; instead, they are cultivated through careful crafting of the emerging NBAs. In this deliverable, we provide an overview of various skills and crafts identified in the COEVOLVERS LLs

that humans can employ effectively. This careful crafting further enhances and enriches the potential of the NBA to generate benefits for both human and non-human members, as it undergoes ongoing co-evolutionary change.

Careful crafting is a distinct action mode of intervening in coevolutionary processes, with the paradigmatic case of the craft of gardening (Schwarz, 2023). For COEVOLVERS, the critical challenge is how to fully account for a multispecies perspective and conceptualise NBS as multi-species NBAs. In practice, this requires methods that allow for the inclusion of non-human species in the NBA processes, going beyond a mere formal emphasis on biodiversity. As said, the various “co” concepts mostly tend to highlight participatory processes in which language is the prime medium, especially in the interactions between experts and non-experts. Recently, this has been expanded to include a wide range of art-based methods by which non-human views can be explored and represented by humans (as an example, see van Veen et al. 2024). Our concept of crafting an NBA goes beyond a methods-centred view (see D.1.2) in arguing that the NBA co-evolves an endogenous structure of nature-based governance, which includes political institutions but is primarily grounded in aesthetic forms of sensory governance (see D.2.2, pp. 161ff).

The fundamental concept that connects our various overarching terms is *embodiment*. This concept highlights two different meanings of "nature-based," which we outlined in the definition of nature-based governance in deliverable D.2.2 (see also Herrmann-Pillath, 2024a). In current and official definitions of NBS, the term is often regarded as relating to nature as a resource used to provide solutions for human society. However, our interpretation suggests that

- Firstly, the practices involved in NBS are based on an embodied relationality between humans and "nature," primarily understood as multi-species cohabitation, and
- Secondly, we view "nature" as a source of normative commitments and constraints for human action, serving as a medium for governance in ecosocial transformation.

There are various frameworks for understanding relationality in the literature (West et al., 2024). The analytical advantage of assemblage theory is that we can diagnose

various forms and expressions of relationality even within the same group of actors in the same general context of action. For example, at Cagliari LL, we can distinguish between bird watchers who engage with the birds via personal sensory experiences, which is an embodied form of relationality, or biologists who might tend towards a disembodied forms of scientific analysis (e.g. weight and plumage control), thus revealing an important difference between expert- and non-expert knowledge holders. Crafting an NBA is the art of creating meta-assemblages of implicit and explicit knowledge which sustain successful NBS practices in the long run, thus ultimately proving the original hypothesis about the instrumental rationality of the solution to a problem.

Figure 1.2: The spiralling dialectic of NBS and NBA

In summary, as illustrated in Figure 1.2, we envision a dialectical relationship between Nature-based solution and Nature-based assemblage that unfolds through time (indicated by t_1, \dots, t_n). The NBS is an idea developed by humans that prompts interventions to initiate an NBA. Once established, the NBA operates not on the principles of design and intervention but on the co-evolution of human and non-human

elements. In this co-evolution, humans engage in an ongoing learning process that continuously transforms the original idea of NBS. The relationship between NBS and NBA develops further, shifting the NBS from primarily an expert-driven idea to a transdisciplinary process of knowledge creation within the local community where the NBA is situated. This expanding knowledge informs careful crafting activities aimed at enhancing the co-evolutionary potential of the NBA, all while avoiding direct, goal-oriented design and intervention. The result is a spiralling process of shared flourishing. If all is well done...

1.2. Setting the scene: How the chapters connect, with illustrations

1.2.1. Assemblage theory in action: Emerging multi-species stakeholder assemblages

The second chapter of this deliverable introduces the concept of "Multi-Species Stakeholder Assemblages" (MSAs). The COEVOLVERS project follows a standard approach in project design and management by building on stakeholder analysis to launch co-creative processes in an NBS. Specifically, when considering the reconfiguration of the governance structures of an NBS, stakeholder analysis is the starting point. The stakeholder approach is typically interpreted in terms of human groups that are affected by an NBS and those who impact it. This approach tends to be inclusive, as vulnerable groups are often recognised as stakeholders, even if they may not be active participants or have legitimate representation. For instance, migrants are impacted by NBS initiatives; however, they may not voice their concerns and may even face discrimination. The inclusion of such groups primarily occurs through local political processes, which can be influenced by higher-level factors, such as legislative changes.

As discussed extensively in D.2.2, expanding the stakeholder approach to include non-human entities is challenging because human politics is primarily perceived as language-based (Meijer, 2019). D.2.2 presented arguments that address these limitations. To align with the practices of LLs, we are now exploring emerging solutions across these contexts. The main issue at hand is representation, and the typical

solution involves stewardship. This means that certain humans take on the role of representing non-humans, much like NGOs do in the fields of environmental conservation, nature protection, and animal rights. However, this form of representation does not resolve the question of how stewards effectively connect with non-humans.

In this regard, sustainability sciences have long recognised the need for transdisciplinarity (Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2006). This approach places expert and non-expert knowledge on equal footing. Representation can be based on expert knowledge about the functional needs and requirements of non-humans in the context of NBS, such as the species cohabiting with humans in a forest. The relationship of non-experts with non-humans often derives from a different kind of knowledge that is embodied, contextual, and local. This difference drives the productivity of transdisciplinary integration.

A critical issue in LL design and practices is that projects are primarily led by researchers who often face limited funding periods. Researchers come and go, leading to frustrations among local participants, who often feel that while researchers profit from their work, locals are asked to contribute time and effort without any compensation. For LL practices to be successful and sustainable, it is essential to create an environment that actively engages and incorporates local stakeholders in ongoing NBS concerns. Additionally, considering the non-human perspective, we can identify the role of MSAs. The meaning of this new concept can be further explored and defined:

- Firstly, long-term success in LL practices is achieved when they foster the coevolution of LL functions and stakeholder assemblages. This means that the composition of stakeholders is dynamic and changes over time. A successful LL creates a configuration that allows its practices to continue even after the funding period has ended. The term “assemblage” implies that this stakeholder composition is not necessarily the same as what was identified during the initial stage of the project, when stakeholder analysis typically occurs.
- Secondly, the concept of “multispecies” indicates that both human and non-human stakeholders are considered equal participants in the assemblage.

Given the initial lack of non-human representation, implementing the idea of the NBS amounts to creating conditions for the endogenous emergence of MSA.

- Thirdly, and most importantly, the MSA is viewed as an agent and a stakeholder, rather than just as a collection of separate individual units. This is a crucial step in how the stakeholder approach can bridge the gap between human and non-human interests. The MSA is recognised as an emergent complex agent within NBS as well as the associated political, social, and cultural processes.

This approach is based on assemblage theory, which acknowledges the emergent agency of complex composites while still presuming the autonomy of their constituents. Unlike the standard stewardship approach, the human members of MSAs do not engage autonomously with non-human entities; instead, they remain in an embodied relationality that grounds this emergent agency. In other words, the human/non-human duality is sublated in emergent MSAs, which are now considered as stakeholders of their own rights in stakeholder analysis. A standard example is regarding the assemblage of a dog, a dog-owner, and a forest as an emergent MSA. Clearly, this is not an ontological given, but depends on contextual conditions, and MSAs can evolve with the life-history of an NBA, including their dissolution, which does not imply that the constituent units vanish.

1.2.2. Peeking at sheeps and shepherds: a first view on crafting a COEVOLVERS NBA

In COEVOLVERS, a clear-cut example is the Barcelona LL, where sheep, shepherds, dogs, and local flora come together to form an NBA for wildfire control (Rovellada et al., 2025). The NBS is the idea of deploying animals to maintain firebreaks. Globally, wildfires have been increasing in both frequency and severity, often with catastrophic consequences for both humans and non-humans living in areas affected by these fires. It is widely recognised that a systemic control-based approach is ineffective for both preventing and combating wildfires. This ineffectiveness is due to the complex nature of wildfire causation, which cannot be simplified into clearly defined systematic mechanisms (Erni et al., 2024; Oliveira et al., 2021). Indeed, the causation of wildfire

can be considered as an assemblage of multiple factors, which is also reflected in the academic discourse that accompanies such events (Whitman and Holmgren, 2024). As a result, NBS are increasingly promoted as alternatives to conventional prevention and control measures. This approach creates a specific local combination of various natural components that help reduce the risk of wildfires (Regos et al., 2023). The Barcelona LL utilizes a natural grazing system where sheep and goats maintain firebreaks between human settlements and forests.

In this NBS, all umbrella concepts described in this deliverable are relevant. Unlike traditional practices where wild goats are utilized (Pareja et al., 2020), the herds must be controlled and owned by humans, specifically the shepherds, who provide ecosystem services as the primary "assemblers." These shepherds differ from conventional rural herders; they are often newcomers and entrepreneurs driven by business motives. As a result, they should be compensated for their services and seek additional income through selling milk or other products derived from the animals, such as meat. Additionally, they are required to keep their flocks within a clearly defined area, referred to as the firebreak, to optimise targeted feeding and grazing.

As in the stylized example of the mule and the cart, however, sheep and goats are not simply non-living

Box 1.1: Multispecies assemblage MSA at Barcelona LL

We have several relationships: shepherds with dogs, and sheep with goats. Both species play important roles. Goats tend to push sheep into new grazing areas that the sheep normally wouldn't explore. In turn, sheep help to calm the more restless goats. It's generally better to have more sheep than goats because goats can be a bit unpredictable. There are two types of dogs used in herding: herding dogs and protection dogs. The herding dog is often seen as an enemy by the sheep and goats, as its instinct is to control the flock and the sheep tend to avoid it. This dog is typically very calm; when it approaches the flock, the sheep instinctively move as a response. On the other hand, the protection dog is viewed differently. Many shepherds say that the protection dog feels like one of the sheep because it has grown up among them since it was a puppy. This dog sees itself as part of the herd and thus protects the flock, which the sheep accept. The herding dog is responsible for guiding the flock to the right grazing areas, while the protection dog ensures the safety of the flock against outside threats, such as wild animals or sheep thieves. However, in most cases like this one, threats from wolves and bears are not a concern. Herding dogs and protection dogs often work together without conflict. When raising a protection dog, it is essential to allow the dog to spend time with the flock so it learns to bond with them. This bonding occurs through instinct and genetics. Herding dogs, on the other hand, require training. Shepherds typically purchase dogs that are already trained, but a new dog can learn from experienced older dogs in the flock. The younger dog learns by observing and interacting with the older dogs, while the shepherd also trains and teaches them further. While herding dogs have natural instincts and genetics, they still need guidance from the shepherd to learn how to perform their roles effectively.

Elena Gorrriz and Marc Rovellada, Barcelona LL

mechanical tools that can be controlled by the humans. The NBS, although clearly defined in terms of composition, is a complex multispecies assemblage of five categories of living beings: the sheep, the goats, the herding dogs, the protection dogs and the shepherds (see box 1.1). The flock has to move according to functional needs, but the sheep also have their preferences and are attracted by neighbouring areas with richer nourishment. In other words, there are differences between the non-human cognitive maps of the territory and the official maps used for implementing the NBS. At the same time, the economic goals of shepherds are not necessarily compatible, because the optimum size of the flock for milk and meat production differs from the size required to implement the NBS in the targeted areas. In addition, since the flocks must be kept close to the settlements, there are many tensions and conflicts between different groups, such as those between shepherds and citizen dog owners whose dogs disturb the flock, or goats that intrude into private gardens. Such conflicts are not necessarily resolved by the fact that citizens are effectively the beneficiaries of the NBS; to the contrary, they may not even understand the rationale. Hence, we observe a complex stakeholder dynamic. How this structure unfolds through time very much depends on the narrative framing and the corresponding interpretation of various actions and events. For example, citizens may appreciate the local business emerging from the NBA and become regular buyers of products such as artisanal sausages. In these developments, the shepherds obtain a crucial role as they mediate many mechanisms, such as regulating flock size, selecting animals for breeding and so on. However, to manage the NBA, they effectively transform into members of an MSA, that is the multispecies assemblage of humans and non-humans who coproduce the NBS of fire prevention.

The case clearly illustrates the distinction between the NBS as an idea and the development of the corresponding NBA. Researchers cannot optimally design the NBA solely based on scientific knowledge; instead, they serve as instigators, moderators, and monitors. In the LL, they participate in the crafting process, which involves two types of key stakeholders: municipal administrators, who are considered disembodied stakeholders, and shepherds, who include both disembodied and embodied stakeholders. As we discuss in this deliverable, reflecting on this LL

experience shows that the long-term sustainability of the NBA requires establishing a network of embodied relationships among various human and non-human entities. Creating this network activates different aesthetic modes, including tangible products, such as artisanal goods sold to local residents and visitors. In summary, the NBS evolves into a viable NBA through a variety of multidimensional place-shaping activities.

In this brief case description, all umbrella concepts of this deliverable play a role. The concept of NBA requires new methods and media for representing NBS as multi-species assemblages. In the COEVOLVERS project, a key approach used across all LL is mapping in various forms, reflecting recent trends in cartography and mapping practices that have triggered substantial theoretical and methodological advances (Kitchin et al., 2013).

1.2.3. Mapping narratives, narrating maps

When COEVOLVERS was launched, the central significance of mapping was not yet fully in sight: Identifying mapping as a critical technique in crafting NBAs is a result of the continuous feedback between theory and LL practice.

NBA, by definition, are situated in physical space and time, distinguishing them from other concepts that might be considered immaterial, such as a patent for new technologies. NBA are coevolutionary and grounded in the locations where they are implemented by humans. However, in the moment of implementation, humans also relinquish some of their autonomous control. COEVOLVERS argues that this transition is not a loss or trouble; rather, it signifies that “nature” is invited to be recognised as an active agent in the NBA, or more accurately, as the totality of non-human species cohabiting with humans in the context of the NBA. Assemblage theory allows for the generalisation over the specific approach to “affordance mapping” championed by COEVOLVERS (see D.3.2) in conceptualising a map as a device to show the potentialities of a spatial unit, such as, for example, Murray Park, the site of the Scottish LL (see box 1.2).

Mapping has traditionally been human-centered, as it aims to meet human needs for representing the environment and facilitating communication. However, even these human-centered maps are also embodied, inviting actions such as following the directions they provide. Map design typically considers these actions, thereby smoothing the process of translating the map into real-world behaviour.

COEVOLVERS draws inspiration from various forms of counter-mapping conducted by scientists, activists, and artists, often focusing on vulnerable groups that are rendered invisible on dominant maps. In contrast, the coevolutionary approach emphasises the importance of recognising non-human entities as well.

Maps are clearly anthropocentric, as they address humans as the primary map readers. However, counter-mapping that includes non-human entities is a means of establishing embodied relationality between humans and non-humans. For example, as Cagliari LL demonstrates, involving local communities through sound mapping of selected areas of the Molentargius Park, in recording and mapping sounds of nature

(mostly avifauna and sound of wind and water flowing), can effectively facilitate the emergence of MSAs that include both humans and animals, especially birds. Modern

Box 1.2: Mapping affordances at Murray Park

Murray Park affords a complex and dynamic set of physical, emotional, and ecological relationships that shape both human and non-human experiences. For human actors, the park is a highly valued green space that supports physical health through walking, dog-walking, and outdoor recreation; emotional well-being through solitude, social connection, and a spiritual sense of immersion in nature; and educational affordances through activities such as birdwatching, fungi foraging, and environmental learning. Users describe it as “a haven” that fosters a profound sense of belonging and identity, often developed over decades of use. The park’s semi-wild quality, in contrast to the more formal Haughton Park situated alongside Murray Park, it is particularly appreciated for offering a sensory-rich, accessible, and intimate encounter with seasonal change, wildlife observation, and restorative peace. These affordances are relational: shaped by memories (e.g., grandparents walking with grandchildren), current uses (e.g., ecological stewardship), and aspirations for future conservation.

For non-human actors, Murray Park’s affordances emerge in the relative stability of its habitats and the microcosmic ecologies it supports. It is regarded as “in good condition” by ecologically literate observers, supporting key Scottish species such as red squirrels, owls, hedgehogs, and chanterelles. The woodland, affords shade, nesting, and seasonal markers of ecological rhythms, while the trees also becoming vulnerable actors under pressures from deer overgrazing, climate-exacerbated storm events (like Storm Arwen), and unsanctioned foraging and wood collection. The park thus functions as a co-constructed socio-ecological system: shaped by historical stewardship, contemporary multispecies interactions, and ongoing negotiations around access, care, and preservation. It affords humans a sense of continuity and purpose, while simultaneously affording non-humans habitat, resilience, and, at times, exposure. Affordances here are not static attributes of the landscape, but are dynamically constituted through shared practices of living, sensing, and managing across species lines.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

technology provides various methods for making non-human perspectives accessible to humans. One example is the virtual nature tool commonly used in COEVOLVERS and originally designed by the Hutton team, the leader of the Scottish LL. Digital technologies enable the integration of different sensory experiences and viewpoints, such as combining a topographical map with a soundscape or offering a perspective from ground level and on a smaller scale. Like modern GPS navigation, virtual nature encourages people to engage with their surroundings, even if in a vicarious way.

Conventional maps are static, but modern developments in cartography and technological advancements have made maps dynamic. This transformation has transformed maps into a form of narrative, enabling the connection between maps and storytelling (Caquard and Cartwright, 2014). Storytelling is a well-established method in ecosocial transformation and in exploring the relationships between people and nature. Thus, it has played a significant role in COEVOLVERS right from the beginning. The narrative form encompasses various media, particularly digital formats, including digital storytelling. The advantage of these media is that they open new avenues for transdisciplinary engagement, as stories are no longer just collected and archived by researchers but can be shared within the local learning community by everyone. COEVOLVERS researchers step in as scientific entrepreneurs and develop new digital tools, such as NatureNex.

COEVOLVERS approaches narratives in two fundamental ways: first, as an object of research, serving as empirical data, and second, as a medium through which research is reported and reflected upon. These two aspects are systematically connected. It is widely acknowledged that storytelling is often the most effective means to access emotions, embodied feelings, and the tacit dimensions of the practices of people living in a particular place and experiencing specific life conditions. This is particularly relevant for capturing vulnerabilities that can be difficult to express or diagnose. By extension, this approach also applies to the inclusion of non-humans. In the context of constituting MSAs, storytelling is an essential form that necessitates appropriate research methods, such as walking interviews and sensory walks, practices that are intensively used and explored in Tartu LL. By utilising these techniques, research

practices align more closely with the lived experiences of individuals, making the stories told by partners also reflect the narratives conveyed by the researcher.

Narrative analysis is a well-established method in ecolinguistics that systematically distinguishes between different forms of narratives (Stibbe, 2021).

A key distinction is made between event-based stories and narratives that shape perceptions of a situation and inspire corresponding actions. The latter type is particularly important for the design, implementation, and maintenance of NBS. If an NBS is viewed solely as a solution to human-defined problems, it may be challenging to sustain it beyond the project period. However, broader stakeholder commitment can be garnered when the NBS is framed within a narrative about “the multi-species city” (see box 1.3). This narrative, when shared by many

Box 1.3: The trouble with “multi-species” city at Tartu

In Tartu, the term "multispecies city" has not yet been officially adopted; however, the city is actively involved in biodiversity projects that are visibly supported by local authorities, contributing to a pro-biodiversity image. Despite this, there are some tensions surrounding these initiatives. Tartu has efforts to bring nature into the city center, and there is awareness and willingness to engage in biodiversity projects. However, in real situations, when real estate is being developed, biodiversity often becomes a weak argument. While it can be claimed that biodiversity exists, business interests frequently take precedence. There have been confrontations with the city council as it seems that the city is more focused on promoting biodiversity in the city center while neglecting the outskirts. Thus, the tension is not about biodiversity itself but rather about how the city is addressing it—focusing on the center and overlooking areas where our gardening projects are located. Initially, we aimed to include everyone living in the LL area, even those who might not have an interest in biodiversity. Eventually, we decided to narrow our focus to those who are genuinely interested. For this group, the concept of a multispecies city is not new. Our goal is to help them implement biodiversity practices effectively. We have experimented with various methods to embody these narratives and translate them into action. For example, during permaculture workshops, we discussed the needs of birds in a garden. Our approach emphasizes not just conveying a message but also putting those ideas into practice in real-world situations.

Riin Magnus, Tartu LL

local citizens and endorsed by community leaders, can foster greater engagement and support. Several COEVOLVERS LL employ story-telling in this way, as a cumulative building of an alternative vision of the place where the NBS is located, hence, as expressed in D.2.1, as a place-shaping activity.

1.2.4. The human agents: Entrepreneurs, craftspeople, caretakers

Stories are a preferred medium for recording and communicating entrepreneurial experiences. This deliverable argues that entrepreneurship is a key factor in making

knowledge actionable, particularly in addressing the challenge of sustaining NBS beyond the funding period (an aspect that has been seminal introduced in another, earlier HORIZON project (Kooijman et al., 2021). This argument applies to the narrower conception of entrepreneurship as market-oriented, since private sector engagement is essential for launching many NBS. For instance, private property owners often need to participate, and private entities must provide crucial inputs. Generally, financial sustainability cannot be guaranteed solely by public entities.

However, we extend the notion of entrepreneurship beyond this market context. This broader perspective is well-established in sustainability literature, including the concept of “institutional entrepreneurship” or “system entrepreneurship.” In collaborative ecosystems, various types of entrepreneurs play a vital role in connecting research with practice and anchoring NBS within the community. Special attention is given to the entrepreneurial role of researchers: scientific entrepreneurs act as brokers who arrange stakeholder collaborations and often adopt a serial approach to project management to overcome the limitations of short funding periods. The Beskydy LL is a paradigmatic case that we discuss in Chapter 5.

Institutional entrepreneurship is closely related to the concept of narratives, as institutions can be understood as enacting linguistically mediated perspectives of the world. Indeed, the NBS, as an idea, is a narrative comparable to the “business plan” in the market context, which aims to demonstrate how the idea can be made “actionable” (Beckert, 2016). This understanding of institutions has been systematically developed by philosophers, such as John Searle, with his notion of the “status function” (Searle, 2011, 1995). There is a long intellectual tradition that conceptualises institutions as “second nature,” following Hegel’s terminology (Basso and Herrmann-Pillath, 2024). However, this tradition has been somewhat overlooked in the so-called “New Institutional Economics” approaches to institutions, which have significantly influenced theories of governance, as discussed in D.2.2.

COEVOLVERS advocates for the concept of Nature-based governance, emphasizing the role of embodied mechanisms in the institutionalisation of NBS. The conceptualising of the NBS as a “Nature-based assemblage” moves away from viewing NBS purely as “solutions” designed by humans, where there is a clear-cut

causal relationship between mechanisms and objectives (for example, street trees intended to lower temperatures in urban areas). In real NBS practice, most NBS are now recognised as multifunctional, with purposes that extend beyond human goals, reflecting biodiversity requirements. This multifunctionality undermines the idea that an NBS serves as a straightforward "solution" to a clearly defined problem. Instead, the NBA should be viewed as a coevolving, multi-species assemblage that inherently generates functions beyond the initial "trigger" function it was designed to address.

In this context, humans play a significant role as "craftspeople" or "artisans," taking on various roles such as instigators, supervisors, therapists, and more. We refer to this process as "crafting an NBA." This terminology diverges from the standard concept of "planning," such as in "urban planning." Crafting an NBA represents a distinct form of multi-species niche construction (see D.2.2., pp. 28ff) within the specific institutional framework of an NBS (as designated in the institutionalising narrative). In employing the term "craft," we emphasize the individuality and contextuality of an NBA and the creative process that results in such individual assemblages of people, things and non-human living beings. An essential dimension of craft is care: The crafting needs to be done carefully. Care is understood in a wider sense, including the technical aspects. However, a key aspect of care is being attentive to vulnerabilities that emerge in the process of NBA. Moreover, care in crafting is expressed in the aesthetics of the NBA, like the aesthetics of an artisanal product, say, a piece of pottery. The aesthetics manifests the care in crafting, and it invites the careful handling of the NBA by its stakeholders, now seen as caretakers.

Returning to Barcelona LL as a central example in this overview, the conventional view is that urban planners implement an NBS to create and maintain firebreak areas near human settlements. They typically focus on functional design aspects, such as the appropriate size of livestock herds and the space required for pens, as well as the incentives for individuals to engage in shepherding within the framework of the NBS. However, if we consider the NBS as a product of crafting an NBA, we highlight the complexity of multi-species interactions and the importance of the evolving stakeholder structure that can sustain an NBA in the long run. Crafting involves the co-production of an NBA by various parties, with some playing more prominent

leadership roles. For instance, the long-term acceptance and institutional legitimacy of an NBA can face challenges due to potential tensions and conflicts over the behaviours of non-human participants. Some shepherds may actively share their experiences and ways of living in harmony with animals through social media, generating significant interest and positive engagement. This suggests that, broadly speaking, narratives can transform technical NBS into an NBA where humans and non-humans coexist. Concurrently, the narratives surrounding the NBS may evolve, shifting from viewing it merely as a “solution” to recognising the MSA of the NBA (i.e., the sheep, shepherds, and dogs) as integral members of the community, deserving of voice and recognition. In this transformation, the economic use of animals can further enhance these embodied relationships, such as when enjoying the flavour of locally produced artisanal cheese. In many ways, crafting the NBA activates aesthetic dimensions of the assemblage, for example, children enjoying the interaction with sheep, adults indulging in nature when hiking, and both appreciating the taste of artisanal food products.

The crafting of the NBA is mediated through linguistic channels that enact embodied institutions, often referred to as “habits” in what is called “old institutional economics” informed by pragmatist philosophy (Hiedanpää and Bromley, 2016). The fire-prevention NBA becomes institutionalised not by the regulatory mandates of public authorities, but through the co-creative interplay between various actors who communicate with each other. This communication encompasses not only linguistic exchanges but also diverse forms of interaction between human and non-human actors — for example, shepherds guiding their flock with the help of their dogs, as well as the communication that takes place between the dogs themselves.

1.3. Conclusion

In summary, this deliverable concludes the theory-practice “hop, step, and jump” movement of WP2 in collaboration with all COEVOLVERS. The five umbrella concepts have proven to be effective tools for systematizing the COEVOLVERS experience across LLs and generating new ideas for further development. Making sense of LL

practices also motivated adding a new theoretical tool to the coevolutionary theory as developed in previous deliverables, namely assemblage theory. Taken together, this motivates the paradigm shift from NBS to NBA. The paradigm shift enables to take a strategic turn in LL practices: In which direction can these practices coevolve beyond the project time horizon?

One notable strategic insight is the critical role of children in the long-term formation of MSAs that we explore in Chapter 2. Initially, when COEVOLVERS started, children were not prioritised in the analysis and design stages. They were mostly viewed as a vulnerable group and passive stakeholders, if at all. While children were mentioned in various contexts, they were often regarded as a marginal group—for instance, they tended to be tested first in an educational Role Board Game before “serious” engagement with other stakeholders: There has been no research on children in COEVOLVERS. However, through the D.2.3 work and further interviews with Living Labs, we recognised that children play a very significant role in sustaining NBA over the long run. The reasons for this shift in perspective are numerous and can be categorised within the MSA framework. Children have a deeply embodied relationship with other living beings that differs from that of adults. They connect with parents through embodied relationality, enabling a form of “nested stewardship” that works through the interactions of children, parents, and non-human entities. Furthermore, as children grow up alongside an NBA, they develop connections to these environments, with the NBA acting as a place-shaping force. Therefore, children should not be viewed as merely passive actors; they are essential constituents of MSAs, embedding NBAs in an open arrangement of nature-based governance. In the next chapter, we detail how this insight emerged in COEVOLVERS LLs and can be seen as a major result on how to envisage follow-up research.

Chapter 2: The coevolutionary approach to multi-species stakeholder assemblages

2.0 Chapter summary

A key aspect of the coevolutionary approach to NBS is the concept of the endogenous emergence of multi-species stakeholder assemblages (MSA). This chapter explains the fundamental principles and includes real-life examples. For MSA, embodied relationships with both living and non-living non-humans are essential. We differentiate between embodied and disembodied stakeholder relationships, aligning this distinction with the framework of embodied governance described in deliverable D.2.2. We introduce basic categories for stakeholder analysis: the methodological distinction between emic and etic perspectives on "stakes," concepts of vulnerability and affectability, and the duality of legality and legitimacy. Children serve as the paradigmatic case of embodied representation within stakeholder assemblages, such as the relationships between children and non-humans, and between parents and children, both of which are embodied and thus contribute to forming an MSA. By considering embodiment, we can address the challenges of conceptualising stewardship as representation. The chapter also develops criteria for identifying MSAs. We conclude that the design of NBS should always include institutionalised inclusion of children as members in MSA.

2.1. Introduction

2.1.1. Children as a paradigmatic case of vulnerable stakeholders[†]

This chapter further develops the coevolutionary approach to stakeholder analysis as expounded in D.2.2, pp. 152-160 and extends it to the assemblage approach. While we present many observations on the various COEVOLVERS LLs, we pay special attention to one paradigmatic case, the children in the COEVOLVERS overseas cousin Carriacou Island, to which we devote various boxes accompanying the main text that present interview materials. COEVOLVERS have maintained close contact and exchange with the activists of the Kido Foundation, such as transferring methods of digital story-telling. This chapter highlights the reverse flow of inspiration and insight:

[†] In this chapter, we partly discuss the work done by COEVOLVERS' overseas partners. This is not original research conducted within the COEVOLVERS project; rather, we are reporting on their experiences and practices, which we gathered from interviews and on-site exchanges. Drawing inspiration from these insights, we assess various activities at LLs that engage children, extending beyond the COEVOLVERS research agenda which did not include children.

The experience of Kido Foundation has made COEVOLVERS aware of the central role of children in crafting an NBS as an NBA in the long run (box 2.1).

Most NBS as ideas are conceived with the future in mind, aiming to persist for generations, such as newly developed urban parks. This principle is especially relevant to the COEVOLVERS' holistic view on crafting NBAs as infrastructural landscaping. However, these solutions must also adapt to the rapid changes occurring in the environment due to the increasing volatility of the Earth's climate. This

Box 2.1: The children of Carriacou

In Carriacou, children have been actively engaged in various environmental and social projects since the 1990s through the WYF-Kido Foundation Research Triad (Youth-Wildlife-Flora). They take part as life actors in direct learning experiences, problem-solving, and hands-on projects that integrate nature conservation with social entrepreneurship. Children's engagement with digital cameras has reshaped their interactions with the environment, making them more observant and careful. Children come from different parts of the island of Carriacou and are invited to take photos from the natural environment. An important location to feel nature connection is the so-called Kido Eco Room, a breezy hilltop hall facing the Caribbean Sea and immersed in the forest.

Marina Fastigi, KIDO Foundation

situation suggests that NBAs must depend on the future abilities of humans to create and maintain practices that ensure their long-term sustainability. NBA evolve alongside the practices of the people who live with, and often within, these environments. One key stakeholder group in the context of NBAs is children, as they will face the future impacts of today's NBS interventions. It is crucial for them to develop skills, capabilities and even fundamental values stances that may differ from current societal needs and demands (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, IPBES, 2022). Children are vital participants in the ongoing crafting of an NBA, and this important role has been highlighted in the experience of the Kido Foundation.

Children and other living beings often hold similar structural positions in society, which is why they are frequently referenced in animal rights literature (Deckha, 2021). This is particularly true for young children, who are perceived as lacking the cognitive and linguistic abilities necessary to participate in community decision-making. As a result, they are represented by their caregivers, primarily their parents: The parent-child dyad is a basic assemblage to consider. Children can be structurally compared to sentient animals, both of which deserve attention and care but are often denied recognition as

active stakeholders in society. This structural similarity includes patterns of vulnerability (Russell and Fawcett, 2020). For humans, children embody the universal vulnerability to the future consequences of ecological changes resulting from current interventions. While these vulnerabilities are generally certain, the specifics are highly uncertain. Consequently, children's current stakes in society are ill-defined regarding their particular needs and demands. This uncertainty also applies to other beings and their descendants. Thus, children evoke the evolutionary openness of the future, illustrating both potential risks and opportunities.

This observation highlights the distinction between universal vulnerability and specific vulnerability (Martin, 2021). Children, as a group, are particularly vulnerable to future environmental changes compared to other populations. Additionally, certain social statuses, such as being a migrant child, contribute to a specific vulnerability that these children face relative to their peers. Similarly, while various living beings share a universal vulnerability in a "common world" with humans, some species, especially endangered ones, experience a heightened level of vulnerability. This raises the question of whether these formal analogies suggest that children and other living beings are more likely to form connections based on shared, distributed agency in similar contexts, such as co-habiting in disadvantaged neighbourhoods (Malone, 2016).

Unlocking children's potential for ecosocial transformation and NBS practices requires a comprehensive approach that spans their entire socialisation journey (box 2.2). This is particularly crucial within the institutional context of early childhood and school education, extending from preschool to young adulthood. Such an approach can be integrated into community initiatives that encourage children to become familiar with their local ecosystem (Flanagan et al., 2019; Russ et al.,

Box 2.2: Children presaging future roles as adults

Children's ideas have directly shaped Carriacou NBS projects. For example: Plastic Waste Reuse: Designing and building floating elements for a catamaran using collected waste plastics. The children designed and tested for several weeks all the parts planned for the sailing boat construction. Eventually their Kido Cat sailed its unique design flawlessly several miles at the yearly Carriacou sailing Regatta. The 11-year-old chief child proponent of this mini-catamaran is now an accomplished Marine Engineer living and working abroad with much concern about limiting shipping pollution and Global Warming.

Marina Fastigi, KIDO Foundation

2015). In these initiatives, children can engage with other living beings through various activities, such as playful interaction in early childhood and stewardship during their teenage years.

In examining the role of children in ecosocial transformation, researchers frequently discuss the concepts of “becoming” and “common world,” as highlighted by scholars like Latour and Haraway (Policarpo et al., 2018; Taylor and Pacini-Ketchabaw, 2015). Children exist in a continuous state of becoming, which encompasses not only the fundamental idea of “becoming human” (Tomasello, 2019) but also their socialisation and acculturation processes that enable them to become recognized members of their communities (Bogdan, 2010; Zawidzki, 2013). Whether this process allows for an autonomous and creative role for children largely depends on cultural contexts and pedagogical beliefs. It is worth noting that, in many cases, children develop autonomous relationships with other beings in their communities, relationships that are often acknowledged by adults and, at times, positively valued. A prominent example of this is the bond children form with family pets (Tipper, 2011). Their unique connection with these animals can justify independent actions and decisions on the children's part which are recognised and accepted by adults. However, such leadership often does not extend beyond the immediate family, as there is a common belief that children's development requires adult guidance and structure. This includes the imposition of adult interpretations of children's relationality and its educational modelling according to adult relationality, even well-intended (Murphy, 2018).

In this chapter, we regard children as a paradigmatic case of coevolving multi-species assemblages. This does not necessarily mean that assemblages engaging children persist through time, but that children can become instigators and supporters of other assemblages in the future when growing up. Viewing NBS as NBA means considering the entire lifetime of an NBA, which typically corresponds to human life cycles of socialisation and generational change. We argue that in designing and implementing NBS strategically, elements that focus on children must become an integral part.

2.1.2 Two ideal-types of stakeholder

The chapter combines with a separate paper by Sarkki and co-authors that will explore stakeholder relationships in LLs. The difference is that the paper takes the standard conception of stakeholder and stakeholder relationships for granted as expounded in the literature (e.g. (Reed et al., 2009; Zingraff-Hamed et al., 2020)). This perspective aligns with conventional conceptions of governance, which view governance as a system of rules, rights, entitlements, incentives, and legal constraints that impact the behaviour of agents in accordance with certain functional goals (Bennett and Satterfield, 2018). Accordingly, stakeholder relationships can be analyzed in a matrix of two dimensions where

- one dimension, the material, relates to the causal interdependencies by which a certain state of the world affects an agent, and how this agent affects the state, thus creating a “stake” in this state;
- the other dimension is about voice and recognition in the governance domain, which constitutes the stakeholder as a concerned party in what is fundamentally a political process of setting, monitoring and enforcing rules.

Within the governance domain, we need to take account of the role of hierarchies and mediating agencies so that often we observe triadic structures in stakeholder relationships, for example, when a municipality mediates between users and suppliers of an NBS: A COEVOLVERS example is the Barcelona LL where the municipality mediates and governs the relationship between shepherds and resident citizens. In the case of children, various caretakers mediate their stakeholder relationships, with parents on top.

This duality is a powerful systematising device that easily connects to NBA practices in which material structures and processes are designed and engineered by human agents acting in what they mostly conceive as a distinct social ontology of rules and institutions. In such a setting, the inclusion of non-human agents boils down to the question of how these can be represented in the governance domain and how they relate to the diverse human actors in a governance structure (Hernandez-Santin et al., 2023; Kortetmäki et al., 2023). This question makes sense in practice, where the

duality functions as an implicit performative structure that separates humans from non-humans. Hence, the conventional stakeholder approach is also needed in research to ensure the compatibility of the scientific approach with the sociopolitical context, an important condition for making the former actionable.

This chapter goes beyond the conventional social ontology since the previous deliverables have shown that a coevolutionary approach must overcome the Cartesian dualism between materiality and institutions, tying up with a more general turn to embodiment in social theory (Basso and Herrmann-Pillath, 2024). The conventional view remains useful when considering the performative practices of humans in their domain and understanding its stakeholder politics. However, when it comes to the question of how non-human stakeholders can be included in these practices, just taking the conventional social ontology for granted is problematic, as has been shown in detail in D.2.2 (Houston et al., 2018). Two simple steps collapse their dualism.

- First, the distinction between human and non-human must be discarded in developing a general understanding of agency in stakeholder relationships, implying that the identification of agency is what makes stakeholders, rather than the other way around. The alternative view builds on the rich literature on material agency (Malafouris, 2013) and various approaches to “agencement” in Actor-network theory (Latour, 2005) and assemblage theory (DeLanda, 2006). In assemblages, the human/non-human distinction collapses and is substituted by a flat ontology of various material entities arranged in a fluid orchestration of emerging agencies which are themselves evolving through time and vary in space (Bennett, 2010; Deleuze and Guattari, 2009).
- Second, materiality and rules are seen as ontologically intertwined in the general concept of embodied governance that is grounded in various strands of thought, such as Bourdieu’s habitus (Bourdieu, 2019) or Foucault’s governmentality (Foucault, 2004). As elaborated in D.2.2, embodied governance takes specific forms such as sensory governance (Schulte-Römer, 2023) or Nature-based governance (Herrmann-Pillath, 2024a). In such approaches, the analytical separation between stakeholders and the social system to which they relate withers away, which is fundamental for

conventional notions of governance. As a consequence, the stakeholders' *agencements* become endogenous to the governance structure, while also being pivots of that structure.

In sum, and in the simplest way, we can distinguish between embodied and disembodied forms of governance and stakeholder relationships, a distinction that relates to other fundamental ontological dualities, such as inter-action versus intra-action (Barad, 2007). Disembodiment implies drawing boundaries between actors and their material and institutional context, thereby silencing all forms of relationality; embodiment, on the other hand, means that actors and their context are relationally merged in assemblages (Eyster et al., 2023). Stakeholder analysis must work in both dimensions, since forms of embodiment and disembodiment are endogenous to governance institutions: For example, property institutions can have powers of disembodiment (Herrmann-Pillath, 2024b), such as orchestrated via technologies of mapping that we scrutinize in the next chapter,

This chapter focuses on the implications of such a view for LL practices in NBAs as developing in COEVOLVERS, instigated by the ideas of NBS as envisioned in the project proposal. As said, the conventional framework is performative, implying that the approach in the companion paper directly aligns with what LL actors perceive as their social reality. The chapter is “critical” in Horkheimer’s (2011) sense, meaning that we identify an emerging alternative social reality and ultimately contribute to transforming this reality by viewing it from a different perspective. In other words, whereas the companion paper looks at both disembodied and embodied stakeholder relationships, this chapter focuses on the latter.

The major theoretical innovations of this chapter that move beyond the previous WP 2 deliverables are:

- Introducing the concept of “multispecies stakeholder assemblages” (MSAs) that incorporate both non-human living and non-living entities and that are endowed with material agency and agencement that render them into political agents in LL communities;

- Understanding NBAs as evolving structures that endogenously generate MSAs that assume functions in sustaining them. Accordingly, MSAs are a pivotal element in the Nature-based governance of NBAs (D.2.2., pp. 161-172);
- Transcending the conventional notion of voice and representation in stakeholder politics, the human element in MSAs is approached as staying in embodied relationships with the other elements, effectively transforming the exclusive human voice into inclusive MSA intentionality and voice;
- Grounding human entanglement in MSAs on empathetic relationships of humans caring for other elements and nurturing resonant relationships with them, such that care is experienced as reciprocal. Care is defined as second-order affectability, and stakes as first-order affectability: Caring emanates from affectability by the other's affectability. Vulnerability is a specific form of affectability.

In relation to performative practices, the conventional approach remains a powerful analytical view in the case that human actors do not define themselves as members of MSAs, such as administrators who perceive themselves as functional experts for a particular domain or businesspeople who pursue goals of profit: Both cases count as disembodied stakeholder relationships. In COEVOLVERS, such fixed roles are set in methods such as the role-board game (D.2.2., pp. 18, 164). Accordingly, different from the companion paper, this chapter only looks at the coevolutionary novelties and potentials in stakeholder relationship analysis across COEVOLVER LLs. The full view of the stakeholder theme is only emerging in combining this chapter with the companion paper.

The chapter relates to other chapters of D.2.3 in several respects. By introducing the multiplicity of views in the etics/emics duality, we can identify “nature-based entrepreneurs” (D.2.2., pp. 190ff) as humans who adopt a leadership role in creating and sustaining MSAs. The arena is often the acting political bodies in NBS design, such as urban planning departments, which ties up with Chapter 6 on crafting NBAs. Another bridge is to the mapping chapter, as we also highlight the role of spatial embedding in triggering and stabilising MSAs. MSAs can often be mapped in reference to conventional spatial representations of an NBA.

In referring to LL practices, the chapter identifies practices that ground, foster and sustain MSAs and that transform conventional approaches to stakeholder politics into patterns of nature-based governance. As in D.2.2, we refer to various practices and tools developed in other WPs, however, we arrange them according to their role in the co-creation of MSAs by the various actors in the multi-species arena of stakeholder politics in the COEVOLVERS LLs.

2.2. Legitimacy and justice

An NBS is typically designed and implemented by humans, often by a specific organization such as a municipality. Even if we consider the case of a genuine wilderness, this turns into an NBS if it is left wild intentionally. Accordingly, in the widest sense, NBS are political, and therefore stakeholder analysis applies. The conventional approach to stakeholder analysis focuses on human political mechanisms of voice, rights, or protest driven by stakeholder concerns. Clearly, these categories cannot easily include the non-human perspective, thus tying up with the general debate over ecological democracy (D.2.2, 138-148) (Hernandez-Santin et al., 2023).

2.2.1 Legitimate versus illegitimate stakeholders

If we start our discussion in this way, the issue of legitimacy looms large (D.2.2. p. 154) (Reed et al., 2009). Stakeholders can be included and recognised in the formal NBS process, hence are seen as legitimate by a group that implements the NBS. Modern approaches to urban planning are participatory and open to many kinds of stakeholders, which is also becoming the standard for NBS (Brokking et al., 2021; Diep et al., 2022). However, there can also be illegitimate stakeholders in the neutral sense, as they are not yet recognized, which is mostly the case for animals in relation to business organizations (Smart, 2022). There are also different degrees of legitimacy. For example, at Cagliari LL all animals and plants in the Molentargius Park are protected by law, but at the same time species differ in terms of being recognised

as “endangered”, which implies that more resources (time, attention etc.) are spent on them.

The strong meaning of legitimacy would even imply that certain stakeholders are defined as illegitimate for some normative reasons. For example, newly arriving foreign immigrants may be seen as illegitimate stakeholders as long as they are not included in the process (neutral, barring inclusion, such as realizing the use of green spaces for family barbecues), or a populist municipality may declare them as illegitimate (anti-immigration stance, such as banning migrant barbecues from green spaces). In the future, in Beskydy LL, deer may become illegitimate due to the damage they do to tree seedlings, which are an essential part of efforts to change spruce monocultures into mixed-age and mixed-species forests.

Box 2.3: Legitimising alien species at the Island of Cres

The invasive game, wild boar and fallow deer populations have a direct impact on the management and maintenance of Cres habitats, i.e. plant and animal species within the Natura 2000 ecological network. In addition to the indirect pressure on biodiversity manifested through more intensive abandonment of sheep farming and the consequent overgrowth of pastures, the animals mentioned above also have a direct impact on the preservation of certain habitats. Also, non-native wild ungulates are a threat to sheep due to the interspecies competition (spatial and nutritional overlap), which is especially evident in fallow deer, causing overgrazing of pastures and drying up of natural puddles. So far, the measures taken to remove wild boar and fallow deer from the island have not produced the expected results. The management of the eradication process is left to individual hunting lessees lacking cooperation and coordination, and in the implementation they use almost exclusively measures from the domain of hunting described in the corresponding hunting management documents.

Until now, the problem has not been approached systematically, with the involvement of the professional and scientific community, either those specialized in the field of hunting, or those specialized in nature protection. The impact of non-native game on the island's ecosystem and biodiversity is generally neglected and has been expanding. The Government (several ministries that are directly or indirectly in charge of the problem) has changed some laws according to which these species now can "domicile" as autochthonous species, and so legalise the introduction of these animals into the Game Management Plan and the problem seems to “disappear.”

Ugo Tojć, Cres small scale pilot

Hence, the question of legitimacy matters in the context of expanding the notion of stakeholder to the non-human domain: For example, animal rights activists may regard an invasive alien species as a legitimate stakeholder, whereas ecologists declare them as illegitimate. This example demonstrates that stakeholder analysis cannot be conducted in an objectively, even though ecologists may invoke a scientific basis. Moreover, the dynamics of stakeholder politics can result in shifting and fuzzy borders between legitimacy and illegitimacy (see box 2.3): For example, one of the

most abundant invasive species, the fish Round Goby, is increasingly seen as a commercial opportunity by fishermen in the Baltic Sea (Puntila et al., 2018). Interestingly, in this case, a process of disembodiment may neutralise embodied concerns for other members of an ecosystem.

Illegitimacy is a status that creates distinct vulnerability. Other actors may feel legitimised to take actions that are not in the illegitimate actor's interest, and other third-party sanctions do not apply to such actions. At the same time, the illegitimate actor may be denied voice

and recognition in the political processes of designing and implementing an NBS. In the NBS context, there are many issues of illegitimacy of non-human entities, since the design approach as such may define what is legitimate in relation to the intended function. For example, in designing an urban garden according to certain needs and ecological functions, some plants may be regarded as “weeds” (Triman, 2019), or some animals as “pests” (D.2.2., p. 117). These non-humans become vulnerable to human violent action, such

Box 2.4: NBA stakeholder politics at Cres

The interests of the animals introduced on the island of Cres in mid 80s of the last centuries (wild boars /*Sus scrofa*/ and fallow deer /*Dama dama*/) are represented in first instance by the hunters. The purpose for introducing these nonnative species (by definition they could be even called invasive species) was to develop hunting tourism on the island. At the beginning, the animals were reared in a confined hunting ground where foreign hunters (mostly Italians) were invited for hunting. Once the fence has deteriorated (after approximately 5 years) the animals escaped and the business with the foreign hunters started to decline. The animals were more and more present throughout the island and the local hunters started to change their interest from the small game to the big game. Over the years they have developed a passion for big game, particularly for wild boars, and have become biased in the discussion about their (negative) impact on the biodiversity and the local economy. From the perspective of the islanders, there is the impression that even public institutions, like the ministry in charge for the nature protection represents the interests of these animals more than the biodiversity in total. Also, there is the impression that the Directorate for Hunting always overcome the Directorate for Agriculture which are part of the same Ministry of Agriculture. At the end of the day, only the farmers directly advocate for the sheep, but they have far less lobbying capacity than the hunters. The general public on the island is supporting the sheep breeding community, since the sheep farming has, over centuries, shaped the landscape of the island and conditioned the development of tangible and intangible heritage which is now important part of the local identity. Based on the feeling of the local community, the local authorities (municipalities) are also representing the interest of the sheep.

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as killing garden slugs. A clear COEVOLVERS case of such tensions is the small-scale pilot on the Island of Cres (see D.2.2, box 4.13 and box 2.3), where wild boars

had been introduced as an alien species and started to cause considerable damage to local sheep herders. However, patterns of legitimacy shifted because professional and recreational hunters became stakeholders in the wild boar populations.

In a most general sense, a stake means that someone considers an aspect of the NBS important for realising their interests and, therefore, might aim to influence how the NBA works (Ferreira et al., 2020; Mitincu et al., 2023). Since the interests of various stakeholders may not converge or harmonize, there is always the potential for conflict: The NBA is a contested

Box 2.5: Children pinpoint the tension between legality and legitimacy

In Carriacou, unlike adults, who often view nature as a resource, children exhibit curiosity and openness to learning. Unlike adults, who often treat nature as something they can use, e.g. wood for building or charcoal, hunting and eating animals, children are open and interested. For example, after asking questions about how many of them ate turtle eggs or iguanas, we slowly started discussing about impacts...a process of co-learning about consequences, such as consuming heavy metals in the flesh of hunted sea turtles and their eggs. When the children saw a fisherman who had just caught a sea turtle (a critically endangered species) they asked why would he eat it or sell it knowing that the creature was poisoned by pollution? Adults often act in contradiction with their factual knowledge, whilst children cannot comprehend how one could act against one's well-being.

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ecopolitical arrangement (see box 2.4). However, as said, this raises the thorny issue of whether politics is human-only: If yes, we cannot expand the stakeholder concept beyond the human domain. We can turn this argument around and argue that stakeholder analysis is a step towards expanding politics to the more-than-human. In this perspective, employing stakeholder analysis in LLs is transformative in redefining the LL as a multi-species political community, at first sight, independent from whether there are explicit political mechanisms for negotiating stakes already in place (D.2.2., 144f). This marks a critical turn in stakeholder analysis: it no longer assumes the stakeholder structure as given, but instead identifies and, in an action research approach, even creates new stakeholders. In other words, via identifying non-human stakeholders, pressure is put on the human political domain to develop mechanisms of representation and voice. COEVOLVERS deliverable D.3.3 (Pittaway et al., 2025) presents an overview of water challenges across all LLs, where some also affect non-humans, eventually eliciting human reaction. For example, in the Barcelona LL, sheep are dependent on a sufficient water supply, which cannot be guaranteed in dry years;

hence, shepherds and public authorities are under pressure to find solutions. Via the construction of the NBS of “wildfire eaters”, sheep become recognized stakeholders in the water infrastructure. This is a highly significant step to expanding the scope of the NBA.

As we see, stakeholder analysis cannot be done without considering the normative dimension and is, hence, an expression of the coevolutionary approach as belonging to the normative sciences (D.2.2, pp. 14-28). If we distinguish between legitimacy and legality, we refer the latter to the actualized rules of governing the NBS: Some stakeholders may be formally recognised as having a voice in NBS matters, while others are not. Here, we connect to the standard view on governance in relation to stakeholder politics (see box 2.6).

The distinction between legality and legitimacy matters a lot for NBS

since some non-human species have a specific legal status, such as protected species, which defines them formally as stakeholders even if they are not themselves taking this role with an active voice in the governance institutions (e.g. flamingoes in Cagliari LL; flying squirrels in Turku LL). Other human organisations are legally obliged to represent them as such. These cases are of special interest since they create assemblages of non-humans and human organisations by legal construction. Legal

Box 2.6: Conflicting stakeholder claims at Cagliari

Certain vulnerable groups face significant barriers in fully accessing and enjoying the Molentargius Park. These groups include individuals with physical disabilities, such as those who use wheelchairs or have limited mobility, due to the lack of continuous accessible pathways, ramps, and adapted rest areas. Elderly visitors may also encounter difficulties navigating uneven terrain and reaching key observation points. Additionally, visually impaired individuals often lack access to tactile maps, audio guides, or proper signage, which limits their independent exploration. Families with young children, especially those with strollers, may struggle with unpaved or narrow paths. Addressing these accessibility challenges is essential to ensure equitable use of the park for all. All activities organized in the Parks need to be authorized but violations of these rules are frequent: families organize birthday parties without permission, as well as local sport associations and social NGOs. The perception of public space in Molentargius Park is shaped by subtle but significant territorial conflicts among different user groups, which can impact how the park is experienced and managed. As a multifunctional area that serves both ecological conservation and recreational purposes, tensions sometimes arise between environmental protection efforts and public use demands. Birdwatchers and conservationists may perceive the presence of cyclists, joggers, or large gatherings as disruptive to wildlife, while recreational users might feel restricted by access limitations and regulations aimed at preserving sensitive habitats. Additionally, there can be perceived inequalities in the use of space, with certain areas more accessible or welcoming to specific groups, such as tourists or sports enthusiasts, while local residents or vulnerable populations may feel marginalized. These tensions reflect broader issues of governance, inclusion, and competing interests, underscoring the need for participatory planning and clear communication to foster a shared sense of stewardship and respect for the park's diverse functions.

Oriana Mosca and Ferdinando Fornara, Cagliari LL

triggers can transform non-linguistic behavioural signs of non-humans into a vicarious voice of the organizations. However, in the human domain, this does not automatically mean that all other human stakeholders regard these constructs as legitimate: For example, certain formally recognised rights of protected species may be rejected by farmers. In COEVOLVERS we observe various constellations of this kind: For example, since the saline park at Cagliari is a protected area, certain non-humans are even represented as legitimate stakeholders, while certain recreational uses by humans may lack formal recognition, despite meeting other vulnerabilities.

2.2.2. Justice in coevolving stakeholder relationships

The normative conception of legitimacy goes beyond formal governance structures and refers to the question of recognising stakeholders to general principles of justice. This is Rancière's view of politics as a struggle for recognition and inclusion (Rancière, 2004). A stakeholder may even have a disruptive impact on the NBS by employing expressive means that are beyond the legal governance scheme. How can we judge such an action as a just action that must be taken as a voice demanding legitimate recognition?

Since NBS are universally expected to enact reciprocity between people and nature (D.2.1. p. 69), we can most generally define an NBS stakeholder as an entity who is legitimised for staying in a reciprocal relationship with those entities, typically humans, who raise a claim on it: In NBS ideas, this claim is on specific ecosystem services. That means any entity that contributes to the ecosystem services that define the NBS has a legitimate stake in reciprocity, as a principle of fairness and mutual benefit or "win-win." In general NBS standards, this is reflected in the requirement that NBS should not only fulfil a certain function in the human interest, but also meet biodiversity criteria (IUCN, 2020). Biodiversity is an abstract and formal criterion that, in practice, needs to be specified in terms of concrete stakes that various species have in the NBS. We meet another form of tension between disembodiment and embodiment. At this point, the distinction between legality and legitimacy is valid again, since we need to distinguish between those entities that are recognised in the reciprocal

generation of specific ecosystem services and those entities that are affected without being part of this human-designed and defined structure of the NBS: These are the stakeholders in the NBA as distinguished from the NBS as idea. Consider the creation of extensive urban forests for climate change adaptation. The biodiversity norm can be met through either the intentional design of species diversity in the forest or by rewilding, which allows for unplanned evolution, such as the immigration of wild animals. Whether these animals are considered legitimate stakeholders of the forest remains open to a political process that has so far been dominated by human incumbents. Once humans set formal rules for dealing with those species, they assume a certain status of legality, while legitimacy might still be disputed in the human domain. A case in point is the European policies regarding the governance of wolf populations (Hiedanpää, 2023).

This discussion demonstrates that stakeholder analysis of NBS must follow evolutionary principles, in the sense that the patterns of stakeholder relationships are constantly changing and dynamic, hence endogenous to the NBA. For NBS, we must add that the environmental conditions and ecosystems are also evolving, given climate change and other human impacts (D.2.1, pp. 14f). Therefore, an evolutionary approach defines stakeholder analysis as forward-looking. In fact, that follows already from defining NBS as an intervention. When the NBS is implemented, this requires forward-looking analysis, and further, when the resulting NBA is evolving. That means stakeholder analysis must be conducted in a dynamic way: a snapshot of stakeholder relations at the time of NBS design does not suffice.

We can further radicalise this dynamic view by approaching stakes and stakeholders as evolving entities. This view follows from two basic arguments.

- First, the NBA can only be sustainable if there is a network of stakeholder relationships into which it is embedded and where the various stakeholders continue to take actions to reproduce the pattern of the NBA despite changing environmental conditions. Without stakes, no motivation to endorse the NBA. This simple fact must also be seen in the reverse direction: To what extent does the NBA create the conditions for emerging stakeholder relationships and is it even productive in creating such entities (D.2.2, p. 155)? This is the first

meaning of the coevolutionary process of stakeholder relationships: The NBA coevolves with those relationships.

- Second, if we consider the emergence of new stakeholders in such a coevolutionary process, we must acknowledge that the NBA has generative socio-ontological powers. These powers are manifest in creating assemblages of entities that are newly emerging stakeholders (Youn and Baek, 2024). The notion of assemblage is essential in the coevolutionary approach, as multi-species stakeholders are typically assemblages of humans and other entities, such as other species or related physical structures. That means, a key aspect of NBS as evolving structures is that the NBS is sustained by coevolving multispecies assemblages of stakeholders: MSAs. As we will see, defining an NBS in this way is the key to reconceptualising NBA politics as more-than-human stakeholder relationships and their negotiation.

Figure 2.1: Endogenous emergence of multi-species stakeholder assemblages

The implication for research into LL practices is that we concentrate on those practices that result in the formation of MSAs, which further drive their coevolutionary dynamics.

We summarise the framework in Figure 2.1. In the current approach to NBS, stakeholder analysis is often conducted in the initial stages of the project, for example, to define the arena of participatory approaches. These stakeholder relationships are by definition disembodied as they refer to the NBS as an idea only, and they only include humans since only humans have a voice at this stage. When the intervention is done, the scene is set for the emergence of MSA in the NBA. The NBA framework does not separate the stakeholders from the NBS but treats them as endogenous elements. Some of the stakeholders (S1 and S4) in the diagram may retain their disembodied relationship. Others experience disembodied relationality (S3). Via the intervention, new stakeholders are created, some of them non-human (S6 and S7). Some original stakeholders become elements of multi-species stakeholder assemblages (S5 and S2). In understanding these complex relationships, conventional stakeholder analysis reaches its limits.

2.3. Coevolutionary principles of MSA analysis

A widely accepted definition of a stakeholder is that this is an agent who is affected by a certain state of the world and who affects this state (D.2.2, p. 153f) (Reed et al., 2009). The distinction between active and passive stakeholders adds the aspect that a stakeholder may be only affected but cannot affect this state (“passive”). On the other hand, in the human political arena, there are many active stakeholders who are not themselves affected by the NBA on the ground: They are disembodied stakeholders. However, these distinctions are overly general and miss the aspect of agency. A stone that falls on solid ground, causing a hole, but also breaks apart into pieces by the blow, is both affected by and affects the state of the ground; however, we wouldn’t consider the stone a stakeholder. A stakeholder is an agent, which means that the mere causal effects are embedded in states of intentionality vis-à-vis the world. This raises the question of whether both sides of causal relatedness are necessary to manifest intentionality, which is tricky when considering non-living elements of an MSA.

2.3.1. Etics and emics of stakeholder relationships

The notion of intentionality is philosophically complex, and we keep the discussion in lay terms. Intentionality has no direct relationship with being affected and affecting, as there is a pervasive phenomenon of unintended consequences resulting from intentional actions. First, the agent may affect a state of the world without intending that state. A hiker in the forest makes a noise when singing a song and scares birds away without intending to. Second, an agent may be affected without intending this to happen. The hiker may enjoy the birdsong intentionally but is hit by a drop of bird shit without intention.

The notion of unintended effects points to the important distinction between the two epistemological positions of the agent and the observer. The observer may notice effects of which the agent is not aware. This may apply to the case of birds chased away, and is generally often the case for many environmental impacts of human action. Vice versa, the agent may be affected by states of the world without being aware of it. The hiker may experience the effects of the environment on specific bodily functions, such as blood pressure, without being aware of it. As we can see, the distinction matters in practice in many ways, such as when the observer creates awareness of certain effects by communicating information to the agent. The ecologist informs the hiker about the effects of noise on birds and suggests a behavioural change.

This implies that stakes can be approached through the two methodologies of emics and etics (Whitacker, 2017), a distinction that relates to the Umwelt concept. A causal effect can be viewed in the etics perspective, which means that we look at the physical materiality of the effect, such as what the bird shit does with the hiker's hat when dropping on it, i.e. an intersubjectively verified damage. In contrast, we can view this event from the emic perspective and may learn from talking to the hiker that she is enjoying the event as fun and does not care about the damage. However, other scenarios are possible, such as often the case with environmental damages: In the

emics perspective, the affected agent may not be aware of the actual damage, or even relate positively to it, whereas the scientific observer diagnoses severe negative impacts. As we see, these distinctions matter a lot in practice since, for example, in the etics analysis, there may be stakeholders of a certain state of the world who do not even count themselves as such.

The distinction between emics and etics is a crucial aspect of the coevolutionary approach to NBA, as it relates to the problem of mediating between the different Umwelts of humans and non-human species to achieve a pattern of stakeholder relationships that sustain the NBS. Then, the scientific observer identifies certain causal patterns that generate the desired ecosystem services and can also refer to these as concrete causal patterns in sustaining a certain

Box 2.7: Ecological connectivity and stakeholder relationships at Cres

Because of the presence of griffon vultures and other bird species, the island of Cres is an integral part of the area HR1000033 Kvarner Islands, i.e., a wider area of special protection within the NATURA 2000 network classified in accordance with the Birds Directive. There are two ornithological reserves on the island (Kruna and Pod Okladi) where vultures nest. These are carrions, whose survival is enabled by the extensive breeding of Cres sheep (today there are around 13,000 heads) given that vultures mainly feed on sheep and lambs that have died in the pasture. So, there is ecological-social interconnection between griffon and sheep. Griffons are a symbol of our community, sort of a brand, as well as Cres sheep. Both are an integral part of the island's economy and resilience. The invasive game, wild boar and fallow deer populations have a direct impact on the management and maintenance of Cres habitats, i.e. plant and animal species within the Natura 2000 ecological network. In addition to the indirect pressure on biodiversity manifested through more intensive abandonment of sheep farming and the consequent overgrowth of pastures, the animals mentioned above also have a direct impact on the preservation of certain habitats. Also, non-native wild ungulates are a threat to sheep due to the interspecies competition (spatial and nutritional overlap), which is especially evident in fallow deer, causing overgrazing of pastures and drying up of natural puddles. So far, the measures taken to remove wild boar and fallow deer from the island have not produced the expected results. The management of the eradication process is left to individual hunting lessees lacking cooperation and coordination, and in the implementation they use almost exclusively measures from the domain of hunting described in the corresponding hunting management documents.

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pattern of evolving biodiversity (see box 2.7). However, that does not reflect the various states of knowledge that are embodied in the diversity of Umwelts of entities relating to the NBA. A simple example is the possibility of dangerous and even harmful encounters between humans and other species which are driven by mutual misperceptions and misinterpretations of behavioural cues and intentions.

This example is especially relevant when considering children (box 2.8). The domain of autonomous interactions between children and nature is closely monitored and influenced by adults. This oversight is necessary because “nature” can have both positive and negative effects on children's lives. While nature offers many learning opportunities, it also poses threats, such as poisonous plants, venomous snakes, and aggressive animals. Thus, teaching children how to engage with nature often involves establishing stricter boundaries between humans and the natural world, which differentiates human

Box 2.8: Children meet nature

In Carriacou, through hikes and environmental education, children often develop bonds with nature, evidenced by their interactions with trees, animals, and ecosystems. We hardly keep an eye on the clock, but absolutely pay high attention to raising consciousness events with Nature's representatives. And the rewards are deep and valuable because a special silent bond develops between the child and the tree, or snake or bird or even a caress on a tree trunk in full bloom. We call these Peak Learning moments, their value is immense and lasting, because the experience is placed outside of the memory library... new 'space' and connections are created. These experiences not only foster long-term environmental stewardship, but children have also influenced adults' views, leading to behavioural shifts, such as reduced turtle hunting due to health concerns raised by these younger generations.

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experiences from those of other living beings. Two significant areas of concern are cleanliness and societal practices that exploit other beings, such as meat consumption, which involves the act of killing. Moreover, in modern societies, children are bombarded with distorted representations of living beings through movies, cartoons, and toys, which often present a fictionalized version of nature. Therefore, it is important not to assume that children have any inherent relational affinity for nature, such as universal biophilia (Young and Rautio, 2024). However, this does not diminish their potential role as essential participants and even co-creators of NBA. For instance, young children may not necessarily value neatly maintained sidewalks, but they might find joy in exploring weeds growing in cracks and observing bugs. Acknowledging this form of relationality of “lingering” with other beings could bolster initiatives aimed at rewilding urban plant environments (Byman et al., 2024).

The distinction between emics and etics is particularly important when considering children. Vulnerability to nature is defined etically as a risk assessed by adults. However, emically, children experience a different type of Umwelt that may not be fully accessible to adults. Adults construct and impose their understanding of "nature"

based on their perceptions of children's Umwelts, but they do not start entirely from scratch in this understanding. A key insight from the coevolutionary perspective of the COEVOLVERS project is that children can provide valuable insights that inform adult views, thereby significantly impacting stakeholder relationships in the NBA.

2.3.2. Affectability and vulnerability

The etic/emics duality takes a different twist if we consider the temporal dimension. The stakeholder notion is often used to refer to future events: Who has stakes in a change in the state of the world if that is implemented? Obviously, states of knowledge matter essentially here since human agents may not be fully informed about the possible effects in the future. The etics/emics distinction often obtains a political dimension, as different kinds of human agents may maintain radically different opinions about future states and therefore enter debates or even conflicts.

The temporal dimension requires differentiation between actual states of the world and possible states that may be realised in the future. We introduce the general term of “affectability” here, meaning both being potentially able to be affected and to affect, i.e. adopt the somewhat unusual interpretation both as passive and active. However, this is justified in the Umwelt framework since Umwelt is constituted by ways of affecting and being affected (Uexküll’s *Merkwelt* and *Wirkwelt*). We can also directly relate the notion of affordance with that of a stake: If the environment incorporates an affordance for a certain entity, this can become a stake if the affordance is experienced as necessary for the wider aims of living: For example, a cat may have stake in the affordance of a tree for climbing when dogs are regularly present in the surroundings chasing cats.

The notion of affordance is also closely related to opportunity, which is central to understanding stake specificity as defined in D.2.2, p. 156f. Following the economics uses of the term “opportunity,” we can define the difference between the two terms in the following way. An affordance is an instantiation of an opportunity in the opportunity space. The tree is an affordance for the cat to climb. However, the question is whether there are other trees with similar affordances or functional equivalents, such as a roof.

The value of an affordance depends on the scope of the opportunity space: If the tree is the only affordance offering the opportunity to flee the dog, this is most valuable.

The notion of stakeholder often refers to stakes as a potential, in the sense that a stake is about affectability in the first place, since in practice, changing states of the world is what matters. Changing states of the world can be seen as changing opportunity spaces. This is very important as we cannot directly observe the opportunity spaces: Even if we do not diagnose any change of current patterns of action and related states of agents, their opportunity space may have undergone even drastic changes: The cat habitually always climbs the same tree, but through time, all other trees have been cut, so this tree becomes more and more valuable. If we focus on passive affectability, these observations relate to vulnerability. The cat becomes more and more vulnerable to dogs, the narrower the opportunity space shrinks spanned by trees.

COEVOLVERS deliverable D.3.3 *Vulnerabilities in design and implementation report* (Pittaway *et al.*, 2025) highlights how changing vulnerabilities linked to shrinking opportunity spaces arise from environmental degradation, urban expansion, governance gaps, economic pressures, and social or cultural shifts. These dynamics limit the capacity of communities and ecosystems to adapt or benefit from NBS. For example, in Pansio-Perno LL, urban densification and harbour activities have blocked shoreline access, reducing green corridors and habitat connectivity for biodiversity. In Murray Park LL, climate change has disrupted water cycles, diminishing the opportunity for traditional winter activities like curling while increasing path erosion and flooding, which limit recreational engagement. Molentargius-Saline LL faces growing competition for water due to tourism and urban expansion, shrinking wetland habitats vital for species such as flamingos. In Beskydy LL, water is becoming increasingly scarce due to climate change and artificial snowmaking for tourism may pose a threat for local forests in the future, while fragmented governance limits coordinated action across the border. Similarly, Barcelona LL grapples with abandoned land leading to wildfire risks, restricting the scope for grazing-based NBS due to water scarcity and inadequate infrastructure. Finally, in Pomáz–Kiskovácsi LL, rigid institutional hierarchies and funding gaps could limit opportunity for space for therapeutic gardens

that could integrate ecological and health benefits. These cases illustrate how changing vulnerabilities reduce the transformative potential of NBS.

The term vulnerability is widely used though analytically imprecise (D.2.2, pp. 156ff). In everyday language, mostly shaping uses in research, the term relates vaguely to negative affectability. Philosophically more precise approaches tend to treat the term more neutral, or even positively, since vulnerability is the potential to be affected by the world, including the aspect of awareness and sensibility (Honkasalo, 2019). Here, vulnerability is a necessary condition for meaningful action. If we want to maintain the negative meaning, vulnerability may relate to two different aspects that are not mutually exclusive. The first is that the term would refer to unintended affectability, which in economics is referred to as negative externality. In this case, an agent faces a future effect that she values negatively. The key aspect is that the agent may anticipate this effect but expects that she cannot do anything to avoid it: The opportunity space is very limited. In the latter case, vulnerability relates to a lack of agential power in changing states of the world. In this chapter, we will use the term in these two senses combined.

For understanding vulnerability, it is essential again to distinguish the etics and the emics (seminally, Spiers 2000). A scientific observer may identify a vulnerability that emerges in certain future trends, but the affected agent is not aware of this. Vice versa, the agent may feel vulnerable even though the observer considers this as a misperception. Moreover, the normative dimension comes into play since various vulnerabilities may be given different weights by different agents. The coevolutionary approach does not take an independent normative stance here, but points to the endogenous political process in which the stakeholders develop those stances interactively. However, this requires certain conditions, in particular, empathetic communication. The mediation across diverse Umwelts happens via understanding vulnerabilities, which is possible both by interpreting the other's vulnerability in terms of one's own frame of reference, and by imagining the frame of reference of another being.

The emics and etics can be coupled in a species-transcending capability approach (D.2.2, pp. 50f) (Parker et al., 2022). For example, a human can empathise with a dog if she is hurt by a stone since the human can imagine her own pain when being hurt, or the human can empathise with a fish on dry ground by imagining herself as being deprived of air (instead of water). This leads to the conclusion that affectability closely relates to the notion of care.

Box 2.9: Caring for vultures at Cres

We have feeding places. Now we somehow maintain them artificially via rescue programs. We observed ten couples nesting here, for longer than the past couple of years. A few days ago colleague of mine, coming from Orlec to work, noticed a dead sheep that must have been hit by a car. He put the sheep in his car, called the rescue centre and he said, "I have a sheep," which means "I have food for the birds". They came to collect the dead sheep. So, the community is not all but being aware of the value people try to help.

Ugo Tojć, Cres small scale pilot

A most general definition of care is affectability by the affectability of the other, which can be further specified in reference to vulnerability. This second-order affectability is grounded in empathy, which is a complex phenomenon (Decety, 2015). In humans, empathy can be embodied or cognitively triggered, hence tending towards disembodiment (Decety and Yoder, 2016). The latter bridges the etics and emics, since often cognitive empathy is conditioned by information about certain conditions of vulnerability: We hear that a lake dries out and imagine the fate of the fish. The question is whether this disembodied cognitive state can trigger the emergence of MSAs via nurturing embodied relationality.

Different forms of relationality in children and adults matter for conceptualising MSAs and developing practices of crafting NBA. Research on childhood has scientifically explored the everyday experiences of children cohabitating with animals (Tammi et al., 2023). Children develop deeply embodied and sensory relationships with other living beings and often project their feelings and subjectivity onto them, demonstrating a strong sense of anthropomorphism. For instance, children talk to animals and plants, imagining that these beings respond based on their observed reactions. This illustrates how children are almost "naturally born" members of MSAs. It is important to distinguish this from their independent role in claiming embodied stakes. For example, studies have shown that playing in a forest enhances children's creativity

and imagination while also improving their well-being (Sallnäs Pysander et al., 2024). Activities like climbing trees or walking on uneven ground foster motor skills. The stakes children have in the forest are physical and embodied, with particular vulnerabilities since other environments may not provide equivalent experiences. This contrasts with the emotional stakes that arise from relationships with specific beings, such as a child forming a bond with a particular tree in the forest.

Box 2.10: Children and vulnerabilities

At Carriacou, Kido Foundation prioritizes inclusive participation, ensuring children from various backgrounds, including vulnerable communities, can engage. Post-hurricane recovery efforts have heightened awareness of environmental vulnerabilities, emphasizing the importance of replanting mangroves and integrating traditional ecological knowledge into NBS projects. This is hard social work, not for average or faint hearted: the night and day pressure on young children at their most vulnerable and sensitive (genius level) age is impossible to overstate.

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Affectability by the other means that there is a causal relationship between the state of the other and the state of the concerned actor that leads to embodied coupling (a phenomenon designated as “resonance” by Rosa (Rosa, 2018)). In such a state of coupling, one actor cares for the other in recognising its vulnerability. The distinctiveness of this state can be best illustrated by an example. During certain periods of the year, toads may traverse roads and suffer violent death by cars. Municipal authorities may recognise this issue and set up signs alerting drivers of this risk, receiving advice from experts who professionally monitor the local ecosystems. Neither the administrators nor the drivers develop a caring relationship with the toads, perhaps most of them rarely meet a toad closely. In contrast, some activists express empathetic concern and organise actions carrying the toads across the road. This represents embodied affectability and care for the toads’ vulnerability. The conceptual novelty proposed in this chapter is that the toads and the activists are identified as assemblages and, hence, multispecies stakeholders vis-à-vis the authorities that manage traffic. The toads and the activists are MSAs.

2.3.3. Emergence of MSAs

Let us consider the question of what an agent is that has stakes. So far, stakeholder analysis has been almost exclusively conducted for humans. However, this is unwarranted anthropocentrism since there are many non-humans who manifest features such as intentionality and sentience (Deckha, 2021), hence have agency and could be stakeholders. Accordingly, we need to develop a criterion of where we draw the line between affectability in the mere physical sense and in the sense of stakeholder analysis.

This question relates to the burgeoning literature on rights of nature and related topics since if we employ the notion of rights, say, to a wave in the ocean, we are almost certainly compelled to use the notion of stakeholder for these entities. This point is open to debate, and we discuss this in the next section. The position here is that agency is the key criterion of the stakeholder status, implying that the wave, as such, cannot be a stakeholder. However, we do not limit agency to human agents only and adopt the perspective of material agency in the sense that agency is a property that emerges in assemblages of various entities. This view generalises over the Hegelian insight that intentions are essential social, which, however, would only count assemblages of humans as grounding agency. In the coevolutionary approach to NBA, we approach agency as a property of multispecies assemblages, including non-living entities: MSAs have agency (so, the wave is a part of an assemblage with people and other living beings). To this, we add the important point that MSAs are evolving themselves and are endogenous to the NBS. In general, MSAs are not fixed and exogenous givens, even in the sense of a specific individual representing a species, but are emerging agencements in the sense of Deleuze and Guattari (Deleuze and Guattari, 2009).

The difficulty is when we can diagnose an assemblage with intentionality? An example may help. A paradigmatic case of an MSA is pairs of dogs and human dog-owners (compare D2.2, pp. 109f, 133) (Fox et al., 2023; Merritt, 2021). Here, we distinguish the case that a professional dog-owner raises puppies to sell them as fast as possible. This relationship does not necessarily count as MSA, as we will develop the argument,

since the puppies are merely seen as assets. The relationship is disembodied. This constellation is different for the human who caringly owns a dog and regularly takes her out for a walk in the forest (see box 2.11). Dogs and humans develop the feature of shared intentionality in walking, and both pay mutual attention to the other. This relationship is embodied in terms of feelings of care, often called “love.” The pair may regularly walk to the same forest nearby so that both are deeply familiar with the place and develop a shared sense of place. In this case, we can

Box 2.11: Dogs and people at Murray Park

The assemblage of dog, dog-owner, and forest, as lived in Murray Park, Scotland, reveals a multispecies entanglement wherein human, animal, and environment are dynamically co-constituted. Throughout the project interviews, Murray Park emerges not as a mere setting for human and animal interactions, but as an integral force that provides a space for relational dynamics between species. One dog-owner spoke of venturing into the park on cold nights solely because of the presence of their dogs, an act that enabled encounters with owls, foxes, and hedgehogs otherwise hidden from human view. Here, the dog’s embodied needs intertwine with the human’s desire for connection, drawing both into the forest’s natural state. Another participant described Murray Park’s sheltered character as decisive in choosing it for daily walks, emphasising how the forest offered a safe space where dog and owner could regularly roam, interact, and engage with the environment.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

expand the MSA to include the forest and its physical properties, such as the shape of the terrain. The coevolutionary view treats the assemblage of dog-forest-human as a stakeholder, an MSA.

Consider the case where the forest is regarded as the NBS. As the example demonstrates, in such an MSA the human is not simply representing the other two entities when she acts as a stakeholder of the forest. She is the one who talks, but what she says is grounded in the embodied relationship with the other two entities. This observation resolves the difficulties when the forest would be seen as a stakeholder itself, since the forest neither has voice nor intentions. On the other hand, simple representation would apparently also be the case if the forest is owned by a private businessperson in the logging industry. Here, the stakeholder is only the human, who might represent the forest, but there is no MSA in which the human would relate to the forest in a caring relationship and recognize the independent interests of the beings that make up the forest. In COEVOLVERS, the role board game is a powerful tool to illustrate the relevance of communication between human actors, and

their relationships with other species as key determinants of success in managing NBS. However, the underlying game-theoretic constructs remain disembodied. It is necessary to include embodied stakeholders or MSA. The Beskydy COEVOLVERS team collaborates with various human stakeholders at the small scale pilot Cres and explores how the multispecies relationships can be represented in various role of the game.

This discussion also prompts the question of whether phenomena described by certain mass or aggregate terms can actually be considered parts of assemblages. In ecolinguistics, it is well recognized that using mass terms often obscures and even suppresses the resonant and caring relationships that exist within these contexts. (Stibbe, 2021). For instance, when forest owners transition from clear-cutting forestry to continuous-cover forestry to promote ecosystem health, this shift can change their

relationship with the forest towards a more individualised approach (Kortetmäki et al., 2023). Such a transformation may lead to the development of a complex and multifaceted MSAs. One way this transformation might manifest is through the creation of detailed, multi-dimensional maps of forest micro-environments, each associated with different emotional experiences (as discussed in the next chapter). Furthermore, the

Box 2.12: Individualizing forest experience at Murray Park

We began the VNT project during the "Searching for Common Ground" workshop. In this workshop, we engaged with the community to explore their activities in Murray Park. From the insights gathered, we developed a storyboard outlining the sensory experiences and various media to be included in VNT. The design of VNT reflects a journey through the park. Participants will walk through the park gate, where they will hear the sound of the gate opening. The purpose of VNT is to highlight the sensory experiences found in the park and raise awareness of its spaces. Many people have expressed that they feel there is nowhere to go, and this project aims to connect them to the park, as few are aware of its existence. We also created an app that allows users to share their experiences of the park by leaving photos during their walks. This community-driven platform encourages individuals to share their memories and experiences related to Murray Park.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

transformed forest offers a richer landscape of affordances, encouraging the emergence of various MSAs, such as distinct groups concentrating on specific aspects of the forest (for example, foragers or birdwatchers). A notable example of forests featuring diverse MSAs is the Satoyama forests in Japan (Berglund et al., 2014; Ishizawa, 2018).

Children play a crucial role in MSAs due to their developmental and relational characteristics. A typical example of a child-centered MSA involves a triad consisting of a child, a non-human living being, and a caregiver. The effectiveness of this MSA largely depends on the relationship between the child and the caregiver (Murphy, 2018). The caregiver, often responsible for the child's daily education, influences the child's

Box 2.13: Children as knowledge-holders

At Carraciou, children need to find out by themselves what the problems are and consequently discuss aiming to co-create the solutions. What could be done locally to address global challenges requires a bottom-up approach, not only in theory, but practically on-site, by raising consciousness of the issues and discarding anthropocentric world views. Here, ancient knowledge is relevant. For instance, the hurricane Beryl catastrophe brought back the value of ancient knowledge, by sharing the information that we now need to grow back the mangroves and plant evergreen trees.

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behaviour and attitudes toward other beings. Adults generally approach interactions with animals and nature differently than children do, which can shape their perceptions (Taylor and Pacini-Ketchabaw, 2015). For instance, children may engage with earthworms playfully, while many adults tend to avoid touching them. Interestingly, children can also inspire adults to reconsider and change their own behaviours toward the natural world. This is crucial for parents to build the bridges to formal NBS governance by representing the MSA and giving it voice. It is important that this avoids adult paternalism and recognises the shared agencement of child and non-human members of the MSA. One of the critical activities is what Tsing and others have introduced as “feral storytelling” which aims at unearthing the non-conformist and “nomadic” tendencies in the MSA assemblages (Osgood and Odegard, 2022). There are already existing MSAs (such as engaging dogs) or those that are starting to form, as well as innovative MSAs that are created by both children and their caregivers. In all instances, the connection to formal stakeholder politics is established through these caregivers, who serve as stewards of the MSA, representing children and other entities. Formal NBS governance may ease such connections by integrating educational institutions into NBS management.

2.3.4. Criteria for identifying MSAs

The dog-human example is the case for a strongly embodied and bounded MSA that can include various other non-living entities, such as street trees. These are cases where MSAs are bonded by shared intentionality and mutual care. If we generalize this criterion, we immediately see that MSAs can be endogenous to the NBS, and even stronger, that the emergence of such stakeholder assemblages is critical to its resilience and sustainability. NBS practices should aim at nurturing strong assemblages that evolve dynamically. A COEVOLVERS example is the emerging assemblages of residents, shepherds, and sheep in the Barcelona LL. Even the shepherds and the sheep may not have the status of a multi-species assemblage as long as the shepherds and the municipality treat the sheep only as assets for business and as a service provider. Disembodied stakeholders are only the different human groups, such as the residents and the shepherds, and even residents may not be stakeholders if they are ill-informed about the NBS. In this case, we also observe hierarchical structures in the governance domain, as discussed in the first section. The municipal administration has the power to fix the rules and conditions of the NBS without staying in a caring and resonant relationship on the level of the individual administrators. Their relationship is disembodied and instrumental. Shepherds and sheep can emerge as an MSA if shepherds nurture a caring relationship with them, and this may even include the residents, if they also engage with the sheep beyond just indirectly utilising their ecosystem service (see D.2.2, p. 169).

MSAs do not necessarily presuppose shared intentionality in the etics perspective, which is, however, well confirmed in the dog case. An important topic is the role of non-humans in providing cultural ecosystem services, which includes the special case of Indigenous relationality with non-humans (Kimmerer, 2020; McMillen et al., 2020). In these contexts, non-humans attain the status of beings that relate to humans in their human-specific Umwelt beyond what can be etically confirmed. In other words, even shared intentionality can be emically constructed. We can refer to these phenomena as cultural MSAs (compare D.2.2, pp. 81f, 160). This differs from representation as the imagined relationship is embodied in cultural stances towards the non-human,

such as expressed in ritual practices (D.2.2., pp. 169ff). An important case is the relationality that children may develop towards other species, which may include their parents as caretakers.

An important condition of MSAs is a spatial structure. However, analytical precision is necessary as often the term assemblage is used in referring to a mere spatial arrangement, such as the neighbourhood in the sheep case. Clearly, mere spatial arrangements do not qualify as an MSA. However, spatial arrangements can be necessary conditions for nurturing the emergence of such assemblages. The classical case is the garden (D2.2, p. 41). Gardens can nurture relationships of care between humans and other species, and they can also establish human-human assemblages. One necessary condition is the spatial contiguity between different garden plots. Beyond such obvious examples, there are many others which relate to connectivities, such as the connectivities created by pollinators moving across urban neighbourhoods (D.2.2, p. 49) (Marshman, 2019).

In the MSA framework, children play a crucial role in shaping a stakeholder politics of NBS that recognises the interconnectedness of all beings. This is largely because children share locational vulnerabilities with other species. For instance, children are more closely tied to their local environments, where their well-being is influenced by their interactions with animals and plants: This place-boundedness creates particular vulnerabilities compared to peers. They also have limited capacity to cope with negative impacts, often relying on the care provided by others. It is important to differentiate between etics and emics in this context. Shared vulnerability does not necessarily mean that children are aware of it. For example, if a neighbourhood park is replaced by a shopping area, etically speaking, the living beings in that park lose their local livelihood with no alternatives, while children lose access to green space that is easily reachable. The park holds specific significance for both children and other living beings, which leads to a generalised understanding of vulnerability. However, children may not recognise the broader vulnerabilities of other beings, except in relation to their own experiences, such as playing with them. Emically, the vulnerabilities differ significantly: the *Umwelts* of children and other beings partially overlap but may only connect minimally.

A final comment is warranted on the individualisation of MSAs (D.2.2, pp. 51ff). Unlike other social and life sciences structural terms, they are strictly individualised in time and space. This is a key aspect in the coevolutionary approach to NBS since we cannot take a certain structure of MSAs as a given and as typical across different NBS of a similar type. Moreover, the notion of reciprocity needs to be referred to specific entities that enter such a relationship. Accordingly, treating the forest as an element in an MSA is problematic. Here, the role of mapping Umwelts is salient, as “the forest” is never perceived by specific entities in its entirety. Humans may not perceive the roots and fungi below the surface even though these are pivotal for the forest’s existence (foragers may do, and they can be drivers of MSAs, as in the famous case of Japanese Matsutake activists, Tsing, 2017). Reciprocity is individualised in the sense that a forest is factually a super-assemblage of many MSAs, such as constituted by various dog-owners and their habitual routes. This is an example where mapping techniques such behavioural mapping are essential for identifying MSAs (D.2.2, p. 99). We discuss this in detail in the chapter on mapping.

2.4. Intentionality, voice and Nature-based governance in crafting NBAs

Another important theoretical issue concerns what causes the changes in states of the world. The criterion of intentionality matters essentially here, too. Most people wouldn’t say that we are stakeholders in a hurricane, even though we are seriously affected by it. Obviously, there is an important distinction between a state of the world that results from intentional action, and which does not. For example, consider a river. We can reasonably ask who the stakeholders of the river are. However, we typically ask this question only if there is an intentional action taken that changes the state of the river. The notion of stakeholder is not used without reference to intentional action towards states of the world since otherwise, for example, we would approach all members of an ecosystem as its stakeholders, which would certainly count as a category mistake or a mere metaphor. The term stakeholder is not a scientific notion in biology but in

the social sciences. The social sciences relate to categories of meaning, intention, or social interaction.

Stakeholder analysis is mostly done in the context of such states of the world which are enacted by a certain concerned and dedicated agent, such as an organisation like municipal planning agencies or environmental NGOs. As such, it is highly relevant for NBS research and design: NBS are designed and implemented by humans to achieve certain goals, so we can ask which entities are stakeholders of the NBS as an organisation. This perspective aligns with the standard conception of governance, so we must neatly distinguish between the materiality of the NBS and its institutional superstructure. MSAs relate to materiality in the first place, whereas the conventional stakeholder concept relates to the institutional form of the NBS. Accordingly, we distinguish between two modes of governance, embodied and disembodied (Herrmann-Pillath, 2024a).

One implication of the discussion in the previous sections is that we cannot approach the intentional action of creating and implementing an NBS in terms of conventional notions of engineering design. Even if designers adopted such an approach, they still would need to acknowledge that the NBS is only sustainable via endogenous MSAs. However, evidently, this evolutionary process cannot be designed in advance: NBS design can only create the setting and guardrails of an otherwise self-organising evolutionary process (Houston et al., 2018). This assessment includes all kinds of inclusive governance of NBS which would suggest formal recognition of other species in a kind of political representative mechanism (Meijer, 2019). Therefore, NBS design is bricolage or, literally, crafting an NBA via a mix of interventions and spontaneous evolution. Crafting NBAs is the coevolutionary counterpart to engineering design and is a defining feature of Nature-based governance (D2.2, pp. 166-172).

In Nature-based governance, MSAs are the critical political actors, in two senses. First, crafting the NBA means nurturing MSAs, and second, assembled MSAs participate in crafting the NBA. For example, to create a pattern of sustainable stakeholder relationships in the Cagliari LL, it is necessary to assemble MSAs that relate citizens and birds (such as bird-watching communities at schools), and these MSAs, in turn,

become stakeholders vis-à-vis the municipality that manages the nature reserve of the salina and continues with assembling it as sustainable natural pattern.

The coevolutionary approach identifies the crafting of an NBA as a learning community and the Living Lab as one of its paradigmatic forms (D.2.2., pp. 57ff). For example, a

municipal administration would approach the planning of green spaces as a dynamic process in which emerging and existing MSAs are included in the regular application of participatory approaches in urban planning; moreover, this approach is extended to the deliberate nurturing of emerging MSAs in identifying and endorsing all forms of citizen

Box 2.14: Children as innovators

Children engagement takes place through various outdoor learning activities, group discussions, and immersive educational games like the 'Planetarium' (set in 3025), where children explore alternative planetary systems and environmental ethics. Children choose their own groups and planets, and they could switch between them. One of challenges they faced was garbage. During a beach trip, they realized most of the trash wasn't even from their own island but had drifted in from elsewhere—almost like it came from another planet. That got them thinking about solutions. The boys came up with the idea of building a catamaran out of collected plastic, while the girls started turning discarded materials into bags and other useful items. Eventually, the latter also was turned into microenterprises..

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engagement with the NBA. Such activities can start from place-shaping measures that employ artistic methods in eliciting a sense of place among humans relating to the green space that nurtures and nudges the formation of MSAs (D.2.1., pp. 55ff). For example, there might be initiatives to observe, count and record pollinators in the green space, and of to create locations in the green space that foster human awareness of the cohabitation with pollinators. This may include long-term initiatives such as engaging pre-school children who might grow up as MSAs in the future.

As a concrete example, let us go back to the paradigmatic dog-human MSA. As we learned during a COEVOLVERS meeting at the city of Budapest, municipal planners face the mundane challenge that it is difficult to sustain street trees as an NBS to urban heat regulation because of the omnipresence of pet dogs who literally poison the trees with their urination. Trees often have no time to grow to a sufficient height and are substituted by new trees which, however, cannot adequately fulfill the intended function of an NBS because the canopy never closes up. Limiting the number of pet dogs is not politically feasible in the current constellation of stakeholders. The dog-owners are part of a two-species MSA who is a powerful stakeholder in the status quo

enacted by the regular dog walks in the neighbourhood. Can we expand this MSA to include the trees? What kind of behavioural changes are necessary to create a new stakeholder relationship pattern in which dog-owners, dogs and trees are bounded by mutual care and recognition? Dog owners often do not have an adequate understanding of dog Umwelts, so one aspect is improving the awareness and empathy of dog owners who might otherwise see the dog's action as a mere fulfilment of the function of relieving the dog and avoiding mess at home. Learning about the relationality between dog and tree can induce awareness of the tree's well-being, which can be bolstered by art-based measures that would highlight the individuality and future beauty of the tree (D.2.2, p. 47). In a newly emerging triadic MSA, the NBA would be supported by a new stakeholder pattern. This pattern is endogenous to the NBA and cannot be simply designed, enforced or directly incentivised by the municipal agencies. In the end, the MSA achieves voice via the human members who develop embodied relationships of caring with both dogs and trees.

The fictitious Budapest scenario would be a case of Nature-based governance which would build on a range of measures in the modes of sensory and embodied governance. At the end of the evolutionary process, the NBA of street trees would be endogenously sustained by embodied and coordinated actions by humans and dogs, embedded into the NBA as a place shaped by trees as a key element in urban aesthetics.

In practice, embodied and disembodied forms of governance interplay, and, for example, at the city hall, human stakeholders of all kinds voice their interests and concerns. The difference between embodiment and disembodiment matters less in such formal contexts, but how the politics of stakeholder relationships is embedded in evolving multi-species assemblages. There are those who represent voice with disembodied concerns, such as an NGO arguing for toad protection, and those who express embodied care and carry the toads across the road. It is important to emphasise that in the current context, we do not say that embodiment is good and disembodiment is bad. However, embodied stakeholder relations are essential in Nature based governance and for pushing the change of values and habits in an NBS community. After all, habits are embodied values.

A key group mediating between disembodiment and embodiment are Nature-based entrepreneurs NBEs, who are human members of MSAs. We will examine them further Chapter 5. NBEs are motivated by embodied values and adapt their concerns into formats that align with disembodied interests, concerns, and motivations. A common example is the transformation of an MSA activity into a business model, such as offering foraging as a commercial leisure activity. These activities often blur the

Box 2.15: Institutionalizing the role of children in NBA

Recent years have seen increasing support from different organisations, such as local schools and the Grenada Tourism Authority. Schools actively collaborate with Kido, recognizing the value of experiential learning. Principals and teachers at primary schools are particularly keen on KIDO presentations and we have developed a close collaboration interacting with generations of students. We also have a good relationship with many parents, who are happy that their kids are with Kido on weekends. Once, a mother came to me and said: What have you done to my child? He is now quiet, he does his homework, eats and goes to bed – happy and exhausted. Key lessons include the importance of self-learning, co-creation of solutions, and blending local and scientific knowledge. Activities fostering deep environmental connections might be expanded to other regions, with children as stewards of environmental and social change. Notable success stories include children from these programs pursuing environmental science careers and returning to their communities to contribute.

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lines between what is acceptable within the NBS context and what is not, and they can be limited by existing regulations. For instance, in the EU, countries have widely differing regulations regarding foraging. It is significant whether this activity is conducted by MSAs as part of voluntary public education—such as guiding children through the forest—or operated as a small business (Valguarnera, 2017)).

NBS faces challenges on multiple fronts, particularly regarding long-term financial viability. NBEs can play a crucial role in transforming stakeholder relationships related to disembodied governance, including various forms of governance, such as market governance versus administrative governance (Pahl-Wostl, 2019). For instance, as discussed in D2.2, hunting and killing animals can be a significant factor in enhancing public acceptance of an NBS and shifting stakeholder support in its favor. If this process involves strengthening market governance—like in the Barcelona Living Lab, where sheep-based products such as sausages are sold—MSA plays a vital role in mitigating the negative socioecological impacts of marketization. This includes lessening the profit-driven motivations and promoting the adoption of appropriate legal structures for social enterprises.

In the implementation of NBS, communities can actively promote the development of MSAs that place children at the center. This approach recognises children as essential contributors to the long-term sustainability of NBS. Practically, this means that NBS implementation should be supported by various measures, including ecological education and community activities that involve children (Tidball and Krasny, 2010). This is already well recognised in practice: A case in point are community gardens where adults and children of all

Box 2.16: The “Nature Club” at Pansio Perno

At Pansio-Perno, there are some active inhabitants, and citizen associations, who are actively promoting the development of the neighborhood in various forums. These active residents are mostly middle aged or older people, white, Finnish speaking, relatively highly educated, employed or retired. Many of them are involved in a local house owners’ association but also some who live in rental buildings. They do also voluntary work at the community center “Panskis”, which is maintained and organized in practice by citizen associations. Panskis does mainly food aid and organizes guided activities for kids in the afternoon, when their parents are not yet home. The “children’s Nature Club” is also organized by Panskis. Activities linked to nature in the Nature Club. For example, environmental artist did 4 workshops with the children. The workshops included exercises focusing on local nature, e.g. drawing with natural pigments and charcoal, ‘Forestway’ dance, making friends with trees (a ‘friend tree’), and rock painting. The exercise starts with a dance in a group. The instructor brings an acoustic instrument. The participants go to a circle so that they can see each other’s faces, then turn around, listen and watch the forest, and start moving their bodies. Then they start moving in the forest and find a tree that catches their attention more than other trees, a ‘friend tree’. They make a piece of art under this tree using rocks, pines or any material they can find in the surrounding nature.

Kia Andell, Turku Living Lab

ages work together and share experiences in caring for other beings (Krasny and Tidball, 2009). Institutionalised settings of MSA emergence are bolstered if the appropriate pedagogical stances are adopted that are directly informed by ideas about shared agencies in multi-species assemblages (Carlyle, 2019). An important example is the educational paradigm of “wild pedagogy” that stays in a long tradition of including outdoor activities in early childhood education (Møller et al, 2025). These approaches are a key condition for crafting NBAs on the basis of an NBS: The idea of NBS always must include the view on future emerging MSAs who sustain the coevolving NBA. A COEVOLVERS example can be found in Cagliari Molentargius Park. As part of a NBS approach to environmental education, the park promotes learning experiences that go beyond just the umbrella species pink flamingo, focusing instead on the entire ecological network of the wetland system. The Environmental Education and Sustainability Centre (CEAS) plays a crucial role in raising awareness about non-charismatic species, including insects, amphibians, reptiles, and small mammals, all

of which contribute to the park's functional biodiversity and the essential ecosystem services it provides. Through participatory and place-based learning activities—such as field explorations, thematic workshops, and gamified educational experiences—children and young people interact directly with various life forms. This engagement fosters an emotional connection to nature and nurtures long-term stewardship of the environment. These activities also help to build ecological literacy among younger generations and reinforce the social co-benefits of NbS by promoting inclusive environmental awareness and pro-nature behaviors. By adopting a systemic and interdisciplinary perspective, the CEAS encourages an understanding of the interdependence between species and habitats, supporting the NbS goal of enhancing biodiversity while also delivering educational and cultural ecosystem services.

Box 2.17: The educational experience of biodiversity at Molentargius Park

At Molentargius Park, the flamingo is the bright invitation—the dazzling ambassador that draws eyes and cameras—but it's only the beginning of the story. Through the work of the CEAS, children and youths are guided beyond the pink allure to discover the quiet, essential lives that truly sustain this unique ecosystem: the darting insects that pollinate, the camouflaged amphibians that balance food chains, the resilient reeds that filter water and shelter the unseen. These small, often ignored beings are the threads that hold the wetland tapestry together, like an assemblage. By shifting the spotlight from the spectacular to the subtle, Molentargius Park is nurturing a new way of seeing nature—one that values every life form, not for its beauty or fame, but for its irreplaceable role in the balance of the ecosystem. And once a child sees a beetle with the same wonder as a flamingo, we know something powerful has taken root.

Oriana Mosca and Ferdinando Fornara, Cagliari LL

2.5. Conclusion

This chapter presents a complex argument regarding stakeholder analysis through the lens of assemblage theory. Initially, COEVOLVERS adhered to a conventional approach to stakeholder analysis that aligned with institutionalist theories of governance, focusing solely on human institutions. However, with the concept of Nature-based governance, COEVOLVERS has expanded this framework to explore how non-human elements can play an integral role in governance. In doing so, COEVOLVERS follows its general emphasis on strategic thinking in the longer run of coevolutionary processes, such the formation of habits, that reach far beyond the time

frames of project management. Children have not been part of the project frame as defined in the project proposal. As a result of LL experiences, COEVOLVERS suggests a strategic focus on children as key MSA in future NBS design.

A critical challenge is that all established governance theories assume human agency in their definitions of stakeholders. The recent trend of assigning agency to non-humans—including granting rights to non-living entities like rivers—leads to the complex issue of representing non-humans. Assemblage theory addresses these challenges by viewing agency not as a characteristic of individuals, but as an emergent property resulting from the interactions of various elements, including both humans and non-humans, as well as living and non-living entities. In this context, the problem of representation disappears because humans are an intrinsic part of the assemblage. The MSA expresses itself through humans, but those humans do not serve as mere representatives.

We have demonstrated that for this to occur, some (not all) humans must maintain an embodied relationship with other elements of the assemblage. This concept is well illustrated in Indigenous ontologies, where, for instance, a river is perceived as being part of the human body and vice versa. Practically, this fundamental idea leads to the question of how we can actively foster such forms of embodied relationality. This raises a paradox: when we consider this through an instrumental approach to “tools,” we risk moving into a disembodied realm of rational purposiveness. Simply put, can we rationally decide to love? The next chapter will explore a crucial set of tools that may help to cultivate MSAs within a Nature-based governance framework.

Chapter 3: Mapping Nature-based assemblages

3.0. Chapter summary

A common trend in LL practices is the use of various mapping approaches and tools to explore the multi-species environments where NBS are implemented. This chapter systematises mapping practices based on recent scholarly literature related to cartography and mapping tools. A key focus is the shift from traditional, purely representational uses of maps to a more multi-functional perspective. This includes a range of methods such as participatory mapping, emotion mapping, and behavioural mapping, each serving different purposes—such as performative, transformative, or therapeutic uses. In the context of multiple species, a significant challenge lies in making the environments, or *Umwelts*, of non-human beings accessible to humans. This accessibility is crucial for forming multi-species stakeholder assemblages that endogenously sustain an NBA. Modern digital technologies are utilised in the COEVOLVERS project to integrate these various elements into single mapping applications, which facilitate a rich diversity of user experiences and expressive options, specifically NatureNex app and Virtual Nature Tool.

3.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the importance of mapping as a critical activity within the coevolutionary approach to Nature-based solutions. In the COEVOLVERS project, various types of mapping methods are employed, including participatory mapping, emotion mapping, behavioural mapping, and affordance mapping. The chapter presents a cohesive theoretical framework for mapping and showcases the experiences of COEVOLVERS. Building on the agenda outlined in Chapter 1, we focus on a distinctive aspect of COEVOLVERS: expanding the concept and methods of mapping to include the more-than-human dimension, and specifically, conceiving mapping as a central form of crafting Nature-based assemblages NBA. In other words, mapping is a critical craft in moving from the idea of NBS to a co-evolving NBA. Mapping cannot be exclusively grounded in scientific methods, but is a creative and contextualised skill that experts and non-experts develop in shared practices of crafting an NBA.

This expansion necessitates two different methodological approaches, grounded in the etics and emics of mapping. First, we explore how to map the diversity of the multi-

species NBA in a particular territory. Second, we investigate how to access the unique Umwelts of other species through anthropocentric mapping, thus activating maps as media of cross-species communication and understanding. Additionally, in the context of the normative sciences framework (see D.2.2, Chapter 1), we also examine the transformative functions and potential of mapping, in particular as an art-based method of nurturing the emergence of multi-species stakeholder assemblages MSAs. The COEVOLVERS approach exemplifies the role of mapping as a transformative technology in human niche construction over many centuries. Traditionally, mapping, as it developed in Western modernity, has served as a crucial means of establishing human control and dominance over space. In particular, mapping is a critical tool in building the infrastructure of human societies. In contrast, the coevolutionary approach reimagines mapping as a tool that fosters cohabitation and promotes shared flourishing within multispecies communities.

Traditional cartography emerged as a key technology in human niche construction, for example, mapping a territory and the resources that can be exploited, such as a river for transport or subsoil mineral deposits. In contrast, mapping in multispecies niche construction renders the worlds of other species accessible to humans, such as the affordances of a place for various species. In developing this approach, COEVOLVERS can build on the rich results of decades of multi- and transdisciplinary research on mapping which transcends the classical positivist approach to cartography (Kitchin and Dodge, 2007; Soini, 2001).

While traditional mapping is often viewed as a scientific method for representing space, this perspective has always been balanced by another viewpoint that sees mapping as an art form and a unique aesthetic approach to understanding meaningful relationships between people and space (Cosgrove, 2005). Maps possess not only a functional aesthetic dimension, which allows them to convey spatial information effectively, but they can also serve as expressive media that reveal the emotional significance of particular locations and trigger correlated emotional stances in the map reader. In recent decades, maps have increasingly become recognised as a distinct genre within the arts (Harmon and Clemans, 2009). Art-based methods aimed at eco-

social transformation frequently incorporate various mapping practices (Pearson et al., 2018). Hence, mapping is an essential feature of approaching NBA as co-creative more-than-human artwork (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2023). Mapping is not just a technology representing space, but an aesthetic means of place-shaping in multi-species communities (Horlings et al., 2020). Mapping places can be a coevolutionary transformative medium that creates the conditions for sustainable and

Box 3.1: Digital technologies in mapping NBA: NatureNex

Our NatureNex App has significant potential as a mapping tool designed to enhance our understanding of nature. It helps users identify what aspects of nature they are interested in, what attractions draw them in, and the stories they wish to share. This app serves as a reflective tool that prompts questions and encourages users to engage with nature in various ways. I believe it will promote a deeper connection to nature and may even inspire social entrepreneurship focused on improving our understanding and interaction with the natural world. If we consider how stories have evolved over time, we can examine why individuals share different narratives now compared to the past. Landscape architects can utilize these stories to inform their planning. The app allows for the highlighting of specific elements, providing insights for the design of urban spaces and conducting research. However, it's essential to adapt this tool to different contexts. NatureNex is a spatial tool for collecting geographical information, identifying locations, and sharing stories. If we were to recruit 50 people to regularly use the app in a specific area, we could potentially gather 100 points and stories related to those locations. This would provide a holistic view of the site's nature interactions, showcasing the differences between various environments such as grasslands, parks, forests, and other landscapes.

Himansu Mishra , WP 1

just NBS (Raymond et al., 2023) and plays a crucial role in mediating between the multi-species community and the functional agencies of regional and urban planning (Houston et al., 2018) (see box 3.1). Whereas the latter represents the rational principles of socio-technological engineering, the former engages in productive counter-mapping of feelings and valuations, thus arranging the arena for emerging reflective equilibria between human and other species concerns. Accordingly, multi-species mapping is a critical step in engaging other species in an inclusive approach to NBS design and planning, and can be seen as a form of non-human political participation. An important corollary is that maps always include the non-living aspects of a territory, which implies that mapping is also a means to identify assemblages of living and non-living entities that eventually are recognised as MSAs, for example, a river, certain fish species, and human fishers. Therefore, mapping is an indispensable input for building more complex models and conceptualizations of the web of interactions in NBA (Schlüter et al., 2025).

3.2. Epistemic justice and vulnerabilities in countermapping NBAs

3.2.1. From mapping to countermapping

The previous deliverables have positioned NBS as a key component of multi-species landscaping practices that foster co-creative niche construction. The concept of NBA has been newly emerging from our current reflection on LL practices. Mapping is a vital activity in landscaping, which we now conceptualise as crafting NBAs (Corner, 2011); maps do not simply represent a landscape, but actively shape it through the interpretations of map users and their resulting actions. Recent advancements in cartography and the use of maps, combined with diverse applications across the social sciences and humanities, have established mapping as a means of creating relationships with spatial territories beyond mere representation (Kitchin et al., 2013). In mapping, the process is as significant as the outcome, and the outcome influences the patterns of action taken by users of the map. Digital technologies allow for developing entirely new approaches to mapping that merge and synthesise across media, for example, in visual story telling (Song et al., 2022).

In this chapter, we focus on the original meaning of maps and exclude metaphorical meanings which are often used for diagrams that show the relationships between different entities, such as a network of stakeholders (“stakeholder mapping”, for instance, (Zingraff-Hamed et al., 2020). Such maps can be interpreted in a spatial context, particularly when examining MSAs. This is crucial because the stakes involved are often tied to spatial structures, as ecological niches exist within specific locations. Additionally, maps serve as a tool to uncover properties of a NBA that might not be immediately visible, linking spatial aspects with other characteristics of the NBS. For instance, analysing a map of an urban park alongside data about the income distribution in its neighbouring area can provide insights into the issue of green gentrification.

We also specify that we will exclude maps that compare different NBS locations across a larger geographic area when assigning specific data points to them, such as in institutional mapping (Primmer et al., 2021). These methods do not focus on mapping

the NBS itself in terms of its internal spatial structures and the related behavioural patterns of both humans and non-humans. They can be important sources of learning in networks of decision-makers and concerned citizens about alternative designs of NBS (Van Der Jagt et al., 2019).

The co-evolutionary approach presents a groundbreaking perspective on maps by moving away from the anthropocentric view that dominates most mapping practices. Traditionally, maps are created by humans for human purposes, such as guiding individuals through a forest during outdoor activities. This human-centered perspective is also reflected in contemporary methods of mapping ecosystem services, which are defined primarily in terms of their benefits to human societies (Maes and Burkhard, 2017; Martínez-Harms and Balvanera, 2012). In this context, both the creators and users of maps are humans. This also applies to advanced approaches in citizen science and postnormal science regarding NBA, as these methods broaden inclusion beyond human expert groups, while remaining within human domains (Jaligot et al., 2019; Lim et al., 2021). The first step in developing a co-evolutionary approach to mapping NBA is to abandon

anthropocentrism, particularly concerning biodiversity, as this is often the standard used to evaluate NBA (IUCN, 2020). This transformation means that specific methods of postnormal science mapping turn inclusive on non-humans: The key example is the role of mapping in community formation, where approaches to human community building (seminally, (Crouch and

Box 3.2: Coproducing spatial patterns at Murray Park

In Murray Park, the pathways were not originally human paths. It was the transformation of animal paths into human paths, which illustrates how Nature-Based Solutions can be approached as process assemblages. In this example, the path does not emerge from a single act of human design or from the agency of deer alone, but from the ongoing interactions between species, materials, and landscape features. For example, the paths are co-produced through the repeated movement of deer, the recognition and adoption of these tracks by people, and the physical characteristics of the terrain that guide both human and non-human convenient best routes for movement. It emphasises that NBS are living, evolving configurations, shaped by interactions that unfold over time and across scales. Like the animal paths that become a human path, many NBS (such as informal green corridors, community woodlands, or wetland restorations) are not simply designed and implemented, but emerge and adapt through contingent relations between ecological processes, human practices, and material conditions.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

Matless, 1996)) can be straightforwardly expanded to building a more-than-human

community of the local ecosystem: Mapping is a constitutive practice of the Living Lab as a multi-species learning community (see box 3.2).

Mapping an NBA cannot be solely reduced to depicting what humans deem worthy to be mapped. It involves significant and complex issues of epistemic justice, which means ensuring that various perspectives from both human and non-human agents are represented without discrimination. This concept of epistemic justice is also relevant for human-only mappings, especially regarding the viewpoints of marginalized and vulnerable populations (Brown and Knopp, 2008). In many respects, vulnerabilities and constraints to express them are a theme shared between humans and other species, implying that mapping methods can apply in more-than-human ways.

For instance, a tourist map represents an area from the perspective of those who can afford to engage in tourism, neglecting how the homeless experience the same space. This discrepancy can obscure potential conflicts: a location may serve as an attraction for tourists while simultaneously providing shelter for the homeless. An affluent tourist might feel

Box 3.3: Exploring the multi-species city at Tartu

A sensory night walk gave us the opportunity to reflect on the unseen lives that share these spaces with us. It was a time to consciously acknowledge the proximity of wild animals in the city. Like many other urban animals, certain species have adapted to the city's rhythms, changing their activity patterns to avoid human presence. These shifts affect not only their behavior but also their prey, as they hunt at different times and navigate an altered urban ecosystem. Their ability to move through human-made spaces — crossing roads, scavenging for food, and finding shelter in hidden corners — speaks to their resilience and ingenuity. Yet it also reminds us that the city is not just ours. It's a shared environment where human and non-human lives intersect and interact in ways we don't often notice. One of the most important lessons from our walk was to learn how to engage our senses differently. Urban animals experience the city in a myriad of ways. Their survival depends on acute senses of smell, hearing, and sight — often finely tuned to pick up cues that we are completely unaware of. As we moved through a park near the edge of the city, we frequently stopped, listened, and smelled. The group absorbed their surroundings through the senses they seldom use to navigate. Hedgehogs, for example, navigate the city by scent trails and sound, finding their way through gardens and alleys using sensory information that we often ignore. They smell not only food but also danger, navigating human-made barriers with precision that belies their small size. The city is, for them, a living, breathing organism full of cues and signals. Walking through the city at night, with its hidden creatures and quiet corners, reminded us of the incredible diversity of life that exists even in the most human-dominated spaces. These animals — whether they are foxes, bats, birds, or hedgehogs — have found ways to survive in a world that wasn't built for them. They adapt, they communicate, and they thrive in ways that we are only beginning to understand. The city, with all its lights, sounds, and structures, is not just ours. It belongs to the creatures who inhabit it alongside us, often unseen but always present. Recognizing this is the first step toward creating urban spaces that are more inclusive, more mindful, and more attuned to the needs of all species.

Nelly Mäekivi, Tartu LL

uncomfortable upon encountering homeless individuals. If a tourist map included the resources available for people experiencing homelessness, would tourists start to avoid areas with a significant presence of homeless people? Furthermore, who conducts these mappings? The police may create a map that tracks the regular locations of the homeless, which is often inaccessible to them. In contrast, the homeless community might produce a self-help map that provides crucial information for their survival in the city. This situation can be mirrored in the non-human realm as well (see box 3.3); for example, ecologists may generate maps that detail how birds inhabit a certain area, including their movements and nesting sites. This resembles a form of surveillance akin to that imposed on the homeless in policing them. In a coevolutionary approach to NBS, a fundamental question arises: how can we incorporate mapping from the perspective of the birds themselves? The instance of the homeless creating their maps exemplifies countermapping that challenges hegemonic narratives and asserts a struggle for recognition (Peluso, 1995).

Epistemic injustice has been a pervasive aspect of human mapping throughout history. A particularly notable phenomenon is the mapping of “terra nullius”, which depicts entire continents as uninhabited land, disregarding Indigenous territories. This mapping approach has been used to justify colonial land appropriation (Bhandar, 2018; Harley, 2011). Interestingly, Indigenous territories, such as hunting grounds, are closely linked to the spatial behaviours of various co-habiting species. Consequently, these territories lack the precise mapping criteria that emerged during Western modernity (Greer, 2017). Such complex phenomena of more-than-human mapping can be easily identified in modern societies, such as in the case of Sami herders in Northern Europe (Johnsen et al., 2024). Similarly, in the case of the homeless, we often observe their companionship with stray dogs (Pearson, 2021). This raises questions about how these dogs perceive and navigate the city's resources, and how their understanding of the urban environment, along with that of the homeless, contrasts with the dominant maps created by municipalities. This example straightforwardly applies to all kinds of wild animals cohabiting with humans in cities (Van Patter, 2023) (see box 3.3). Indeed, as argued in earlier deliverables, in

the Global South, street dogs can even be recognised as members of a NBA in urban nature-based governance (Barua, 2021).

3.2.2. Countermapping NBA

As we see, human mapping of NBA may overlook other species that inhabit the territory. A map depicting a wetland without acknowledging the presence of other species' Umwelts reflects the human appropriation of the wetland, presenting it solely in terms of its human-defined function as NBS in urban water management (Ramírez-Agudelo et al., 2020). This perspective suggests that NBS literally colonises the area it occupies. Such domination contradicts the principle of reciprocity, which is essential for crafting the NBA as a place that promotes multi-species justice (Maller, 2021).

Accordingly, mapping NBA as located in multi-species landscapes can follow the practices of counter-mapping that in recent decades have been adopted by Indigenous people and concerned parties such as NGOs

Box 3.4: Mapping challenges in a multi-species landscape: Barcelona

In our LL we focus on NBS for risk mitigation. Risks are typically mapped, where these are more likely to take place (trying to reflect ecological processes), and which areas are vulnerable to those risks, and potential intensity/severity of the damage. These are technically developed maps based on:

- the best available information -based on an abiotic/physical process occurring on biotic elements (biomass/fuel),
- jointly with some political criteria: recurrence time for floods (e.g. 500 years vs 100 years cover more or less area), or breadth of the strips around houses to keep them "safer" from wildfires (in Catalonia it's 25m fixed, in Valencia is variable according to technical criteria, in Aragon in 20m... -while the fire behaviour is the same).

One key challenge that urban planners face today is that they planned urban expansion without considering wildfire risks -which is recently appearing as new maps. A consequence is that nowadays some areas wouldn't be allowed to be built according to this emerging criterion, but we find that an important part of houses are built already in those risky areas.

On the other side, we have the NBS protagonists, who are the shepherds with their flocks. The sheep and goats move around, trying to optimise their feeding activity: if possible, they walk the minimum to eat as much as possible. This means that shepherds and their dogs need to push them to walk further and not to exhaust the grass, but also to keep within the artificial 25m limits of the buffers around urban areas. One of the conflicts they face is that, as soon as the goats/sheep find an adjacent area with humidity (gully/watercourse), or a tasty grass area (below tress, as a garden or part of a farmland or forestland) they tend to move towards those pieces of land. The dog/shepherd need to bring them out from them in order to avoid a fine. In my interpretation, this means a mismatch between the affordances available physically and the institutional barriers for their accessibility. A few municipalities are starting to expand the buffer areas to include some "expansion" areas (if of their municipal ownership), to cover those natural movements, or to facilitate permits of private landowners in case those lands are private. Therefore our "mapping" would show overlapping interests/needs in the same space!.

Elena Gorriz, Barcelona LL

and researcher-activists (Chao, 2022; Povinelli, 2016). Counter-mapping challenges the official maps in making the Indigenous views and claims on the land explicit (Sparke, 1998). This strategy has its pitfalls, as the resulting map may miss the fluidity and dynamic relationality between people and land. Taking this into account, counter-mapping can be adopted as a strategy for mapping NBS which realises epistemic justice (see box 3.4).

Interestingly, counter-mapping for humans can differ fundamentally from standard mapping. In human counter-mapping, emotions and emotionally charged events often play a crucial role in challenging official maps (Kwan, 2007). This approach is particularly significant for addressing vulnerabilities. For instance, maps can reflect race, gender, or sexual orientation by highlighting emotions associated with certain places, such as fear experienced by vulnerable

Box 3.5: Mapping stories at Tartu

We use telling, collecting and facilitating story telling as a means of strengthening human relation with the multispecies urban environment by bridging subjective experience, local knowledge and relations with other species. We gather stories through an online form and storytelling events. Simpler stories can be mere notes about encountering other species, more complex stories could be place lore, biographic narratives, explanations of the urban environment and history or even fictional narratives. We created a web page and an app to collect simpler stories of encounters. Through geolocation option the app enables mapping of stories. This is limited to a point of location. A map of locations of observations can be derived from these and potentially also some kind of statistics from it. As stories unfold in time and space, a more complex digital tool could enable other, more relevant spatial features to stories beyond a point of location – for example a line, an area, height, temporality, or patterns relevant to the story. Our story telling events take place in a fixed place or during a walk in the LL area. Therefore they support a place-related storytelling activity. While some stories told are explanations of a nearby feature, many stories rather take an inspiration from the surroundings and divert from the place or walking trajectory. Stories involving other species enrich interpretations of the urban environment with cultural knowledge but also with the sense of copresence and multiple perspectives. Stories can state a fact but they also open up subjective worlds and other spaces (narrative, folklore, artistic, psychological, alternate uumwelts). Bringing together different perspectives, subjective worlds and spatial-temporal structures, stories and shared storytelling provide a glance into the meaningful richness of local environments.”

Tiit Remm, Tartu LL

groups. These emotions are often evident in different behavioural patterns, such as men using different routes than women. Researchers employ various methods to identify these emotions, and one especially effective approach is counter-mapping. This method is valuable because vulnerable groups may hesitate to express their feelings in traditional interviews and surveys. An “emotion map” of the area can directly capture their sentiments (Pile, 2010) (see box 3.5). By focusing on emotions, this approach transcends the artificial barrier between humans and non-human entities,

which language often creates. Both humans and other sentient beings share many emotions due to their common phylogenetic origins (Damasio, 2019).

Countermapping can be modified for other species, however, only via human mediation. Therefore, MSAs become a key actor in countermapping: The human member is not “representing” the non-human members of the MSA but stays in a reciprocal embodied relationship. For example, dog owners may record perceived emotions as expressed by dogs when walking across an area. Generally, making non-human emotions explicit by standard science methods requires considerable investments in ethological research. Therefore, countermapping may adopt a citizen science approach in collecting many observations and shared experiences in MSAs, such as of birdwatcher communities. In fact, citizen science can generate thick information about emotional stances of other species via highly individualised observations (Ackerman, 2023). Hence, collecting a huge amount of citizen observations can produce dynamic counter-maps. This is especially important in the context of NBA where climate change may cause many behavioural novelties of other species, such as animals looking for new foraging opportunities in residential areas. In summary, if we view NBS as a coevolutionary technology of crafting NBAs by multiple species, mapping plays a crucial role in establishing relationships between the landscape and its human and non-human inhabitants. In this context, the interplay between standard mapping and counter-mapping holds transformative potential. This means that the typical maps used for planning an NBS are complemented and challenged by various alternative mapping activities. This interplay drives the learning process in LLs and helps to foster the development of these spaces as multi-species communities.

3.3 The diversity and multiplicity of maps

3.3.1. Inclusive projection of other species' Umwelts on human maps

What is a map? At first glance, a map appears to be a cartographic product, described as a "mobile immobile" in the words of Latour (2011). However, adhering to this

perspective could lead us to the pitfalls of anthropocentrism, particularly in the context of the cultural dominance of certain ideas about maps that arose during the Enlightenment, rationalism, imperialism, and colonialism (Edney, 2011).

To begin with, we can view mapping as a cognitive universal and as a fundamental aspect of the Umwelts of all living beings (Rescorla, 2017). In order to navigate their environments, all living beings must rely on some form of mapping. However, these maps do not need to resemble human cartographic products, and even among humans, cognitive maps can vary significantly (seminally, (Downs and Stea, 2011). Non-human mapping shares several characteristics with human mapping, such as the ability to orient themselves using spatial beacons and triangulating locations in space (Jeffery et al., 2024). However, this does not necessarily mean that non-human maps

represent space with mathematical accuracy. What matters is whether the sensorimotor action patterns effectively support the functions required for a living being's survival and flourishing. Cognitive maps serve as a link between the Uexküllian *Wirkwelt* (the effective world) and the *Merkwelt* (the perceptual world).

Other species in the NBA utilize non-human mapping for various purposes. Most commonly, these are cognitive maps in a broad sense, but they can also encompass externalised symbolic media, the most famous example being the waggle dance of bees (Chittka, 2024). Many behaviours

Box 3.6: Smellscapes at night in Tartu LL

As we walked, we explained how animals like birds and bats adapt to urban environments. Streetlights, for example, create a patchwork of shadows and brightness that some animals avoid while others use to their advantage. Slow-flying bats, especially, rely on darker spaces where they can avoid predators. Fast-flying bats, on the other hand, are drawn to lights to feed on all the insects who are also attracted to artificial light sources. It's easy to forget that every light we switch on changes the dynamics of the space for someone else. For these creatures, the city at night is both a haven and a challenge.

As we moved through a park near the edge of the city, we frequently stopped, listened, and smelled. The group absorbed their surroundings through the senses they seldom use to navigate. Hedgehogs, for example, navigate the city by scent trails and sound, finding their way through gardens and alleys using sensory information that we often ignore. They smell not only food but also danger, navigating human-made barriers with precision that belies their small size. The city is, for them, a living, breathing organism full of cues and signals. The smells of the night were particularly telling. As we moved through a park, the air changed — from the metallic tang of the city center to the earthy smells of damp soil and cut grass. For animals, these smells form a map, guiding them through the urban maze and helping them avoid predators or find mates. It's a world that exists parallel to ours, hidden but ever-present.

Nelly Mäekivi, Tartu LL

exhibited by other species can be interpreted as a form of mapping intended for other members of the same species, although these are often transient (see box 3.6). For instance, marking spaces with pheromones can indicate paths and locations. Such maps are tied to specific locations and cannot be transported, unlike the information conveyed through the waggle dance. We can approach such different forms of mapping with the help of semiotics as deployed in D.2.2. Marking spaces is indexical mapping that directly elicits actions in space, following landscape beacons is iconic mapping, and the waggle dance is symbolic mapping.

When discussing mapping, it is essential to distinguish between a "map," which is the result of mapping and the mapping activity itself, which may not produce a portable or enduring medium. Many behaviours related to territoriality can be viewed as forms of mapping. It is also important to

differentiate mapping from other types of territorial signaling, such as threats directed at intruders. Birdsong can be considered a form of mapping, as it is a continuous activity that does not respond to specific situations. In this context, we might say that the soundscape created by birdsong serves as a living map of the territory from the perspective of the resident birds (Despret, 2019; Hao et al., 2021). Other birds learn about this Umwelt, just as researchers with sophisticated technology can record the soundscape (see Box 3.7).

Box 3.7: Participatory sound mapping and soundscapes at Cagliari

The term soundwalking refers to walking through sounds, i.e. focusing on the exploration and auditory experience of the soundscape. The environment, the soundscape and walking in nature share in a person's well-being. This project, by means of immersive listening in selected natural contexts, aims to activate (I) processes of awareness of one's own internal states in relation to the environment for improved well-being and (II) a better relationship with the environment itself. The project envisages the co-construction of sound maps through the sharing of audio recordings synchronously acquired via smartphone at different points in a single natural environment. The sound maps aim to signal the presence of natural micro-environments in which participants have experienced comfort and acoustic restorativeness in urban spaces. The capture of sounds was followed by the administration of an evaluation questionnaire to support the participants' reconstruction of a perceptual analysis of the explored acoustic environment. The audio recordings were acquired by the researchers at the same time as the participants' evaluation and subsequently processed to determine the descriptors of the corresponding acoustic environment. According to the Citizen Science paradigm, the explorer-listener can immerse himself/herself in an evolving reality and experience himself/herself as a citizen-scientist, thus contributing personally to the body of studies in salutogenic psychoacoustics. Collective sound maps could function as a supplementary tool to objective, non-participatory maps, i.e. those based on simulation, as well as fixed monitoring stations. Localised sound events take on a social significance that is mixed with individual contemplation, imagination and state of mind.

Oriana Mosca, Cagliari LL

Soundscapes can become an important orientation for human designers of an NBS. For example, public parks are normally designed according to human aesthetic preferences, today also having biodiversity criteria in mind. Once we consider the soundscape, designers may consider using certain material arrangements in a park to reduce the noise pollution from neighbouring areas in the interest of birds and their sensory conditions (Cristea et al., 2024).

The traditional view of maps has been heavily influenced by the military and political interests of longstanding absolutist states and their successor nation-states. This view aligned closely with the interests of property owners and their creditors, aiming to clearly identify landed assets (Vanuxem, 2022). As a result, these maps are often artificial and fail to capture the complex realities of how various species interact with their environments (see box 3.8). Specifically, maps of NBA should illustrate the spatial aspects of the different species' niches within the territory where the NBS is

Box 3.8: Overcoming human borders via transformative digital mapping: Beskydy virtual commons

In the Beskydy region, there exists a simple human institution, namely the border between Slovakia and Czechia, which is also a linguistic border. One of the significant achievements of COEVOLVERS is to foster cross-border collaboration by creating tools like the Virtual nature and Virtual commons platform for knowledge sharing. These tools improve how people communicate and collaborate in coordinating their actions facing climate change and avoid the “tragedy of the commons” in using increasingly scarce water resources. There have long been challenges from both the Slovak and Czech sides. The cross-border forest area is hilly and people live in valleys only connected via long and winding roads. By air, it's only a few kilometres apart, but by car, it can take several hours. Therefore, digital tools can help bridge these challenging cross-border distances as well as strengthening the cross-border understanding of common goals.

LL Beskydy team

located. Defining NBS maps in terms of niches has significant implications for mapping practices. Traditionally, human mapping has focused on establishing clear boundaries; however, this approach—rooted in the political delineation of human territories and property—must be reevaluated. Many species have niches that cannot be accurately defined by human-made boundaries. For some species, their niche is much smaller than the area encompassed by the NBA due to their limited foraging and mating ranges. In contrast, species such as migratory birds have broader, interconnected niches that extend beyond specific areas. Additionally, there will be

numerous cross-border niches to consider. Thus, a multidimensional mapping approach for NBA must capture these spatial complexities.

In a sense, the multispecies NBA relates to assemblages of humans who take collective action in implementing an NBA: Ecosystems do not pay respect to human

borders, and so human collective action must adapt (see box 3.8).

From this, we can conclude that there is no single map for an NBA. Mapping an NBA involves creating a multidimensional database that reflects its biodiversity and enables the generation of user-specific species maps. Given the vast variety of life forms within an NBA, mapping them presents a significant technical challenge. This observation raises the question of how human mapping of NBA can also include other species mapping, such as projecting a bird species soundscape on a human map. Modern digital technologies allow for many novel approaches such as tagging border locations with bird song files. Digital technologies can already be used to

publish various layers and scales of maps within a single data file, allowing for maps to be generated based on users' specific needs, including personalised options (see box 3.9). For example, we can design a map for birds and easily switch from a human-centric map to a bird-focused one. We can also zoom in to create a detailed map of the area surrounding an ant hive. The limitations we face are not technical; they are

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Box 3.9: Virtual Nature Tool at Murray Park

We are using the VNT to map where people go in the park and which areas they find most interesting. The VNT not only helps us track this movement but also maps the multisensory experiences captured in photographs. Additionally, we have included a questionnaire for visitors to fill out, either during or after their park tour. This survey allows people to describe their experiences and highlight what they found interesting. Our questionnaire incorporates questions from previous Coevolvers surveys, exploring feelings about nature and what Murray Park means to individuals. With each photo taken, users can add a description that goes beyond mere visuals—it can include textual memories. This may lead us to map emotions and memories through stories, reflecting the park's history. The journey begins at the park gate. Visitors can enjoy short video snippets featuring moving trees, 360-degree views, and sounds of wind blowing and birds singing. Users can choose different paths marked by arrows and explore various spaces, each offering distinct 360-degree views, sounds, and storyboards about specific items, such as a lake or a river. Clicking on the river will reveal common bird species found near it, providing educational insights as visitors progress through the park. The experience emphasizes a multisensory approach, allowing for inclusive opportunities to engage with the park. The photos taken and locations chosen contribute to a co-creative process involving the Living Lab and the local community, whose feedback has shaped the VNT's design. The local community is excited about the VNT, and we plan to link it to the Murray Park webpage for easy access.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

primarily financial, as considerable personpower and special equipment are required for this work.

In sum, we can define an NBA map as an assemblage of multi-media data that includes other species mapping media. This is another example of how the object assemblage of the NBA projects into assemblages of media and actors relating to it. Obviously, this creates many design challenges since digital media have limitations. For example, dogs use olfactory signals that are similar in function to birdsongs in marking a territory without resulting in portable and durable media. Their signals cannot be easily translated into digital media. However, we can record behaviours associated with dog's sniffing, such as observed during dog walks, and construct a behavioural map of the dog's olfactory Umwelt. Solving such challenges is the craft of more-than-human mapping.

3.3.2 The etics and emics of mapping multi-species Umwelts

When we differentiate between the three stages of mapping, as well as its outcomes and applications, it is important to recognize that each stage has its unique characteristics. Mapping is not solely focused on producing a map as an end result. As previously mentioned, in many social science contexts, the act of mapping itself serves an independent purpose as a form of expression, which can even have therapeutic benefits (see box 3.10). In these instances, the primary focus of the mapping is the mapper themselves rather than other users. The resulting map can express emotions and provide a sense of catharsis. While researchers may utilise these maps to assess vulnerabilities, the findings are not specifically intended for other users' orientation.

This expressive use of mapping is familiar from the valuable experience gained through art-based methods in eco-social transformation (Pearson et al., 2018). In many cases, these mapping exercises aim to increase awareness among citizens and practitioners, with no intention of utilising the material further. However, this is not always the case. For instance, in community mapping efforts, grassroots-level mapping has been employed to enhance the city hall's decor, helping to communicate

the identity of local places to visitors (Crouch and Matless, 1996; Perkins, 2018). Similarly, in Living Labs, mapping can be a tool for fostering a shared sense of community.

This discussion highlights the important distinction between emics and etics in mapping. We can view maps as tools for recording and displaying the Umwelts of living beings, hence transforming the emics into etics. When vulnerable individuals create maps, they reveal their meaningful relationships to space, making the emics of their Umwelts accessible to

Box 3.10: Expressive and therapeutic countermapping of the healing garden at Pomáz-Kiskovácsi

Within the Healing Garden LL, our multisensory observations aim to map the garden as a living system including its human and non-human agents. In addition to visual experience, we also examine other sensory impressions, since the perception of our environment is linked to sounds, smells, touch, movements, etc. In many cases, we can also better perceive and understand our encounters with plants and animals through our different senses. We have applied and combined audiovisual and sensory tools and methodologies that allow us to listen, observe, hear and collect information about the environment and the living beings through embodied visual and sonic sensations. These techniques, to capture the diversity of sensual perceptions include: soundscapes audio recordings at different points in the garden, timelapse video recordings at different times of the year, visual and sensory observations ("sit-spot technique").

Aural experiences are important in a healing garden design because they have a deep impact on well-being and contribute to a therapeutic environment. Soundscapes are used to explore the auditory environment of the garden, focusing on both human and non-human living beings. We can observe which areas of the garden are noisier or quieter, as these sound dynamics can influence the healing potential of the garden. We identify the different natural, artificial, or human-made sounds present in various parts of the garden, noting how they change with the seasons. Thus, unlike static, conventional maps, soundscapes can capture a temporal dimension. Furthermore, soundscapes allow us to reveal sounds which originate outside of the hospital garden (such as the noise of traffic) but have an impact on the garden's sensory experience."

Beáta Pántya, Orsolya Lazányi, Pomáz-Kiskovácsi

others: The observer diagnoses vulnerabilities etically. Eventually, there is the possibility communicating this diagnosis back as a method of verification, if the concerned individuals agree with the diagnosis. In the case of non-human entities, we cannot use the same approach; instead, we can rely on the Uexküllian dialectics of *Wirkwelt* (the world as experienced) and *Merkwelt* (the world as perceived) to interpret their observed actions as expressions of their relationships with space. From this perspective, many human maps also serve as a way to illustrate spatialised affordances for human action, relating to the niche in terms of the human Umwelt. More specifically, we differentiate between the niche concerning functional

interdependencies, such as resources available, and the Umwelt in terms of subjective perceptions of that niche.

This perspective already applies to human maps, which primarily represent the cultural niches of people (Nagatsu et al., 2023). For instance, a tourist map highlights points of interest for travelers and the routes to access them. These locations serve as affordances for activities typically associated with leisure. This viewpoint suggests that by examining a tourist map, we can reconstruct the temporary Umwelt of an average tourist, identifying which affordances are relevant to that imaginary person and what types of activities they are likely to engage in. Essentially, the tourist map illustrates the cultural niche of tourism. However, the question arises about how this map is actually created. We can distinguish between etic and emic approaches, as well as the perspectives of different groups. For example, the local tourist bureau may designate tourist locations based on past data and assumptions about potential affordances. This represents the emic perspective of the tourism agency officials, although they may position their assertions as etic. As we know, such assumptions can be inaccurate: the official tourist map is essentially an artificial representation of a hypothetical Umwelt featuring assumed affordances for tourists. They may fail to address the emics of the independent adventurer.

Modern technology enhances the capabilities of mapping by introducing participatory tools that allow tourists to personalise their experiences publicly. For instance, individuals can add locations to a digital map and provide comments, moving beyond the static maps created by local tourist bureaus. These participatory mechanisms deepen our understanding of tourists' experiences, transcending the artificial constructs of the tourist bureau. There are two ways to approach the data collected from these participatory mapping efforts: one is to interpret the meanings intended by the users, while the other is to consider the data as evidence of specific actions taken. In the latter case, we can analyze participatory mapping data as a form of behavioural mapping (Mishra et al., 2023; Vidal et al., 2022).

This example illustrates an important methodological principle of mapping Umwelts: we can record activities related to specific locations within a spatial coordinate system, allowing us to create a map that depicts the relationships of various actors to these

locations (Petrtýlová and Jaššo, 2022) (see box 3.11). For instance, if we note that many tourists visit a particular spot along the river to swim, we can identify this location as an opportunity for swimming. However, this approach is behaviourist and focuses on an etic perspective, meaning we cannot fully access the Umwelt as defined by the personal significance of that activity, which would be the emic perspective. While the case of swimming may seem straightforward, interviewing individuals may reveal that this location is particularly suited for parents with young children, while competitive swimmers might consider it less ideal.

Box 3.11: Citizen science and mapping

In autumn 2023, I was in Tartu to discuss collaborative methods. During the workshop, they identified a need to collect stories not just through traditional methods like pen and paper “or letters, but also using a digital tool that enables a faster and broader data collection process for narratives. We envisioned it as a citizen science app. The concept of citizen science was centered on capturing stories that reveal the relationships and connections between humans and non-humans within their living environments. These stories would focus on spatial references, highlighting the relationship between land, place, the story, and the individual involved—three key elements. Citizen science could be utilized to gather information about places and perceptions of space, exploring why individuals were in those locations and what they encountered there. This would connect to the intent behind their presence. To facilitate this, we established a clear tool division: one track for citizen science would involve objective questions and narratives, along with pictures and data uploads related to locations, species, and specific encounters. The other track would solely focus on collecting stories from various places and species, which we would analyze qualitatively. We are currently developing a method for analyzing this data. At present, the app is designed as a straightforward platform. In the future, if funding allows, it could evolve into an independent app. Within our group, I hope everyone will use and pilot it. Our goal is to eventually create a permanent app. Currently, there are existing apps for bird and animal spotting, as well as others that focus on stories about specific places and sights, including trees. However, none of these apps combine story collection linked to encounters and citizen science spotting.”

Himansu Mishra, WP 1

The etic perspective allows us to formulate hypotheses about the emic experiences within an organism's Umwelt. This approach can be extended to other species, as it relies primarily on observed behaviours, and is referred to as “ecological repertoire analysis” (Farina and Belgrano, 2006; Maran, 2020). Essentially, we can create a map representing the Umwelt of birds based on their actions in space. However, this task is not straightforward, as we often encounter significant challenges when trying to observe and track those actions. For instance, while GPS devices can accurately pinpoint movements and locations, they do not provide insight into the specific activities or purposes behind those movements. Similarly, even a dog owner might struggle to understand what their unleashed dog is doing during explorations in the

forest, especially if the dog is out of sight. This challenge is not fundamentally different from the difficulties encountered when trying to fully track and comprehend the actions of tourists.

Behavioural mapping is a well-established approach in environmental psychology, grounded in the concept of affordances (Ng, 2016). Researchers observe the action patterns of specific populations within a certain area, for example, children playing in an urban neighborhood or users of a public garden (Rastgo et al., 2024; Vidal et al., 2022). These actions provide direct insight into the affordances of the environment. However, there is still an additional layer of meaning to consider in this behaviourist approach (Shilon and Eizenberg, 2024). For instance, if we identify certain trees as favourite climbing spots, we can assert that those trees offer affordances for climbing. Yet, we may not fully understand why children appreciate these climbing affordances. One child might find a tree particularly easy to climb, while another may enjoy the challenge of a more difficult tree. Therefore, it is crucial for researchers to add qualitative interviews to behavioural mapping to gain a deeper understanding of these perspectives. We can certainly develop

Box 3.12: Affordances and varieties of mapping at Barcelona

The law stipulates a 25-meter strip from the last house extending into the forest. However, this area varies; some parts are rocky, while others are grassy, filled with shrubs and trees, which depends on the specific context. The town needs to remove the trees and shrubs, and the shepherd must direct the animals into the 25-meter corridor. However, the animals may stray for flowers and grass, often disregarding the 25-meter strip. It then falls to the shepherd and the herding dog to keep the flock within the designated area. In traditional herding, animals have much more freedom of movement. In an urban setting, the shepherd cannot easily control where the animals go. It can be problematic when sending the dog to assist; if the dog frequently returns, it can stress the flock, causing them to stop eating. Therefore, the shepherd must find a balance between using the dog and allowing the animals to graze.

There are different types of maps needed:

- 1) A map depicting the legal 25-meter buffer strip,
- 2) A map showing the movement patterns of the animals,
- 3) A map illustrating fire behavior, as fire can behave differently in various areas.

Consequently, the 25-meter strip may not be sufficient everywhere. Each area requires context-specific mapping tailored to that particular location, as well as to the shepherd and dog involved. Some municipalities are considering the idea that even with a 25-meter buffer strip, there should also be grassland available for animals to roam freely, allowing them to follow their natural instincts rather than being tightly grazed. Sheep require approximately 8 hours of grazing, which may be interrupted by 4 NBS, followed by 4 hours of free grazing. While the law serves as a policy driver for NBS, municipalities have a legal mandate to keep these areas clean. However, there is a risk of inaccurate maps, including administrative maps and those representing the natural landscape.

Elena Gorriz and Marc Rovellada, Barcelona LL

hypotheses about the Umwelts of other species by mapping the affordances revealed

in their observed actions (see box 3.12). However, we must exercise caution in interpreting these observations through the lens of human perspectives. For example, serious misunderstandings can arise when we apply human concepts of 'property' to data regarding how other species map their territories (for the example of dogs, Gibson, 2021). Nevertheless, when researchers adhere to strict hermeneutical procedures, the connection between affordances and actions becomes a powerful tool for creating species-specific maps.

3.4. Functions of mapping NBA

The traditional map, as a cartographic product, often leads to a perception of maps as mere representative tools, encouraging the "gaze" of a detached observer. However, today's digital media introduce a much wider variety of forms and uses for maps (as noted by Cartwright already in (1999)). Digital representations of space allow for various functionalities that do not require users to adopt a detached observer's perspective. For example, they can provide direct navigation, integrate easily accessible information through hyperlinks, and support interactive media, including gaming applications.

One significant aspect of digital mapping is that it does not necessitate a vicarious visual representation of space. Contrary to common belief about maps as abstracting and compressing spatial information, it could even permit a 1:1 representation of a spatial segment. In this case, the "map" is not the visual representation itself but rather the software that facilitates user actions, leading to the construction of individual spatial experiences. For instance, a map designer may offer users different options for virtual walks displayed on the screen. This can result in an abstraction similar to that of a conventional map, such as a topological subway map, where the designer selects locations that provide significant information and experiences. These locations may also link to digital storytelling files. In this scenario, the map is not visibly presented to the user; instead, it is implicit in the flow of actions enabled by the software design.

These technological developments have increasingly blurred the lines between maps as static results of mapping and stories as accounts of events and processes unfolding

in time. Maps can incorporate stories, and they can also obtain narrative aesthetic dynamics (Caquard and Cartwright, 2014; Roth, 2021). We will pursue this synthesis of narratives and mapping in the next chapter in more detail. At this point, it is sufficient to state that mapping an NBS obtains a central position in narrating its coevolutionary dynamics.

As a general rule, any map—whether explicit or implicit—should maintain the topology of the standard spatial map. This principle is well illustrated by subway maps, which do not need to show the actual distances between stations; they only need to reflect the spatial relationships within the geographic network. In other words, alternatives to standard maps should retain the ability to be projected onto the standard map, similar to how subway stations correspond to locations on a city map. This is crucial for countermapping, which otherwise allows for significant flexibility. However, since we aim to adopt a multi-species perspective, there must be a shared frame of reference. This is also essential for ensuring that NBA maps are compatible with maps used in urban and regional planning.

Maps are essential for describing and planning NBS, such as when designing an urban park. This illustrates the typical role of maps: their representational function. However, representation itself can be an ambiguous concept. Traditional mapping focuses on portraying spatial structures like locations, distances, and elevations. Yet, there are many other forms of representation that connect spatial maps to non-spatial features. For example, we can create a map that shows the frequency of criminal acts across different neighbourhoods. This approach can also apply to a multi-species niche perspective; for example, we might map resource availability for a specific species or track incidents of human-non-human encounters, which are relevant when implementing rewilding strategies. If we enrich such data by story-telling, it is possible to include the emics of multi-species relationality at the NBS, in particular, if MSAs are involved who engage in emotional mapping of the NBA as a place, thus relying on established methods of mapping places (Turk, 2019).

Representation often follows an etic perspective, even when the focus is on subjective data. For example, an emotion map may attempt to illustrate the emotions of vulnerable individuals in a way that appears objectified, as previously discussed (see

box 3.13). One rationale for this approach is statistical. While emotion mapping is also used as an artistic medium, these maps tend to be highly individualised (Harmon and Clemans, 2009). If researchers gather a collection of these personalised maps, they can achieve generalizations, even from a statistical standpoint, depending on the sample size involved (Donnelly et al., 2020).

In participatory mapping, there is a shift toward the expressive use of maps (see box 3.14). This is achieved when researchers aggregate a large number of individual expressive maps into a generalized emotion map. Generally, expressive maps capture feelings associated with a place, while representational maps focus on the physical characteristics of space. An example of participatory place mapping is community mapping, which is directly relevant to NBS

mapping (Perkins, 2018). Community maps are products of creative expression by community members and do not claim to be objective representations of their area. Expressive maps represent a specific type of the broader performative function of maps (Roberts, 2016). Critical geographers argue that maps seldom serve only a

3.13: Mapping emotions at Tartu

In Tartu LL mapping has been used in several activities. Mapping workshops related to emotional geographies where participants from the areal use maps (or areal images) and group discussions to define, locate and share places they perceive as pleasant, unpleasant and places with a high potential for developing urban nature. As a special focus we have asked about places where people “meet” the nature in the city – for example places to go for a stroll or places they highlight in relation to meeting some other species. The resulting maps on paper and notes form discussions give a valuable input for understanding the tendencies of spatial arrangement of perception and interactions with urban nature in the area. Due to cartographic starting point, the results are easily used in GIS based urban planning and governance. While the workshop empowers local voices, it gives access primarily to most dominant features and leaves more subjective worlds hidden.

Garden visits, sensory and umwelt walks are activities that help to cut out from the everyday, stop and notice the multispecies environment around. With mindfulness, guided perception and additional knowledge they produce greater awareness and finer recognition in mental mapping of a place. In practice, garden visits bring people together in a local garden and around a focus topic (birds, plants) to share some knowledge, notice natural and human made affordances, presence, traces and potentialities of other species. Walks bring people to public spaces where some expert knowledge about the environment around and noticing guidance is provided. A visit to a garden helps to map the multiple layers, dimensions and perspectives in a limited place and as depending on a fixed perspective – a local mental map. Umwelt and sensory walks similarly help to map the environment but instead of a fixed local perspective the mapping is organised around the spatiality of a linear stroll and already involves an objective narrative structure. These activities help to map locally; scaling to a larger area like an urban district is problematic due to the loss of subjective relevance and perspective related meaningfulness in scaling and abstraction. Human physical and social activity is useful in supporting multi-sensory awareness but it is also deceptive. While humans and other animals share a place for a moment, the spatiality of a flying bird or a worm in the soil are different and incongruent with the abstract cartographic map. To highlight these differences, the garden visits series is called “üleadne elurikkus” or biodiversity over the fence.”

Tiit Remm, Tartu LL

representational purpose; instead, they actively shape the space they depict. A key example is the act of drawing borders on a map that represent institutions like property rights (Cooper, 1998). These maps are highly performative because they express property claims, which are then reinforced by the actions of those who use the map. For instance, a border drawn on a map may lead to the physical transformation of space, such as planting a hedge along the border, prompting neighbours to adjust their behavior accordingly. Over time, this initial drawing of borders becomes a tangible reality in the physical space, thereby solidifying the property claims through the actions of various groups.

We can generalise these observations to the non-human dimension. Non-human mapping

includes a wide range of performative actions that create and sustain borders and internal spatial structures, as typically associated with territorial behaviour. We refer to such actions as signposting. As mentioned previously, signposting can take many forms, such as sounds or olfactory signaling. The relationship between signposting and the physical landscape as perceived by humans is multi-valued and complex, as

3.14: Participatory mapping at Murray park

We utilized an A1 size printed map during our project, allowing participants to sit around it with sticky notes and images of animals. They had pens to make notes directly on the map. The goal was to gather collective experiences about the area, including where people walk and how they engage with nonhumans. We presented different layers of information:

1. Path Layer: We began by mapping out paths. Each participant shared their thoughts and engaged with the map, noting where they typically walk and why they choose those routes, including where they take their dogs. Our next focus was on inclusivity: we aimed to make paths accessible to individuals with disabilities and parents with strollers, creating wider and smoother paths in the park. This approach led mothers to start using these paths more frequently.

2. Historic Sites Layer: We marked historical sites on the map, including locations of past battles and farming activities. For instance, we highlighted the story of a famous stone where a notable event occurred during a battle.

3. Access Layer: We indicated locations of gates and parking areas to improve accessibility within the park.

4. Water Layer: This layer included streams and ponds within the park, along with the associations people have with water. We shared the history of ice skating; while the ice skating pond is no longer in use, the curling pond remains active. There were stories about individuals who originally drove the ice skating activities, but concerns over safety led to their decline. The conflict surrounding horse riding on the paths was also noted, as the hoofprints from horses created issues with path conditions, which have yet to be adequately addressed.

We have a copy of the filled map, which includes information about nonhumans and their interactions. Participants used sticky notes to identify deer and foxes, sharing short stories and points about specific places. Now, we have a Miro board-style representation of the park, which was well-received. The more people enjoyed the experience, the more they engaged creatively in the exercise.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

in the case of bird soundscapes (Farina et al., 2014). This complexity is further leveraged when we approach the landscape in terms of multi-species signposting. As argued in D2.2, one method to cope with such complexity is to focus on iconic species which are embedded in wide-ranging ecological networks in which they may play a critical role in sustaining the local ecosystem and NBS (Davies and Tippler, 2024). A paradigmatic example is oaks, which are ecological pivots that also play a significant role in the human perceptual structuring of a landscape (Cavender-Bares, 2019; Löff et al., 2016). In such cases, human cultural signposting when sustaining landscapes with oaks can also be viewed as multi-species signposting of MSAs involving humans and other species centered on oaks.

Performative maps involve both the creators and users of the map. The aim of a multi-species mapping project for NBS is to highlight these areas as hotspots for biodiversity and to promote initiatives like the rewilding of green spaces. Additionally, the creators seek to encourage users to take specific actions. In this context, performative maps help facilitate actions by shaping how users think about and perceive their environment. For example, a municipality might organize a permanent exhibition of community maps to enhance citizens' sense of place, which is crucial for inspiring actions that sustain and enhance biodiversity. A performative map has the potential to

3.15: Community maps at Beskydy

We are currently using various virtual tools and planning a physical exhibition as a result of an agreement made with stakeholders during a meeting. The event will take place in a beautiful old barn near the local heritage museum. For two months from now both locals and tourists will have the opportunity to attend the exhibition and find out more about COEVOLVERS activities Coevolvers. Additionally, we will create a nature education trail using digital tools in physical environments. Visitors will be able to access Nature letters via QR codes placed at various location. These letters personalized stories about nature, contributed by individuals who take the perspective of non-humans. The stories will cover not only different species but also soil, water and other ecological elements, and they will be prepared in collaboration with experts on specific topics. The content will include both audio and visual components. All of this will be connected to a Virtual commons platform, functioning as a map with links to the stories tied to particular locations. The Nature letters represent a nature-based solution aimed at increasing our understanding of multispecies justice and management. For example, a species of butterfly, which is only found in the Beskydy region, is under threat due to changes in its habitat. So the butterfly writes a letter to people, telling them his story and explaining how the changing environment is affecting the lives of butterflies. At the same time, however, he suggests ways in which the landscape can be managed to suit him. The Nature letters project will connect these unique places by linking them to the virtual platform, where visitors can access both audiovisual stories and written accounts accompanied by graphics. We aim to identify ca 10-15 locations with these physical links, integrating QR codes in the natural environment that connect to our virtual platform.

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encourage individuals to care for other species. This process is often driven by the designers of the mapping project, reflecting a "top-down" approach. Similarly, participatory mapping allows vulnerable groups to create maps that raise awareness and motivate actions addressing their concerns, particularly in their engagement with authorities. The expressive function of mapping reveals that maps may not be the main goal of mapping, following the adage that the way is the goal. This is well recognised in the therapeutic use of mapping by vulnerable people who otherwise may not feel able to express their feelings and concerns. This observation is relevant when considering other species who cannot do the mapping by themselves. Vicarious mapping by humans or specifically MSAs can be a substitute. These approaches can also contribute to motivating and enabling the emergence of MSAs in the community centred on the NBA (Kim, 2023). There is a direct link between mapping and endogenous formation of stakeholders, as discussed in the previous section (Mere-Roncal et al., 2021).

In sum, the coevolutionary approach to mapping mobilises the whole range of mapping functions with the aim of enhancing the inclusiveness of doing the NBS as a multi-species co-creative niche construction. A key instrument is a digital platform that integrates this diversity of mappings and makes the multi-species maps available to users.

3.5. Conclusion

As we discussed in the previous chapter, a critical challenge of Nature-based governance is effectively using tools to cultivate embodied relationality in NBAs. Mapping serves as one such tool, originally intended to represent the spatial structure of an NBA, such as a forest in Murray Park. However, nurturing relationality requires moving away from conventional, representational, and anthropocentric approaches to cartography. Instead of focusing on the end product of mapping, we shift our emphasis to the process of mapping itself. This activity becomes an embodied practice that engages humans emotionally with the places where they coexist with non-human entities. In this sense, the map transforms into an expressive medium for MSAs, rather

than simply serving as an "objective" representation of the ecosystem. Like in the conclusion to the previous chapter, we pinpoint the strong conceptual and methodological connection to Indigenous practices of countermapping.

Recognising the importance of mapping is a significant strategic insight derived from LL practices. The ability to diagnose the convergence of these practices without a predetermined "project master plan" offers strong evidence for the co-evolutionary potential of mapping. Our strategic conclusion is that the design of NBS should always include systematic and multi-aspectual mapping practices, as a pivotal element in the institutionalisation of the NBA as a form of multi-species cohabitation. This stays in the tradition of cartography as a means of institutionally appropriating nature, but turns this from head to feet. The design of NBS must be grounded in non-anthropcentric forms of mapping.

However, when we concentrate on the final product, we encounter a limitation: maps tend to be static. This holds true even for dynamic forms, such as the Virtual Nature tool, where the underlying database remains unchanged. Counter-mapping practices have demonstrated in various contexts that one effective solution is to dynamise maps through storytelling. We will explore this topic further in the next chapter.

Chapter 4: The craft of narrating Nature-based assemblages

4.0. Chapter summary

Storytelling and narrative analysis are well-established methods in ecolinguistics and transformative social science research. COEVOLVERS employs various forms and methods across LLs, partly connecting with mapping approaches used in advanced versions of the NatureNex app. Assemblage theory suggests that narratives should be approached in terms of their materiality, viewing them as components of Nature-based assemblages. This chapter explores these themes through a multi-species perspective and emphasizes the methodological point that narratives are an appropriate way to report research on NBS within a transdisciplinary framework. This framework acknowledges the voices of both experts and non-experts while making the positionality and subjectivity of the researcher explicit. We differentiate between stories and narratives. Specifically, storytelling serves as a means to access the non-human Umwelts by expressing embodied relationality within multi-species stakeholder assemblages. Narratives situate an NBS within its local context, making them crucial for coordinating diverse views and concerns in the emerging and coevolving NBA.

4.1. Introduction

This chapter explores the role of narratives and stories in the coevolutionary approach to NBAs. Narratives are powerful means to understand and analyze the dialectics of NBS and NBA as outlined in Chapter 1. As we previously argued in D.2.2, narratives are a crucial element of the coevolutionary methodology in two different ways.

- First, narratives are an object of research, and
- second, they serve as a method of research.

Both aspects are grounded in the general theory of narratives as cognitive media (Johnson et al., 2023). “Narratives as objects” recognizes that humans rely on stories to navigate a complex and uncertain environment, and thereby make their Umwelt in the medium of language (Tønnessen, 2015). They are a foundational way of enacting human perceptions of the world and thus play an essential role in cultural niche construction (Rouse, 2023). Therefore, recording and analysing narratives is indispensable for understanding how humans interact with the world. Simultaneously, researchers examining intricate phenomena, such as human societies and their

environments, must use narrative forms to synthesize and generalize their findings. In other words, there is a complementarity between narratives as research objects and the methodology employed in research. In the case of scientific entrepreneurs whom we consider in the next chapter, narratives are the medium in which their engagement with projects can be reported, since they cover aspects such as visions, labour, failure and success. At the same time, the various kinds of entrepreneurial actors in the projects tell their own stories which become an object of research.

Narratives play a crucial role in storing, communicating, and implementing actionable knowledge. To illustrate this, we can compare a narrative to an instruction manual. While a manual outlines the steps needed to assemble a machine, it often leaves out essential aspects related to practical skills and the emotional dynamics involved in the process. For instance, individuals need to know how to use a screwdriver and must exercise patience throughout the task. A narrative that recounts the experience of assembling the machine can effectively convey this knowledge, making the manual's instructions more actionable. This observation is especially relevant when addressing complex issues, such as Nature-Based Solutions in practice.

An important consequence is that researchers adopt a generalised ethnographic (or more appropriately, ecographic) approach to documenting their insights. This approach differs significantly from quantitative social research methods, such as surveys, and also from many qualitative research forms that do not result in narratives from the researchers themselves. It is important to note that even if researchers collect stories from actors in the field, this

Box 4.1: The story of research: Visiting Overseas cousins

Thanks to the University of Cagliari's Mobility Research Programme, I spent 17 days researching Green Mindfulness and Forest Bathing in Piura and Lima. This journey not only transformed my professional mission but also reshaped my perspective on nature. In the Sierra de Amotape near El Chaylo, I learned to see water as a sacred thread of life rather than just a resource. I witnessed the essential work of AIDER and SERNANP in protecting the dry forest through community collaboration and education. AIDER fosters trust with local schools, using nature walks and "forest bathing" to help children connect with the forest. Meanwhile, SERNANP collaborates with local communities to create brigades of forest guardians. In just 17 days, we saw positive outcomes: increased environmental awareness among children, a signed cooperation agreement between the University and AIDER, the plan to develop a Citizen Science App in Spanish, and plans for academic publications. Beyond these measurable achievements, I cherish the shared humanity, warm welcomes, and laughter that defined my experience."

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does not necessarily mean they record these stories alongside their own experiences in the field (box 4.1). The ideal method is for researchers to maintain individual diaries during their research, which can later be used to construct a narrative that merges the two perspectives.

4.2. Narratives as material constituents of NBA

4.2.1. The status of narratives as objects

As discussed in D.2.2 (pp. 102ff), narratives serve as a cognitive means of acquiring agential powers in conditions of radical uncertainty. They represent a cognitive approach to “actionable ignorance” (D.2.2., pp 186ff). Traditional methods of scientific reporting, data presentation, and data analysis imply a hierarchical structure of cognitive powers. These methods assert claims based on proven and widely accepted knowledge to reduce uncertainty. This reduction in uncertainty provides a foundation for planning and implementing science-based designs, such as the design of a NBS (Bulken et al., 2015). Narrative approaches explicitly aim at breaking up such hierarchical cognitive structures, in the spirit of Deleuze and Guattari’s nomadic forms of knowledge (Deleuze and Guattari, 2009). Stories are inherently pluralistic with multiple authors, versions and alternatives, and they are open-ended, as articulated in Indigenous methodologies of research, for example, in the approach of “yarning” where a flow of interwoven stories in a community discourse defines the relevant data base (Drawson et al., 2017).

This general approach is today well-recognised in sustainability sciences, ecological economics and other disciplines which deal with the “wicked” issues of our times and diagnose that the conventional approach of combining science with an expert-guided policy process has failed to produce workable solutions and has even resulted in a populist backlash against science (Veland et al., 2018). There is a wealth of repositories, handbooks or case studies of narrative methods in these topical domains which can be exploited by researchers for their individual research designs (Joosse et al., 2024). This strong trend reflects the turn towards post-normal and transdisciplinary sciences (Strand 2017).

In this development, it is important to recognise that narratives extend beyond traditional text as a medium. Clearly, a movie is a narrative based on a script; however, the script only captures the basic structure of the film's narrative. This structure includes key elements like emotions, which are often enhanced by music, as well as the art of camera work, editing, and other cinematic techniques. A movie is not merely a recording of real-world events; it can function even without language. This is particularly true for animal-themed films, which can convey their narratives without spoken words (like the recently released film “Flow”, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flow_\(2024_film\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flow_(2024_film))) but may still incorporate music, even though music does not play a significant role in the animals' lives.

Non-textual narratives hold great importance in the context of NBAs. One example is narrative maps, which illustrate the flow of events in both space and time (Caquard and Cartwright, 2014) (see previous chapter). In these maps, the creator selects specific locations to convey additional meanings, such as highlighting dangerous areas for humans or animals or marking ecologically stressed regions and their changes over time. Methods like digital storytelling can also operate without text, yet they still represent forms of narratives (Pesce et al., 2024).

There are clear reasons why narratives serve as an effective medium for both implementing and researching NBA. NBA are dynamic assemblages that change throughout their existence, such as a growing forest along with its ecological connections and the various events that affect it, like shifting weather patterns. When humans intervene in the life of an NBA, it leads to a complex intertwining of human

Box 4.2: Narrating place at Turku

We use narratives as materials, focusing on the nature of Turku, which includes place-based narratives, and explore questions regarding people's relationships with places and multispecies interactions. The goal is to encourage people to engage with these narratives. The materials should be easily downloadable and available for use during events. They can include various attachment options, such as text, voice recordings, and videos. The NatureNex app has previously been utilized as a tool for species observations, but the introduction of narratives is a new approach. In the parallel project MUST focus group interviews, we included questions about encounters with other species and moments when individuals felt connected to multispecies or animal experiences. This material is also used in our LL. Narratives will be incorporated into the LL. For example, in MUST, there was a case where a participant described feeling sadness while in nature, but the appearance of a dragonfly alleviated that sadness.

Kia Andell, Pansio-Perno LL

actions and non-human responses, which unfold over time. Thus, we can view an NBA not as a static entity, like a forest captured at a certain moment, but as a narrative in its own right. This perspective is further enhanced when we consider the place-shaping aspects of crafting NBAs (see D.2.1, 55f), as they are deeply embedded within a network of stories that contribute to and sustain the unique identity of a place (Raymond et al., 2023).

The concept of placeshaping highlights the vital importance of narratives in forming and solidifying communities. Shared narratives are essential for how individuals identify with specific places and communities. Consequently, crafting NBAs often relies on integrating these narratives to motivate people to engage with them, such as by participating in eco-stewardship. In these contexts, as previously demonstrated in D2.2, narrative forms should be viewed as specific art-based methods in crafting NBA. It is important to distinguish this from the general use of narratives as a research methodology. As an art-based method, narratives are intentionally generated and crafted—often with the assistance of professional artists—to achieve transformational goals (Pearson et al., 2018; Pesce et al., 2024) (on a COEVOLVERS example, see previous chapter, box 3.15). This approach differs from viewing narratives as a specific type of empirical data. While there are numerous ways to transform these empirical narratives through art-based methods, this practice is a recognised form of interaction in the therapeutic use of narratives. For instance, it is often applied in diagnosing and healing the experiences of vulnerable groups (Harris, 2022). This aspect is of relevance for the main theme of this chapter, namely, activating narratives and storytelling for including non-humans in NBA practices.

The art-based method's emphasis on "treating narratives as objects" should be understood literally. Assemblage theory regards narratives as objects that hold the same ontological significance as other entities, acknowledging their materiality. As a result, researchers take into account the physical form of these narratives, their locations, and the contexts in which they are presented (on Beskydy, see box 3.15). This materiality becomes particularly important with the many innovations brought about by digital technologies, which introduce new storytelling methods and dissemination techniques. From the perspective of assemblage theory, these material

changes are not merely superficial alterations of the narrative's content; they often significantly impact the narrative's causal powers in crafting NBAs.

4.2.2 Seeding multi-species stakeholder assemblages MSA by narrating NBAs

Recognising narratives beyond traditional texts is essential for including non-human species. The distinction between seeing narratives as objects and as methods applies with a peculiar twist. Researchers on animal behaviour often convey their field observations through narratives, which can lead to various implications. For instance, they might project intentions onto the animals they observe (such as interpreting an apparently aggressive act as defence of a territory) or focus on certain aspects of the observed actions while neglecting others. Another significant question is whether other species possess narratives of their own, albeit in non-linguistic forms. One notable aspect is narrative memory, which involves remembering a sequence of events from the past (for example, elephants apparently have this kind of memory and can even communicate it (Ross, 2022)). In sum, there are various forms of non-human narratives and related analysis:

- Humans create and share stories about non-human entities, which encompass a variety of formats. These range from stories about everyday encounters and observations to Indigenous myths (Kimmerer, 2020) and art forms like nature writing (Tüür, 2009).
- Humans can interpret the actions and behaviours of non-human entities as narrative structures, a concept we refer to as the "ecographic method" in D.2.2 (pp. 98ff). This involves two key aspects: first, observations are analyzed in terms of essential narrative elements, such as intentions and plots. For example, courting a sexual partner can be likened to a love story. Second, these narratives can also be transformed using human artistic methods, such as creating an ethologically informed animated video clip. However, the ecographic method faces challenges similar to those encountered in ethnography within the human realm, particularly the risk of misunderstanding

by projecting human meanings onto non-humans (such as interpreting territoriality as property, Serres, 2012).

- Humans can explore the concept of a radically non-human narrative standpoint, which involves viewing animal communication as a distinct form of language that is fundamentally different from human language (Bar-On, 2018; Pepperberg, 2017). Unlike previous approaches, researchers in this area aim to avoid applying analytical categories derived from human language or narratives to non-human communication. This perspective is still emerging and is primarily being developed through art-based methods (Despret, 2021).

Following up on Chapter 2, including other species in narratives related to MSAs is quite straightforward. The premise is that humans in MSAs maintain embodied relationships with non-human entities, which allows for non-anthropocentric viewpoints concerning other species. Additionally, certain narratives can encourage the development of MSAs in NBAs by helping humans connect with the imagined experiences of other beings. An example of this is non-human letter writing as an art-based method (see D.2.2, p. 120). These narratives can encompass all forms of distributed agency that influence actions and events, as exemplified in Indigenous narratives about land and people (Country et al., 2016; Povinelli, 2016). When considering MSAs, we can

Box 4.3: Non-human letter writing at Beskydy

Nature letters are written from the perspective of non-humans. For instance, they reflect the viewpoints of important non-human entities in our region, such as the dominant tree species, the spruce. The conditions for spruces are deteriorating, and they may be replaced by other tree species in the future. One old spruce even wrote a letter to people, expressing that its time is coming to an end and offering advice on how to maintain the vitality of the forest. Another letter, 'Letter from the Soil,' highlights the importance of soil for all life in nature. There are also letters written by, oak tree, bark beetle, bee, butterfly, capercaillie and water among many other non-human elements. These letters are written in an easy-to-read style, suitable for a wide audience, including children, for educational purposes. The personalized stories are directed toward humans. For example, a bear might say, 'Hello, my name is Bear, and I am speaking to you, people.' Audio-visual versions of the letters will be produced by professional actors or voice-over artists and linked to our Virtual nature tool and Virtual Commons platform. There has been a very positive response from stakeholders who have seen some of these Nature letters. The museum has requested our contribution for an exhibition. The exhibition will also have an online component in the Virtual Commons, while the results will be physically displayed in the museum in Velké Karlovice. This has proven to be a powerful tool for improving understanding current environmental challenges.

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integrate non-human species; for example, we can collect stories about shepherds

and their flocks. Human members of MSAs, with their embodied relationality, can convey non-human narratives by switching perspectives—an essential aspect of complex storytelling. Non-expert knowledge holders can have distinct capabilities in empathising with the emotional states of non-humans (Ackerman, 2023). While this may involve some degree of unwarranted anthropomorphism, we have previously argued (D.2.2) that narratives can be structured around certain universal themes of life, as suggested by the capability approach to multi-species justice. For example, threats like wildfires affect both humans and non-humans alike, triggering similar emotions, reactions, and vulnerabilities.

When examining non-linguistic narratives, it is important to consider interactions that possess a narrative structure. One common category of such interactions is the rituals associated with MSAs. A standard case to explore is the human-dog MSA, where we can view dog walks or dog play as narratives. These narratives can be shared by both researchers and dog owners involved in MSAs. Researchers may engage in participant observation, while dog owners can recount their experiences, sharing stories about various events that occur during their walks. Additionally, dog walks can be conceptualised as multi-species narratives. In this context, the dog's olfactory storytelling plays a significant role, as the dog marks its movements and interprets the olfactory messages left by other dogs. MSA narratives can take textual form, but other art-based methods are often more effective, serving as valuable complements to written narratives. This includes established techniques such as photovoice, as well as less conventional forms derived from the arts (Carlyle, 2019).

The merging of narratives, rituals, and more-than-human ontologies defines Indigenous relationality with non-humans and is often expressed through myths (Alexander, 2013). A key aspect of this process is the repeated telling of stories, which reinforces embodied relationships with the world. Building on the insights about ritual discussed in D.2.2, narratives emerge as an essential means to foster the development of MSAs. In the previous section on stakeholder analysis, the example of toads illustrates this well: The ritualisation of actions taken to protect toads as they cross dangerous roads occurs through the accumulation of activists' stories and the accompanying emergence of embodied, often tacit knowledge about toads.

Applying this understanding to NBA, we can suggest that narratives also play a crucial role in implementing these solutions as multi-species communities. For example, an NBS focused on urban gardening can be brought to life through various storytelling practices. This starts with recounting the founding myths about the activists who successfully launched the project, which might be shared regularly during specific rituals, such as

Thanksgiving. Additionally, this storytelling can involve accumulating place-based lore—stories about significant events and activities related to the garden. A classic example of this is the narratives surrounding composting, especially within the context of permaculture (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017). This

Box 4.4: Narrating multi-sensory experiences at Murray Park

At a Murray Park workshop, community members often referenced smells, such as fox musk, chanterelles, or wild garlic, alongside the sounds of birdsong, running water, and the rustle of leaves, and the textures of mossy trees and muddy paths. These sensory experiences influence not only how people navigate the park but also how they care for and relate to it, forming an intimate, embodied connection that shapes decisions about access, stewardship, and preservation. We used a mapping exercise to draw on these lived and felt aspects, through annotated maps, stickers, soundscapes, and shared stories, the community co-creates a dynamic and seasonal portrait of the park that reflects both human and non-human experiences. This form of non-human counter-mapping by story-telling goes beyond representing space; it captures the atmospheric and affective affordances that guide behaviour and foster a sense of belonging.

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example also shows that narratives can relate to complex MSAs that transcend the simple differentiation between various types of agents effectively modelled along the model of human agents, which privileges non-human entities of similar size and shapes, such as other mammals. In gardening, an MSA can emerge in the relationality between human and soil, the latter a hypercomplex assemblage of its own. Whereas the disembodied relationship between humans and soil is defined via formal knowledge, such as in agronomy, narratives stimulate and sustain embodied care for the soil. A case in point is the narratives emerging in ongoing interactions between adults and children in gardening (Taylor and Pacini-Ketchabaw, 2015).

In sum, COEVOLVERS emphasizes the role of narratives in seeding and nurturing MSAs which goes beyond conventional awareness approaches in art-based methods. Often, narratives only play a role in launching NBS, whereas in the ongoing NBA, narratives are a constitutive element in sustaining its functioning.

4.3. Functions of narratives in crafting NBAs

4.3.1. Causal mechanisms in NBAs and narratives as mirrors and drivers

The sciences differ in how they utilise narratives as a method. While the natural sciences typically do not view narratives as an appropriate medium, there are significant areas where they are important. For example, geology relates to Earth's history, and biology pertains to phylogeny. This indicates that narratives often become prominent when analysing complex phenomena that unfold in space and time. Narratives usually describe the causal mechanisms driving these processes. This is especially true for the historical sciences, which combine causal analysis with the examination of meanings (Schmid, 2011). Narratives are essential in dealing with the current societal challenges of climate change. For example, scenarios that depict alternative pathways that connect current policies with future effects on global warming are narratives (such as scenarios like “Garden city” in (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005)). These narratives contain strong elements of scientific theorising about causal mechanisms that, for example, lead from methane emissions to certain

climate changes. However, such mechanisms are by far lacking sufficient explanatory and predictive powers to fully justify specific policies.

Given this context, we can conclude that narratives are also the primary method for analyzing and designing NBA in the sciences and engineering. As discussed in previous deliverables, NBA involve activities of niche construction that occur in space and time, exhibiting uncertainty and complexity. This applies even to seemingly simple cases, such as creating a healing garden in a hospital. Uncertainty and complexity are significant factors in gardening activities, which deal with incomplete and imperfect knowledge regarding the local environment and future changes due to climate change (Schwarz, 2022). Additionally, the interactions within the human domain, such as between the

gardeners and hospital management, are also uncertain and complex. For these reasons, we cannot conceptualise the establishment of a healing garden as merely implementing a theoretical design, similar to constructing an engine that operates according to the laws of physics.

Box 4.5: Narratives, scenarios, and shifting perceptions of NBS environment at Beskydy

Our team previously worked on a project in the Beskydy region as part of the the cross-border cooperation initiative, INTERREG. Initiated in 2018, the project involved collaboration with four Czech and Slovak partners and aimed to develop a climate adaptation plan for the forests in Beskydy. Among others we conducted interviews with stakeholders. These were to gather perceptions of the risks linked to climate change in the region. We also explored potential solutions. Experts from our partner organizations focused on modelling climate scenarios and created site specific models for Beskydy, predicting future changes in the forests. We considered positive, most likely and negative scenarios, assessing their potential impacts on the region. We also held participatory workshops with local stakeholders to discuss measures for adapting to and mitigating climate change. NBS were identified as the most preferable option by the stakeholders. We are currently considering how to further develop and implement the adaptation plan, while disseminating best practices and raising awareness of the associated risks. As Tatiana Kluvanková from the team mentioned, she has had connections to the region for 20 years, stemming from her visits there. The idea for the INTERREG and ongoing projects emerged from these visits, and from the discussion with colleagues from the Czech Academy of Sciences and Slovak research institutions. A key factor in the success of the Coevolvers was that we came to the first meeting with a completed climate adaptation plan. This plan was finalised and printed during the COVID-19 pandemic, which hindered dissemination and communication efforts. Initially, the adaptation plan included climate change scenarios for the region that did not seem particularly dramatic at the time. However, by late 2022, these scenarios had become increasingly relevant and realistic. The effects of climate change were occurring much faster than projected. One example of this is the occurrence of less snow in winter. This has implications for both tourism, which is mostly oriented towards winter sports, and the quantity and quality of water on which local ecosystems and people depend. This situation enabled us to expand on the original project idea. Throughout the INTERREG project we had gained the trust of local communities as they recognised the relevance of climate change and its impact on the scenarios we presented. We were able to deliver an adaptation plan and scenarios that have now become a reality.

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Further exploring the example of the healing garden, narratives have the following functions (for a general overview, see (Johnson et al., 2023)).

- The ideas surrounding the causal mechanisms for creating a sustainable healing garden are based on a narrative. This narrative incorporates both narrative and non-narrative forms of knowledge, such as understanding soil composition and its impact on plant growth, while integrating the expertise of both specialists and non-specialists. However, this is only one aspect of a larger framework. The goal is to organize various planned activities into a coherent pattern that allows for predictions about the outcomes of current actions. For example, this involves distinguishing between a bed designated for herbs and one intended for salad greens.
- The narrative serves as a framework for coordinating human actions in the development of the healing garden project. It identifies key actors essential for the project's success and illustrates how their actions affect outcomes. Essentially, the narrative simulates real-world processes.
- Additionally, the narrative facilitates the transfer and integration of knowledge among diverse stakeholders involved in the healing garden initiative. It establishes a common cognitive framework for action, presenting this information in a way that is accessible to everyone, in contrast to the exclusivity often associated with expert knowledge.
- Moreover, the narrative communicates goals and future possibilities by linking past experiences with future aspirations. This connection fosters a shared understanding of the tasks ahead, legitimises current actions, and encourages stakeholders to take responsibility.

This preliminary list mostly focuses on the cognitive functions of narratives. In this context, a narrative may serve as an instruction manual. However, this interpretation overlooks important differences. An instruction manual describes causal flows—such as the steps to take when composting—but does not create the motivation to follow those steps. Narratives differ from other types of scientific texts in that they explicitly refer to the emotions that accompany and influence actors' actions. This distinction applies to both aspects of narratives, as objects and as methods. As objects,

narratives reveal information about the emotional states of actors in various forms (Goldie, 2014). One such form is that the stories told by actors are often emotionally charged, while the narratives recorded by researchers explicitly reference emotions. As methods, narratives encompass the emotions of both actors and researchers during a particular project. For example, in the case of a healing garden, both actors and researchers develop feelings of care for the garden, which are essential for motivating the actions necessary for its creation and sustainability.

4.3.2. The diversity of narrative perspectives

More generally, narratives take an explicit value stance, which is mostly avoided in standard scientific research that aims to be “value-free.” This is especially important when it comes to vulnerabilities that are not yet manifest so that no actual harm can be measured scientifically. For example, the vulnerabilities of animals facing future climate change can be expressed in narratives of potential deprivation and displacement. Narratives project future possibilities and can prompt actions today, even in the absence of immediate urgency. This aspect is crucial in understanding the importance of literary works for various forms of civic activism (Harris, 2022). A more specific aspect is that narratives often allow for projecting continuity in transformation, which is particularly important in the NBA context (Joosse et al., 2024). For example, scientific projections may signal the stark realities of how global warming may affect health in heating cities, especially for vulnerable groups like the elderly. A narrative about greening the city as a form of adaptation can suggest many interlaced aspects, such as the aesthetics of greenery, so that eventually, continuity trumps transformation in enacting the NBS, despite also achieving the desired goals.

An essential aspect of narratives is their diversity, which arises from the fact that narratives do not present a “view from nowhere” (Goldie, 2014). Instead, they reflect the perspective of the individual telling the story. This perspective is not always explicit, underscoring the importance of narrative analysis. For example, it matters whether a narrative about a healing garden emphasizes economic factors, such as reducing costs for other treatments, or focuses on biodiversity and its positive effects on well-

being through multispecies cohabitation. Researchers must consider this diversity of narratives when examining their subjects. Understanding the various narratives collected from different stakeholders is crucial for grasping their actions and interactions. Consequently, narrative analysis plays a vital role in uncovering the motivations and interests of various actors.

The same applies to narratives as a method. The earlier example of scenario analysis illustrates how researchers rely on alternative narratives to draw global and general conclusions. Narratives as a method can vary significantly because researchers come from different disciplinary backgrounds (see box 4.6). For instance, the narratives of an economist will differ from those of an anthropologist. Given the stark theoretical and

Box 4.6: Stakeholder diversity and multi-disciplinarity of research team

To effectively address the complexity and plurality of perspectives inherent in socio-environmental challenges, it is essential that research teams reflect a diversity similar to the multiple stakeholders involved in complex societal challenges, both in disciplinary expertise and in personal backgrounds. Within the context of the COEVOLVERS Living Lab in Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, our interdisciplinary team, comprising social, environmental, developmental, and health psychologists, demonstrated the value of this approach. The diversity of our research team enabled us to engage meaningfully with a wide array of stakeholders, including educators, conservationists, civic association members, and vulnerable groups. Each researcher brought distinct theoretical frameworks and methodological tools to bear on the co-creation process, enriching the interpretation of stakeholder input and ensuring that the participatory methods resonated across various cognitive, emotional, and cultural dimensions. This interdisciplinary lens facilitated the emergence of multi-layered narratives grounded in participants' lived experiences, promoting mutual understanding and highlighting common values despite initial differences in perspectives and knowledge bases. The convergence of psychological and ecological expertise allowed for a nuanced facilitation of dialogues that not only fostered emotional connection and empathy among participants but also revealed pathways for concrete and inclusive nature-based assemblages. As such, diversity within the research team was not only instrumental in mirroring the heterogeneity of the stakeholder landscape but also foundational to catalyzing the collective intelligence necessary for sustainable socio-ecological transformation.

Ferdinando Fornara, Cagliari LL

methodological differences between those disciplines, reaching a consensus about designing an NBS may be close to impossible, especially since different stakeholders may mobilise different disciplines in arguing their particular interests (Han and Luo, 2024). However, in composing a project narrative, researchers may be able to bridge these differences precisely because the narrative does not use disciplinary jargon. Taken together, these arguments imply the important conclusion for research design that research teams need to be diverse in terms of personal backgrounds and disciplinary expertise. This diversity enables members to share different perspectives

and create multi-faceted narratives from their individual experiences. Such perspective-taking is crucial for understanding the stories of various stakeholders involved in NBAs. For instance, an economist in the research team may find it easier to relate to the narratives of urban planners, while a biologist may connect more with those of MSAs. Therefore, we differentiate between individual diaries and the collective narratives developed during group activities. These group activities can be purposefully designed using a transdisciplinary approach, allowing for the integration of both expert and non-expert knowledge holders.

4.3.3. Narratives, stories, genres

The term "narrative" is used differently across various scientific disciplines. Researchers in the natural sciences tend to use the term in a generic sense without much elaboration, which also applies to economics (Shiller, 2019). In contrast, the humanities provide a more nuanced approach, often distinguishing between narratives and stories (Herman, 2010). This distinction has also been adopted in ecolinguistics (Stibbe, 2021). There are various interpretations of this distinction, all of which are relevant in the current context. Most importantly, "narratives" can refer to larger thematic structures, while "stories" generally pertain to specific events. For example, we can speak of a climate change narrative, which encompasses a broad discussion of the issue, and a story about local birds adapting to climate change, which focuses on individual experiences. This meaning of narrative is close to discourse analysis (Gee, 2011).

Additionally, a narrative can serve as an abstract template for stories. For instance, a narrative might follow the structure of a "whodunit," with individual stories acting as examples of this structure. This could apply to the climate change example if we consider a textual framework that documents certain events and developments, where climate change only emerges as the key causal factor in the end. When exploring the use of narratives in literary studies, it is important to distinguish between various fundamental types of narratives, often referred to as genres. Genres differ in many ways, including how they structure the flow of events and the types of plots they

present. For instance, a love story has a very different structure compared to a detective story. If we apply this approach to LL practices, we can identify different genres of NBA narratives. These genres relate to archetypal situations and processes involved in implementing an NBS. For example, one common challenge in NBS is mobilising actors to engage, often due to factors such as a lack of time or understanding. Researchers who recognise this issue across LLs may define a genre called "mobilisation stories" (see box 4.7). These narratives typically share a common initial setting involving both stakeholders and uninterested parties, with a flow of events shaped by structural conditions that are similar across LLs, leading to specific outcomes. Other genres may include narratives that focus on multi-species community building. Identifying these narrative genres is an important aspect of systematising knowledge about NBA.

In the context of NBA, all these distinctions matter. For example, urban planners may adopt an established NBS narrative following templates such as European Commission documents.

Researchers can performatively adopt these narratives, which implies that their research may reveal a distinct pattern of foci and oblivions, which typically happens when writing proposals responding to calls: "Proposal" is a distinct genre of NBA narrative. They can also approach the established narrative critically, such as pinpointing the oblivions. This can result in counter-narratives,

Box 4.7: :Aligning diverse narratives to grow NBAs

At Turku, we aim to be relevant to society, particularly through various projects initiated by the city and researchers. However, there is a growing sense of participation fatigue within the community. We have endeavoured to develop a concrete plan that focuses on enhancing access to blue spaces and initiating a pilot project aimed at ecosocial recovery. Unfortunately, we have exceeded our budget while attempting to improve access to the sea. The beach we are targeting is challenging to reach and rather small, with difficult routes leading to it. Currently, the grill area is in disrepair; however, we propose starting small by repairing the grill and renovating the pier, as well as adding sand to the beach. From an ecological perspective, Timo Vuorisalo, an ecologist, sees potential in this area from a compensation standpoint. We plan to address the site by removing alien species to make room for endemic ones, and we will approach the planning from a multispecies perspective. Discussions with city officials and COEVOLVERS have been positive; they do not oppose our plans. However, we need to engage with local residents. While there are no objections, we wonder if anyone is interested and if we can effectively reach out to the community. Residents have expressed a desire to develop the beach, acknowledging that, although it is remote, it remains unmanaged and underutilised.

Kia Andell, Turku LL

corresponding to countermapping as a practice (Bulken et al., 2015) and is almost a

methodological principle in Indigenous research (Drawson et al., 2017). For example, greening the city may create disadvantages for certain vulnerable groups, and researchers may collect their stories, such as accounts of displacement by green gentrification, and finally condense these stories in a counter-narrative that challenges the urban planners. This approach has been widely adopted in critical social research, such as feminist studies.

A key motivation for the narrative turn in research is that empirical work focused on "truth" or "evidence" often fails to gather essential information from vulnerable populations. For instance, studying the experiences of rape in traditional patriarchal societies presents the challenge that women may struggle to articulate their experiences. Similarly, certain vulnerable groups, such as young children, may find it difficult to express themselves using standard language. In contrast, storytelling offers a way to express emotions indirectly. It enables interviewees to process their feelings through appropriate means, such as conveying facts with a sense of humor. Narratives provide various indirect methods for expressing social facts and conditions, emphasizing the distinction between facts and fiction. In D.2.2 (p. 133), we noted that using vignettes is an important alternative to standard questionnaires for eliciting emotional responses and more subtle forms of knowledge from interviewees.

The ongoing methodological discussion surrounding storytelling has consistently emphasised the importance of whose stories are included and recorded, as well as who is telling these stories (Joosse et al., 2024). For instance, caretakers may serve as vicarious storytellers for vulnerable individuals, but this does not ensure the authenticity of those stories. Some storytellers may choose to remain silent, while others may be silenced entirely. This issue is particularly significant when it comes to the inclusion of non-human entities, as they are often excluded from the circles of possible story-tellers. Even when we actively seek to include non-humans, we still face challenges in ensuring that some are not overlooked. Typically, stories about iconic species receive more attention and interest, while narratives about organisms that are more distantly related or smaller in scale are rarely told, if at all. We have previously suggested that the MSA approach can address these challenges, as illustrated by the case of soil.

4.4. Conclusion

The power of stories and narratives in "world-making" is widely acknowledged across various disciplines and thematic fields. However, this phenomenon is often viewed as a social issue and, in economics, can even be seen as dysfunctional, as it may impede rational assessments of realities necessary for making appropriate decisions (think of stories driving financial manias). In the field of sustainability sciences and related areas, this perception has shifted dramatically, especially against the backdrop of increasing anti-scientism and populism.

This shift can be understood in two different ways. The first is the instrumental perspective, which somewhat cynically views human weaknesses and considers narratives as useful tools to address these weaknesses. The second perspective, which we adopt here, sees stories and narratives as the most effective means to navigate uncertainty and complex realities that lie beyond the rationalist ideal of social engineering. From the strategic perspective adopted by COEVOLVERS, stories and narratives are not just "tools" as in the art-based methods approach, but media in which Nature-based assemblages are crafted and reflected. Like in the case of maps, they are critical for sustaining an endogenous MSA structure. Stories and narratives serve as essential media for fostering relationality between humans and non-humans because they engage emotions and activate human imagination.

One area where the importance of narratives is recognised, even in economics (albeit outside the mainstream), is entrepreneurship. This will be the topic of the next chapter.

Chapter 5: Nature-based entrepreneurship as embodied medium of actionable knowledge

5.0. Chapter summary

This chapter further explores reflections on actionable knowledge from deliverable D.2.2 and introduces a general concept of Nature-based entrepreneurship as the medium through which implicit, embodied, tacit, and contextual knowledge is manifest in practices of LLs. We distinguish between four generic forms of Nature-based entrepreneurship: political and institutional, social, market, and scientific. According to standard definitions, entrepreneurship is defined as an activity that addresses uncertainty, mobilizes resources, and coordinates collective action. The term "nature-based" refers to entrepreneurial activities that are directly related to the NBA, inspired by the NBS idea. Entrepreneurship is a specific form of leadership that encompasses various boundary-spanning activities, local mobilisation, and engagement in community initiatives. Our primary concern is how entrepreneurship can help sustain an NBA beyond the duration of a project-sponsored NBS. In addition to establishing supportive stakeholder relationships, as discussed in Chapter 2, this requires the mobilisation of both financial and human resources. We also examine the role of serial scientific entrepreneurship, which integrates an NBA into various project chains and networks.

5.1. Introduction

In D.2.2. (Chapter 5), we discussed why the concept of actionable knowledge is problematic, if not paradoxical. This issue arises from the linear perspective that suggests a specific stock of knowledge can be made actionable (Argyris, 2005). This paradox becomes evident when considering the goal of creating documents that record this actionable knowledge. When researchers identify "key exploitable results" (KERs) in standard reporting procedures, they often fail to engage in a co-creative process where these results organically emerge from the practices of Living Labs that engage expert and non-expert knowledge holders equally. Similar to Hegel's owl of Minerva, KERs can only be recognized retrospectively, by diagnosing new practices and habits that become established within certain LLs and spread across their borders through various channels, primarily imitation. Even when researchers identify a KER mid-project, they cannot reliably determine how far the success of any specific practice depends on the unique and particular conditions of that project. For example, the presence of external funding and researchers themselves are crucial factors. There are also many other specific influences, such as the initial conditions of the project.

The question remains: can anyone reproduce the practice without these unique circumstances?

In other words, the established terminology of “results” aims at isolating a key component of what is a practice on the ground and thereby re-establishes the normative borderline between expert and non-expert knowledge (Adelle et al., 2020). In addition, the isolation falsely suggests that practices can be separated from other practices that tie up with them and constitute the arenas and scaffolds of the specific practice that is focused on (Rouse, 2023).

There is even a meta-paradox to consider: How can researchers confidently assert that their findings and the practices resulting from their interventions will be applicable in different contexts? To what extent is their *methodological* knowledge actionable? This is not merely a philosophical question; it underpins the methodological shift in economics towards testing through randomised experiments and evidence-based research (Banerjee, 2020; Duflo, 2017). However, this model relies on very specific conditions, such as a clear empirical distinction between parameters and controls or the ability to quantify results. On a deeper level, randomised experiments (as is the case with economic experiments in general) tend to overlook the influential role that researchers play in their interventions (Herrmann-Pillath, 2019). When researchers apply a particular method in a real-world setting, they may inadvertently alter the local partners' perception of social reality in unpredictable ways, often influenced by local peculiarities. For instance, using a role board game outside its original context of natural resource commons may not yield the intended results because the participants change their own definition of the situation. The RBG as a research method also changes social reality, which is also salient in the multi-valued methodological status of such games, which can be used as empirical experiments or as tools of ecosocial transformation.

As discussed in the previous chapter, the best way to document the generation of knowledge deemed “actionable” is through co-created narratives rather than the conventional format of scientific reports and journal articles (Cohen et al., 2024). A key difference between these reports and a narrative is that narratives also highlight the history of failures and errors, which are crucial for advancing the story. Additionally,

narratives emphasize the specific context of the research, including factors that might be overlooked in standard scientific accounts. In this regard, the appropriate scientific method for recording actionable knowledge aligns with the history of sciences, particularly as it is theorized in Science and Technology Studies (STS) (Barad, 2007). Practically, this means that documenting actionable knowledge can be seen as a form of "auto-history" and "auto-ethnography," reflecting the research project within the context of a LL, which can be conducted both individually and collectively.

The fundamental problem in dealing with actionable knowledge is that action is enabled by many forms of knowledge which cannot be cast into a propositional form, as the trouble with instruction manuals demonstrates to every practitioner. Action is critically determined by embodied, implicit and tacit forms of "knowing how" in contrast to "knowing that".

Such forms of knowledge have the additional characteristic of being local, since they are embodied in the lived practices on the ground. The local nature of knowledge is the reason why there can be many obstacles to upscaling and diffusion of knowledge beyond the local. In D.2.2, we referred to the rich literature on the commons, where, despite Ostrom's attempt at defining general criteria of successful commons, the specification of these criteria in concrete settings still remains elusive.

In this chapter, we will examine the archetypical form of agency that drives coevolutionary dynamics among diverse actors: Entrepreneurship. We argue that actionable knowledge is a specific form of embodied knowledge that enables creative

Box 5.1: Autoethnographic work at the healing garden

In our LL work, we (core group) continuously reflect on our experiences and on our actions. We do it individually by keeping a researcher's diary and also collectively during our core group meetings held in every two weeks. Reflection is an essential part of our work as we carry out various interventions with different stakeholders / LL participants where different subjectivities meet, including our ones. Reflection helps us to pay attention to different needs and relations.

While working with the medical staff of the hospital, we especially need to take into account that we (can) interfere into an organization with already existing relations, formal and informal hierarchies and power-relations. We need to ask ourselves, how do we effect those relations? What kind of impact can we have on others? What can we do to be as gentle as possible in cooperating with the hospital staff in taking into account their different needs but also managing a collaborative process to design a healing garden?

There are no concrete answers for these questions, but it is important to raise them to better understand the impact of the core group's presence in the hospital. Even though the project lasts only a few years, not taking into account such perspectives could jeopardize the LL's work, the participants experience and above all the healing garden.

Orsolya Lazányi, Healing garden LL

action under radical uncertainty. We treat entrepreneurship as a general form of agency beyond the business context, and we look for expressions in the context of LLs. This broad interpretation of entrepreneurship is today widely adopted in the sustainability sciences (Haldar, 2019), but less so in the context of NBS (Gültekin, 2024; Kooijman et al., 2021; Hiedanpää et al., 2011). We will explore various manifestations of entrepreneurship in the context of COEVOLVERS. We refer to these as “Nature-based entrepreneurship”, where “nature-based”, as in previous arguments, has the twofold meaning of relating to a multi-species context in NBAs and approaching this relationality as embodied and place-based.

5.2. The role of leaders and boundary spanners

One of the essential ingredients for successful sustainability practices is leadership, a fact that is well-recognized in Indigenous approaches to sustainability (Trosper, 2022).

Since these practices involve communities and their coordinated actions, effective leadership is crucial for transforming insights and inspiration into real-world practices of eco-social transformation, including scientific research (Case et al., 2015; Southern et al., 2023).

As a COEVOLVERS example, establishing a healing garden at a hospital might rely on established scientific knowledge, on first sight. However, this does not

Box 5.2: Leadership at the Healing Garden

In the Healing Garden LL three organisational partners collaborate, including an NGO run by horticulture practitioners, a small private research company specialised in environmental social sciences and a psychiatric hospital. Beyond the diversity of the organisational partners themselves, the core group of the Healing Garden LL demonstrates a variety of expertise (from biology and landscape architecture to ecological economics and visual arts). By implication, there is no leader in the conventional sense but a collaborative practice in which different actors take the responsibility to lead different actions that always engage some of the hospital staff, too. Often times, the initiative comes from members of the hospital staff and the core group always deliberates on how to best proceed in a way which builds on the abilities and motivation of diverse actors. Leadership is, in a sense, a moving target, anyone can take it up and move it forward. An open-minded atmosphere is deliberately created and being nurtured that ideas are welcome, initiatives are taken seriously, considered and acted upon together.

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guarantee that the individuals involved will take action or that the project will be

successful. Multiple forms of leadership must come into play to turn the healing garden into a lived reality. This includes the hospital leadership fully endorsing the project, having role models among medical practitioners who believe that this initiative should be an integral part of daily therapeutic work, and engaging patients who resonate with the project and motivate others to participate in collaborative efforts within the garden. In this context, we can refer to this concept as distributed leadership (Horlings et al., 2018). In the NBA context, a “strongman” seems out of place, since the need for co-creation is widely seen as indispensable. Instead, leadership is emergent in assemblages of co-leaders in different domains that are bridged by the NBA.

In the context of NBS design, leadership is often overlooked, as these initiatives are primarily designed and implemented by public authorities, such as municipalities. While it is acknowledged that this does not imply a top-down approach, it necessitates participatory project management; however, even when co-creation is emphasized, it does not automatically mean that leadership is shared beyond institutional leaders. Shared leadership is more common in projects involving Indigenous communities, where there is explicit legal recognition of dual leadership between governmental authorities and the Indigenous community. In other contexts, leadership may arise spontaneously within citizen initiatives responding to NBS projects. However, due to the legal framework surrounding participatory project management, this engagement is often limited to the project design and early implementation stages and does not typically extend to the maintenance and ongoing management of NBS (Fisher et al., 2021).

Crafting NBA requires effective leadership beyond the initial implementation phase (Li et al., 2021). When we think of crafting NBA as a form of infrastructural landscaping, it becomes clear that ongoing support is essential, particularly in relation to biodiversity and the vital stewardship role played by the local community. This need is underscored by the fact that many local authorities lack both the financial resources and personnel

necessary to manage the NBA as part of a diverse ecological community. Further, NBS can meet resistance in many forms that do not relate to the concept as such, but to certain elements which are nevertheless critical. Additionally, if the NBA is to serve as a key factor in ecosocial transformation, comprehensive citizen engagement is crucial since this fosters the emergence of new habits of multi-species cohabitation. This can only be achieved if some individuals take on leadership roles within the community who are members of the community and stay there long after formal project completion.

Who are leaders in a project context? Initially, leadership roles are often held by public

representatives and researchers. However, this dynamic is most effective in the early stages of the project. As it progresses, it becomes essential for community members to take on leadership positions. During this transition, boundary spanners play a crucial role by acting as intermediaries between the community and the formal project core (Reid et al., 2016). The specific individuals who serve as boundary spanners cannot be generalised, as it heavily depends on the context. Generally, boundary spanners are individuals with diverse backgrounds across various domains relevant to the NBS initiative. For example:

1. *Retired Professionals*: These may be biologists or other experts living in the community. They can easily connect with researchers and help translate project ideas into local discourses and narratives, particularly in relation to local fauna and flora.

Box:5.3: Conflicting interests at Barcelona LL

The municipality's technicians and the politician responsible for fire management are advocating for a reduction in wildfire risk through NBS. The technicians have proposed the concept, and the local politician supports it. However, implementation faces many constraints that must be overcome by entrepreneurial acumen. Although reducing wildfire risk is generally seen as beneficial for the community, landowners may disagree, especially when it comes to shepherds who need to establish pens or fences for their flocks to stay overnight. Suitable locations for these pens are often identified, but occasionally, landowners may oppose the establishment of these pens, preventing the implementation of the nature-based solutions. In the summer, shepherds relocate to a different municipality (transhumance). During this season, the grass becomes dry, prompting them to move. In one situation, there was a technical barrier that prevented them from using their current location, as there wasn't enough space for a pen. However, in the nearby municipality, there was a shepherd available, which might allow them to shift to that area. This plan is feasible, but a new contract will be necessary, and they need to hire someone else to assist with the move.

Elena Gorriz, Barcelona LL

2. *Researchers with Local Ties:* Some researchers may have a deep personal connection to the area, whether as residents, natives, or members of non-governmental organizations and other citizen groups familiar with the community.

3. *Local Activists and Community Groups:* Individuals and organisations that have established credibility within the community, such as local birdwatchers or gardeners, may find the nature-NBS project particularly meaningful.

4. *Educators:* Teachers and educators across all levels who are committed to the societal project of ecosocial transformation can play a vital role in the initiative.

5. *Local Politicians:* Politicians may choose to support the project for various reasons, including the potential for community economic development and job creation.

6. *Representatives of religious groups:* Many religious confessions and movements recognise the sanctity of nature and may therefore align with the general objectives of the NBS.

Box 5.4: Spanning boundaries at Pansio-Perno

For example, there are entrepreneurs in Pansio who take a holistic approach to local development while also being connected to nature. One local historian, who conducts research on the area's history, writes for Turun Sanomat and engages in discussions with local politicians to bring positive attention to Pansio. He conducts interviews about the shipyard's history as well as the significance of blue spaces, and he has extensive knowledge about the caves and ponds in Pansio. While entrepreneurship in the area isn't specifically focused on NBS, there is a broader, holistic view regarding Pansio. When asked what they appreciate most about Pansio, people typically say it is nature. However, they also express concerns about littering and lack of access to land. Many are not familiar with the concept of NBS and often associate it more with conservation rather than actively developing NBS initiatives. People often talk about the animals that have visited the area and highlight the potential for outdoor routes and activities. The development perspective is holistic, with the same individuals participating in every meeting focused on Pansio. This reflects a sense of neighbourhood activism that extends beyond just nature.

Kia Andell, Turku LL

In the following, we will discuss a unique aspect of leadership: entrepreneurship. While all entrepreneurs are leaders, not all leaders are entrepreneurs. For instance, a local parish priest may serve as a community leader, but that does not necessarily mean they are engaged in efforts to drive societal and economic change.

5.3. Nature-based entrepreneurship in crafting NBA

We approach NBS as a coevolutionary technology, and this highlights an important yet often overlooked link between leadership and entrepreneurship. In the broader

field of technology, entrepreneurship is typically viewed as a key driver of innovation, but NBS is frequently not recognized as a potential area for entrepreneurial activity, even though NBS are clearly innovations, if only on the local level, in the sense of adapting existing designs to local conditions. This oversight may suggest an implicit understanding of NBS as infrastructure, where the involvement of public bodies is generally deemed essential.

However, a closer examination reveals that these assumptions vary depending on the specific type of NBS being considered. For instance, when it comes to urban greenery as a form of landscaping infrastructure, we emphasise the importance of distributed, multi-level activities that engage a diverse array of actors. In the case of restoring a watershed, municipalities may take the lead. Alternatively, for projects focused on enhancing connectivity between green spaces, it may be beneficial if citizens participate by implementing small-scale devices that address the needs of pollinators on their balconies (Ávila, 2022). Thus, effective landscaping necessitates coordinated actions from both public and private entities. This raises the question: who creates these devices and supplies them to households? Here, a local entrepreneur could seize the opportunity to establish a business that manufactures and sells these devices.

Entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in crafting NBA as NBS initiatives operate under conditions of significant ecological uncertainty while requiring the investment of resources from multiple stakeholders. Although NBS projects are often public initiatives, many private businesses are involved (Brokking et al., 2021).

Box 5.5: Entrepreneurial providers of NBS at Barcelona LL

Shepherds primarily rely on market meat, milk, and related products for their income apart from the NBS compensation scheme. Grazing for fire prevention requires effort, including training dogs to work with flocks and being cautious of vehicles. As revealed in Rovellada Ballesteros et al (2025), For a typical flock of 200 sheep, shepherds typically have 3-2 working dogs and 1-2 protection dogs. In NBS, the flock size is smaller compared to traditional shepherding, where flocks can range from 600 to 800 sheep. With a flock of 200 sheep, it is challenging to sustain a livelihood based solely on these products (Rovellada Ballesteros et al, 2025). Meat remains the main product, while cheese and other items are usually secondary. Most shepherds involved in NBS are newcomers, often needing to buy their flocks. Access to jobs in this field can be open to anyone, but it becomes more complicated without the right connections or family ties in shepherding. It is generally easier for those who come from traditional shepherding families. However, traditional shepherding usually takes place in deep rural areas, away from urban centers. Many traditional shepherds prefer this rural lifestyle and do not wish to be close to cities or towns.

Elena Gorriz and Marc Rovellada, Barcelona LL

For example, transforming a city into a “sponge city” necessitates the coordinated efforts of various construction companies. If the municipality implements a strategy to develop the city into a “BiodiverCity,” it could serve as an attraction for tourists, potentially benefiting the entire tourism sector. This shift may also foster a strong community of active stakeholders invested in the NBA. Hence, a reduced-form definition of Nature-based entrepreneurship would refer to all forms of entrepreneurial activity that contribute to the co-creation and maintenance of a NBA.

Key themes in entrepreneurship theories include radical uncertainty, the importance of social relationships, and the value of local knowledge. Entrepreneurs are leaders driven by a mission, and they work to mobilise the necessary resources to achieve this mission. Often, entrepreneurs encounter the challenge that their ideas may not align with established knowledge and lack conclusive scientific support. In fact, without a unique idea that others are reluctant to pursue due to fears of risk and potential failure, entrepreneurs may struggle to achieve profits. Unlike corporate professionals, entrepreneurs frequently view their projects as reflections of their individual lifestyles, serving as a means of personal fulfillment and self-determination.

These remarks also emphasize the difference between organisational form and entrepreneurial function. In this context, we do not consider public enterprises as a separate form of entrepreneurship since we are focusing strictly on the individual level in relation to assemblages, rather than on legal or institutional categories. A CEO of a public enterprise can define her entrepreneurial function in various ways.

We can understand entrepreneurs as exemplifying and impersonating actionable knowledge in two key ways. First, they take knowledge to practice that others might be aware of but are hesitant to turn into action due to various risks. These reasons often include general uncertainty, perceptions of insufficient support from their social networks, or a lack of confidence in their own abilities. Second, entrepreneurs generate actionable knowledge through their achievements. If they succeed, they serve as role models, encouraging others to imitate their actions, which can be a significant driver of social and economic change.

The concept of entrepreneurship has expanded beyond traditional market contexts, leading to the development of the idea of political entrepreneurship. Below, we discuss four typical forms of entrepreneurship, each tied to a specific nature-based focus:

1. *Political entrepreneurship* emphasizes community politics related to crafting NBAs and often takes the specific form of *institutional entrepreneurship*.
2. *Social entrepreneurship* merges a not-for-profit multi-species mission with a business framework.
3. *Market entrepreneurship* capitalizes on the business opportunities presented by NBA.
4. *Scientific entrepreneurship* mobilizes research funds and research networks to support a NBS project beyond the funding period, including serial project management.

The literature on NBS identifies market entrepreneurship as a crucial factor in ensuring the sustainability of NBAs. The HORIZON project, ConnectingNature, has introduced the concept of "nature-based enterprise" (Kooijman et al., 2021) which builds on earlier research related to the green economy, such as "nature-based tourism" (Tervo-Kankare, 2019). In this chapter, we expand upon these contributions by broadening the definition of entrepreneurship beyond the economic sphere. It is important to distinguish between "entrepreneurship" and "enterprise": the latter refers specifically to the organisational form of entrepreneurship within markets. In contrast, political entrepreneurship may manifest through municipal reorganisation or the creation of new units dedicated to ecosocial transformation, and hence often closely relates to institutional entrepreneurship. Scientific entrepreneurship typically takes the form of a "project", and in the case of serial entrepreneurship, a localised research program that morphs into a process of eco-social transformation, in the tradition of action research.

In the COEVOLVERS Living Labs, we explore various forms of Nature-based entrepreneurship. For instance, market entrepreneurship in Barcelona utilises sheep herding for multiple business activities that turn sheep into an economic resource, which includes meat production and sausage making. Political entrepreneurship plays a significant role in driving eco-compensation schemes in Turku Living Lab.

When considering the overall setup of crafting NBA as infrastructural landscaping, various types of entrepreneurship must be analyzed in terms of their interaction. Market entrepreneurs may

Box 5.6: Brokering sustainability at Cres

Being the manager of a local development agency working mainly within a small community (less than 3,000 inhabitants) I have the opportunity to directly initiate some initiatives as well as to create conditions that can facilitate the development of initiatives at grassroots level. The agency has 15 years of experience in participatory planning and stakeholders' engagement in different project implementation, dealing with topics like natural and cultural heritage preservation and valorisation, sustainable tourism and energy transition. Regarding the social entrepreneurship, it has been facing difficult times on the island. The reason lies in the constant development of the tourism industry in the last 40 years which is far more remunerative than any other activity and has engaging an increasing number of islanders. This results in a local community being more and more focused on making money and on individual prosperity, neglecting the public aspects and reducing social cohesion. Nevertheless, there are still people willing to engage themselves into community initiatives. The feeling is that these people are the same one who are more present in the rural area of the island and are more connected to the island's natural and cultural heritage, in other words with the island's identity.

Ugo Toić, Cres small scale pilot

struggle if there are no political entrepreneurs advocating for NBS. Therefore, we introduce the concept of entrepreneurial brokers (see box 5.6). These individuals can belong to any group, and we can best identify them as leaders who act as boundary spanners. The key distinction between these entrepreneurial brokers and traditional entrepreneurs is that the former adopt a community perspective, while the latter focus primarily on project-based outcomes. Entrepreneurial brokers are often local community leaders, sometimes focusing on specific stakeholder groups, such as a leader of a local business association. However, if a research project extends beyond one funding stage, researchers can also adopt this role (Adelle et al., 2020).

5.3.1. Nature-based political entrepreneurship

The concept of political entrepreneurship is crucial for understanding the implementation of NBS because NBS projects are comparable to other public initiatives. For instance, greening urban areas resembles urban renewal efforts (Catney and Henneberry, 2016). This is particularly relevant to the NBS framework promoted by the COEVOLVERS project, which approaches NBS as a form of infrastructural landscaping. Adopting and realising an NBS within a community is mostly an act of political entrepreneurship. However, this is not necessarily the case, since in principle some NBS could also be provisioned via market mechanisms, which we discuss in Section 6.

While political entrepreneurship shares similar criteria with economic entrepreneurship in general, it operates within a different context than the market, though it exhibits comparable competitive dynamics, especially in democratic settings. Political entrepreneurs set agendas, mobilize consensus, and build both internal and external alliances to advance projects (Wohlgemuth, 2000). They also communicate with the public and arrange necessary economic and social resources. In this regard, we can refer to NBS as manifesting political entrepreneurship. Political entrepreneurs often have a personal stake in promoting these projects, especially larger scale, as their future careers in community politics may depend on the success of these initiatives, and they can differentiate themselves from competitors.

In the context of ecosocial transformation, it is important to differentiate between two forms of political entrepreneurship: those that operate within the existing framework of community politics and those that are often referred to as "activism." We can generalize these two forms by using the concept of "stakeholder." Political entrepreneurs are active stakeholders who organise collective action to achieve a shared goal, such as the implementation of a NBS. This process includes not only the realisation of the project itself but also the necessary institutional changes required to establish effective governance mechanisms for the NBS. In this context, political entrepreneurship specifically manifests as institutional entrepreneurship (Maguire et al., 2004). Institutional entrepreneurs deliberately seek to promote and achieve the

reconfiguration of institutions. This differs from the broader goal of altering local practices, as institutions primarily involve formal rules, regulations, and other formalised aspects of public management of NBS. An example of this is when urban greenery initiatives include agreements for renaturing public lawns.

The distinctions matter in COEVOLVERS. A key question to consider is when and how specific collective initiatives become entrepreneurial, independent of the formal landscape defined by the project. For instance, a gardening cooperative can be considered entrepreneurial in a general sense since participants pool resources, collaborate, and cultivate a vegetable garden that did not yet exist prior to their engagement. However, it does not qualify as a form of Nature-based political entrepreneurship unless the members actively engage as stakeholders in the local political process. For example, leaders may work to expand the initiative's scope by advocating for better land availability for similar activities. Such efforts could evolve into institutional entrepreneurship if they also aim to change local regulations governing cooperative gardening.

A defining characteristic of political entrepreneurs is their ability to make representative claims. Even a usurper who overthrows a dictator to take his place may assert that he represents "the will of the people." In the context of this deliverable, which focuses on the inclusion of non-human species, we can explore the claims made within specific NBS. For example, proponents of urban greening might argue that they represent the interests of vulnerable elderly individuals who are particularly affected by heat waves and have fewer resources to cope with them. We should consider the extent to which similar claims are made on behalf of non-human species and examine what motivates and informs these political entrepreneurs. Often, such initiatives are mediated in narratives such as nature conservation.

We can explore the role of MSAs as political entrepreneurs. This concept is familiar in the context of activists and NGOs involved in nature protection and conservation, as well as in various forms of community-based politics. Typically, Nature-based political entrepreneurship focuses on iconic species, which can then broaden to encompass larger issues related to place-based eco-social transformation. Classic examples include the politics surrounding salmon and the involvement of Indigenous

stakeholders (Sarkki et al., 2024). Building on the earlier distinction between embodied and disembodied stakeholder relations, we can examine how embodied multi-species political entrepreneurship allows MSAs to have a voice and make an impact. It is essential to note that this does not align perfectly with the divide between internal, institutionalized community politics and external activism. For instance, a mayor may be an active member of an MSA while also being a passionate forager in her leisure time.

Political entrepreneurs are especially adept in creating nuclei of distributed and collective agency, including the strong case of entrepreneurial collectives (Cohen, 2022). Whereas stakeholder representation is focused on specific groups that are affected by an NBS, entrepreneurial collectives are coalitions of stakeholders who share similar goals in regard to an NBS.

5.3.2. Nature-based social entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship can play a significant role in transforming a NBS into a viable and sustainable institutional form (Bansal et al., 2019). In many countries, lawmakers have established appropriate legal frameworks and tax regulations to support this movement. Social entrepreneurs approach their ventures with a business mindset, aiming to generate income independently of external donors or government subsidies. However, they prioritise their social mission, such as ecosocial transformation, and are content with balancing their budgets rather than maximising profits.

These efforts can encompass both social and market entrepreneurship (Haldar, 2019). For instance, selling mutton sausages can take the form of a place-based social enterprise that aims to foster relationships between citizens and local ecosystems managed by shepherds and their sheep. This approach may even paradoxically contribute to expanding the ecosystem services associated with mutton consumption as a form of community expression. Alternatively, the same product could become a conventional business focused on capitalist goals, seeking to enlarge its market by attracting customers beyond the local community.

Social entrepreneurs play a crucial role in crafting NBA by addressing both economic sustainability and ecological as well as multi-species justice. A significant challenge for NBS is the need to become independent from direct subsidies and external project financing. Achieving this independence requires the involvement of local non-expert knowledge holders. A classic example of this is nature-based tourism, which often relies on volunteers and citizens who serve as guides and support staff. In this context, a social enterprise can serve as an optimal model, helping to manage the

Box 5.7: Social entrepreneurship at Murray Park

The park is governed by the Murray Park Trust, which is currently using the SCIO framework for management. This framework allows them to operate as a trust with a different legal entity. The trust consists of a diverse group of people living in nearby villages who are passionate about nature and the park. They meet regularly and engage in fundraising activities to support initiatives, upgrade the park, and maintain the paths, which is essential. Murray Park was originally dedicated to the public by a poet who purchased the park and gifted it to the people. The trust's role is to manage and maintain the park. From an entrepreneurship perspective, I do not foresee traditional business or economic entrepreneurship, but rather social entrepreneurship driven by community-led initiatives. This involves mobilizing voluntary work and creating cultural events to raise small-scale funding, such as the establishment of forest schools for children and outdoor education programs. While there is a significant focus on social entrepreneurship, there has been one business initiative: the removal of invasive tree species and the sale of the wood, with the proceeds being used to benefit the park.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

expansion of commercial businesses that might otherwise exploit natural resources. For instance, foraging guides might adopt the social enterprise model to cover necessary expenses and infrastructure while also placing clear constraints on foraging activities to protect nature. In contrast, market entrepreneurship can lead to competition among different service providers, resulting in overexpansion and environmentally harmful forms of foraging.

An important aspect of social entrepreneurship is that vulnerable groups can play an essential role both in terms of entrepreneurial initiative and in terms of targeting these initiatives. This is salient in all kinds of therapeutic dimensions of an NBS. For example, a healing garden can be organized as a social enterprise, or the organizers of the garden can set up a consultancy as a social enterprise that contributes to upscaling and diffusion of the NBS.

5.3.3. Nature-based market entrepreneurship

Market entrepreneurship leverages the business potential of NBS. This approach is crucial for inspiring entrepreneurial creativity regarding the business opportunities that NBS can offer. In fact, "Nature-based entrepreneurship" is a well-established and significant phenomenon in rural areas, where it often aligns with the goals of environmental restoration and protection. Typically, these small-scale businesses are operated by women farmers while their husbands handle the primary agricultural activities (Sörensson and Dalborg, 2017). This practice aligns with broader efforts to make agriculture more sustainable and can take on various forms within the context of NBS.

Nature-based market entrepreneurship includes all kinds of businesses that are necessary to create and maintain an NBA. This does not necessarily imply that the entrepreneurs fully subscribe to the ideas and values that motivate the creation of the NBS. However, they become active stakeholders in the project and thereby contribute to its sustainability. In the literature on environmental business, these entrepreneurs have been branded

Box 5.8: Business and ecology at Beskydy

We have a diverse group of entrepreneurs and businesses among our stakeholders, which vary in the scope of their operations. This includes farmers, ski resorts, and tourism accommodations, all of whom are indirectly and directly involved. The key point is that all of them depend on the quality of the local environment. They appreciate engaging with us because they recognize the impact of environmental changes. For example, limited snow in winter affects various stakeholders. Forest managers and owners face potential profit losses if there is damage to forests, but they are also committed to the sustainability of the ecosystem, as it serves as a source of income. Our core group is particularly interested in NBS and adapting to climate change. Ultimately, they need to purposefully rebuild the forest by introducing new species that are more resilient to climate change and dry seasons. This approach promotes the development of multispecies forests rather than monoculture.

Martin Spacek, Beskydy LL

as "opportunists" (without negative connotation) in the sense that they notice the business opportunities offered by an NBS, such as a professional gardener who engages with the build-up of urban greenery. However, there are also other variants of market entrepreneurship, where entrepreneurs pursue green visions, even though they do not move into the domain of social enterprise.

NBS can also be explicitly designed to activate market-based entrepreneurship as a distributed form of producing aggregate results, based on assessing entrepreneurial opportunities using value chain analysis that includes both market profitability and the capitalisation of ecosystem services (Doe, 2022).

Box 5.9: Green tourism at Cres

In addition to the sheep breeders, the tourism industry is also involved in nature protection. The main effort has been done by the local Tourist Board which managed in 2024 to list the island of Cres within the Green Destinations Top 100 Stories. The sensitivity for the nature protection has also the biggest tourist company on the island of Cres which manage several camp sites, the biggest one has the capacity of more than 5000 beds. The company has six different “green” certificates and ten awards. There are several smaller companies which activities are related to the use of local natural resources, like wool, aromatic plants, wood, etc.

Ugo Toić, Cres small scale pilot

5.3.4. Nature-based scientific entrepreneurship

In the modern research environment, many researchers are increasingly taking on entrepreneurial roles. This trend is particularly common in the sciences, where researchers often establish businesses to bring their inventions to market (Aldridge et al., 2017). However, this entrepreneurial aspect is less relevant in the context of NBS, unless the engineering design involves patentable knowledge, which we will exclude from this discussion. Despite this, many researchers today rely on external funding, which leads them to adopt entrepreneurial strategies when developing proposals and seeking financial support. Funding agencies, such as the European Union's scientific directorate, intentionally encourage this entrepreneurial behaviour by fostering a competitive environment and establishing networks of programs. As a result, scientific entrepreneurs actively explore the funding ecosystem, constantly searching for opportunities to secure additional and ongoing funding.

It is important to differentiate between researchers in general and scientific entrepreneurs (Casati and Genet, 2014). Scientific entrepreneurs are leaders who design and implement projects, while many other researchers tend to be followers, joining initiatives without systematically approaching funding as part of their professional careers. Scientific entrepreneurs are often serial innovators because

funding periods are limited, making follow-up funding essential. This is especially relevant in research organizations where even regular positions can depend on external funding. Since these activities usually cannot be pursued in isolation, scientific entrepreneurs often take on leadership roles within their research communities. They leverage their social capital to repeatedly assemble new teams for project applications. Scientific entrepreneurs tend to possess distinct personality characteristics, including being more extroverted and social, as well as having strong team management and motivational skills.

In this section, we focus on a specific topic: the sustainability of research-driven NBS. A significant issue with LLs is that they may not survive beyond the end of the funding period. In general, LLs need to be embedded into wider-reaching networks of knowledge production and sharing (Van Der Jagt et al., 2019). To address this, scientific entrepreneurs might adopt a strategy of integrating an LL into a network of complementary projects or a series of consecutive projects. An important condition for this strategy is that the scientific entrepreneurs establish a strong local foundation by enlisting a sufficient number of stakeholders in the LL who can become long-term partners in the research (on Beskydy, see box 4.5). There are various potential anchors for this collaboration, such as:

- The local conditions may hold unique long-term interest for researchers as a paradigmatic case relevant to their specific research agenda, making substitutes less appealing.
- Researchers may gain additional benefits from the local environment, both in terms of accessing

Box 5.10: Fundraising at Pansio Perno

The Children's Nature Club has previously operated in Pansiksi and successfully implemented a citizen budgeting system in Turku. This system allowed the budget to be distributed to different regions, where citizens voted on how to allocate the funds. This approach was used to support the Nature Club for children. We received feedback indicating that without the Nature Club, the initiative would struggle to thrive. To revitalize the club, funding will be sought from COEVOLVERS, which will cover 50% of the costs. The remaining 50% will be funded by the Uudistuvat lähiöt for one year, during the 2025-2026 period. The club will organize activities twice a week that are centered around nature. For example, an environmental artist has conducted four workshops with the children. The goal of securing this funding is not only to sustain the club but also to actively engage local families, including both children and their parents.

Kia Andell, Turku LL

local resources for their work and potential side benefits, such as consulting fees.

- Furthermore, researchers may maintain a personal connection to the location, whether through residency or other interests, such as an emotional attachment to the area.

Serial scientific entrepreneurship is especially important for institutional reconfiguration since this process typically takes years. Scientific entrepreneurs become members of local collectives of institutional entrepreneurs, mostly as entrepreneurial brokers.

5.4. Conclusion

Entrepreneurship stands out from traditional collective approaches to knowledge co-production by emphasising individual initiative and innovation, while being embedded in collective structures and scaffolds. Rather than serving as a substitute, it complements mainstream methods of co-production and co-creation. However, entrepreneurship can address some of the shortcomings of collective approaches (Adelle et al., 2020). These shortcomings include:

- The processes are time-consuming and often require professional facilitation, making them dependent on project funding and susceptible to fading once the project concludes.
- Despite having inclusive structures, there is no guarantee that powerful stakeholders will not eventually dominate the conversation.
- Interactions among numerous parties can lack transparency, which may undermine trust in the process.
- The complicated consultation processes may not lead to effective long-term solutions because they can face challenges related to individual commitment and availability.

Entrepreneurs act independently but also need to ensure community support, hence towards inclusive approaches in practice. They actively invest in efficacious process designs, and they can focus on immediate practical outcomes.

Nature-based entrepreneurship often involves a combination of different entrepreneurial approaches, highlighting the unique local conditions discussed in the first section of this chapter.

Successful nature-based entrepreneurs are typically

researchers who serve as entrepreneurial brokers. They facilitate the formation of entrepreneurial assemblages, such as coalitions of political and market entrepreneurs, who work together to achieve institutional entrepreneurship.

Box 5.11: Scientists as entrepreneurial brokers at Murray Park

We see ourselves as facilitators and brokers, linking different community groups and NGOs, which has been a very productive process. We are catalyzing engagement through our participatory workshops and VNT, making people excited about new ways of doing things. We are creating platforms for dialogue and helping communities build their online presence through our website. As scientists, we can collect information and share it online, much like we discovered paths previously. We have left a legacy and provided a model for typical community woodlands, which can be found throughout the UK. We also engage in funding applications to support our initiatives. The "Searching Common Ground" workshop provided an experimentation platform for co-creation and exploration. We compiled a report based on our findings and delivered it back to the community. Feedback has indicated that people are asking more questions and expressing curiosity. For example, when we uncovered medieval cattle pens, people were eager for more information. Recently, we took local community members on excursions to other parks, sharing what we have accomplished and how these lessons could be applied to other community woodlands.

Tim Pittaway, Murray Park LL

Chapter 6: Crafting Nature-based assemblages with care

6.0. Chapter summary

This chapter further explores practices in Nature-Based Assemblages, distinguishing them from Nature-Based Solutions NBS as mere ideas. The key concepts derived from Chapter 1 are "craft" and "care." Craft differs from the science-based engineering of NBS by mobilising tacit and contextual local knowledge in practical applications that are grounded in an embodied relationship with the place where the NBS is implemented. Care reflects a mindful deployment of skills and a responsibility for the well-being of other beings in that environment. Together, craft and care serve as the guiding principles for human interventions and the shaping of NBA. We illustrate these principles with a case study of the COEVOLVERS Living Lab, specifically the healing garden at Pomáz-Kiskovácsi, Hungary. The chapter concludes by summarising the paradigm shift promoted in this deliverable, referred to as the "NBS-NBA policy cycle" of socio-ecological transformation.

6.1. Craft and care

The coevolutionary approach to NBS has significant implications for urban and landscape planning, epistemology, methodology, and practical applications. These implications are gradually revealed in the work of COEVOLVERS. The insights were adumbrated by previous contributions, particularly the philosophy of landscape design put forth by landscape architect James Corner over the past few decades. In 1997, Corner (reprint in Reed and Lister, 2020) wrote:

My purpose in this essay is to present a number of theoretical bases that might allow for a more animate appropriation of ecology in landscape architectural practice. These bases have little to do with the object-centered advocacy of Nature ("environment") or culture ("art") and point instead toward the highly interactive processes and relationships that are *life* itself—life as both a specific and autonomous system of networks, forces, combinations, unfoldings, events, and transformations. What is important in this view is how creative practices in ecology and landscape architecture construct—or, more precisely, *enable*—alternative forms of relationship and hybridization between people, place, material, and the Earth. Echoing evolutionary principles, these enabling strategies function less as instruments or ameliorants and more as agents, as processes, and as active imbroglios and ever-emerging networks of potential. Obviously, I am discussing a landscape architecture that has yet to appear fully, one that is less preoccupied with ameliorative, stylistic, or pictorial concerns and more actively engaged with imaginative, enabling, and diversifying practices—*practices of the wild*.

How might the pulsing flow and flux of wild life, its autonomous systems as "other," and its reflective and moral sense to be channeled, liberated, and expressed through an ecology and landscape of creative agents? The answers, I believe, lie within the powers of both Natural and cultural agencies in the evolving of landscapes that precipitate (and are caught within) the processes of indetermination and diversification; landscapes that engage, enable, diversify, trick, and emancipate, and elude- put simply, landscapes that function as actants, as continual transformations and encounters that actively resist closure and representation.

When Corner wrote this, the concept of Nature-based solutions had not yet been established. As outlined in Chapter 1, in this deliverable, we interpret the "practices of the wild" through the lens of assemblage theory (DeLanda, 2016). Corner previously referred to related theoretical principles by using the term "actant" and highlighting the notion of diverse agents. He also emphasised that forms of human intervention can be considered as an art form. This chapter expands on his ideas in relation to LL practices. We approach the work of LLs as a *craft*—specifically, the crafting of spaces that enable the emergence of Nature-based assemblages that nurture cohabitation and shared flourishing of humans and non-humans. As explained in Chapter 1, assemblages are collections of heterogeneous elements that possess emergent causal powers, where the elements retain their autonomy in interacting with other entities beyond the assemblage. In LLs, human actors collaborate with non-human entities to create assemblages that may include stakeholders, material elements like a laguna, or non-human entities such as specific animals and plants and that are conceived as having causal powers, namely capacities to generate “solutions” as emergent processes rather than fixed endpoints: For example, a healing garden is an assemblage with causal powers to influence on processes of healing. Each assemblage is unique, much like any individual work of craftspersonship, and is highly contextualized.

The concept of craft goes beyond the current discussions surrounding the co-production of knowledge and the co-creation of NBS (Sarkki et al., 2025; Van Der Jagt et al., 2019). These discussions often emphasize a social-structural distinction between experts, who are trained scientists, and non-experts. Ideas such as transdisciplinarity seek to overcome this dichotomy, which tends to create a linear paradigm in which knowledge is viewed merely as a product of research that is made

“actionable.” As previously discussed in the context of Nature-based entrepreneurship, these different roles are also shaped by varying circumstances in the lives of experts and non-experts. Experts typically intervene and participate for a limited time, whereas non-experts are part of the communities that are affected by the research-driven actions proposed by researchers.

We propose a radical shift in perspective: instead of focusing on the roles of individuals, we should examine these processes and interactions from the viewpoint of the product itself, conventionally referred to as NBS. When the idea of NBS is implemented, this intervention results in a complex NBA that is highly individualised and contextualised, often addressing multiple goals such as solving environmental issues, supporting vulnerable groups, or promoting biodiversity. Given these characteristics of NBS, we argue that the process of creating an NBS is essentially a form of crafting: The resulting NBA is a work of craftpersonship (this term avoids gender, while still referring to humans).

Craft represents a pattern of human activity that fundamentally differs from science-driven activities (Sennett, 2009). It is rooted in skills acquired through a long process of learning by doing. Craft is shaped and passed down within communities of practitioners, typically through the relationship between master and apprentice. Additionally, the craft is responsive to the materiality of its objects, adapting and accommodating as necessary. In summary, craft embodies “knowing how” rather than simply “knowing that.” Building on the lengthy quote by Corner (1997) mentioned earlier, we view crafting not merely as a skill-based activity that results in a fixed output—such as creating detailed, artistic, and practically usable handicrafts—but rather as an ongoing and evolving process. NBS are never truly finished, despite what the term “solutions” may imply. Therefore, we propose a shift towards the process of crafting spaces that allow for the evolution of multispecies and Nature-based assemblages, guiding them toward desirable futures that are perpetually out of reach. This new conceptualisation further clarifies how to approach NBS as an artwork (see D 2.1) (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2023). As thoroughly discussed in Dewey's aesthetics, the modern conception of art suggests a duality between art and craft, assigning an elitist position to the former (Dewey, 2005; Leddy and Puolakka, 2021). This distinction

is primarily based on the idea that artwork is devoid of practical function that emerged in the transition to Western modernity (Bourdieu, 2019). In contemporary terms, design serves as the counterpart to craft, encompassing production processes that are industrial rather than artisanal. Crafting an NBA involves integrating both functional and aesthetic dimensions (Frantzeskaki, 2019). If we conceptualise the implementation of NBS as a product of crafting an NBA, the distinction between experts and non-experts becomes blurred, as both groups must act as craftspersons in a collaborative effort to create the NBA. The NBS, in essence, is simply an idea or proposal on how to solve a problem using specific means. Executing the NBS involves crafting the NBA. In this process, an essential element is care.

The concept of care has taken on a pivotal role in feminist approaches to ecosocial transformation, and has become widely received in sustainability science, where it is primarily understood as an ethical stance (Moriggi et al., 2020; West et al., 2018). However, there is a significant distinction between care and the concept of multi-species justice (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017). While multi-species justice emphasises formal criteria such as distributional or procedural, care embodies a concern for others, which can lead to unequal treatment of certain entities: caring for one may imply neglecting another. Additionally, justice often places substantial cognitive burdens on individuals, requiring them to weigh the interests of various affected parties and strive for a balance that is acceptable to everyone. Justice is rooted in principles of disembodied rationality, reflecting the Enlightenment tradition and the Kantian ideals of justice. In contrast, care is an embodied concern related to the notion of second-order vulnerability (see Chapter 2), indicating that care is inherently subjective, while justice aims for objectivity and impartiality. Thus, the distinction between justice and care is similar to the difference between science and craft, where care is an essential element of crafting.

This reasoning has been further expanded to suggest that care is not fundamentally an ethical stance. This perspective is reflected in one of the most influential definitions of care by Tronto (Tronto, 2015), who states: "...activities we do to remain, continue, and repair our world so that we may live in it as well as possible." Notably, this definition does not include any ethical terms; rather, it focuses on the concept of "living

well.” Consequently, this view aligns with the classical notion of *eudaimonia*, which encompasses ethical practices. However, these practices also involve forms of care that are primarily aesthetic, merging aesthetic and ethical criteria (Saitō, 2022). This integration is crucial for understanding the concept of craft. The artisan is dedicated to caring for her materials, the products she creates, and the needs of the user. She is obliged to avoid any actions that could result in inferior or harmful products. While this reflects a form of ethical commitment, it is expressed through the skills of the craft and the aesthetic qualities of the final product.

We argue that NBS should be conceptualised as the careful crafting of an NBA. This involves developing skills that are contextually expressed and shared within communities of craftspersons. The practice of COEVOLVERS demonstrates how LLs evolve as communities of craftspersons.

6.2. The practice of crafting NBA

6.2.1. Grounding the paradigm shift from NBS to NBA: The case of a healing garden

The term "Nature-based solutions" is influential and well-established, supported by a special scientific journal titled "Nature-based solutions" and numerous projects that incorporate it. However, this term can be problematic when viewed through the lens of Corner's ideas on landscape planning. The word "solution" raises several questions. First, it implies that there is a problem that needs to be solved. Who defines this problem, and how is the proposed solution related to it? The term suggests a linear understanding, where there is a clear causal connection between the solution and the problem. For example, if the problem is heat waves in urban areas, a proposed solution might be to plant street trees to help reduce temperatures through shading and cooling. Presenting the issue in this way encourages an optimisation approach: planners may focus on selecting tree species that provide the most effective results. However, this strategy poses a challenge to the fundamental principle of protecting, sustaining, and fostering biodiversity within NBS. The engineering approach can lead

to an urban monoculture, where only a few optimal tree species are chosen, ultimately undermining biodiversity.

This example is oversimplified but demonstrates a fundamental problem with the term Nature-based solutions: in practice, most NBS are not solutions to just one problem. For instance, planting trees should contribute to lowering urban temperatures while also supporting biodiversity. According to a well-known principle formulated by Tinbergen for economic policy (Tinbergen, 1998), an intervention should only link one measure with one goal. When we relate one measure to multiple goals, it creates complex trade-offs and makes the planning process messy and opaque. NBS typically violate this principle, and this violation is becoming more pronounced. In the early stages, the linear solution-problem connection was mostly maintained. However, critical assessments have led to the overloading of NBS with many goals. For example, in addition to biodiversity, another common concern is improving conditions for various vulnerable groups.

Theoretically, the solution-problem nexus can be addressed by treating all these other goals as constraints in selecting the optimal solution. However, the notion of a constraint implies a status quo bias and does not mean that the other goals will be actively pursued or improved. For instance, selecting street trees with biodiversity as a constraint means that the existing biodiversity should not be diminished. However, actively supporting biodiversity means that the constraint is effectively treated as another goal. In other words, viewing constraints only as costs undermines the recognition of these other goals as valuable in their own right. This perspective is not what is currently upheld in the prevailing views on NBS, both in scientific circles and policy discussions.

In COEVOLVERS, we observe different constellations. One clear example of a seemingly linear relationship between a solution and a problem is a healing garden. At first glance, the healing garden can appear to establish a straightforward causal chain from creating and maintaining a hospital garden in order to improve the mental health of human patients. This chain would inform the organisational procedures of the hospital's medical and management leadership, based on available scientific

evidence (Panțiru et al., 2024; Soga et al., 2017). In this context, the healing garden is not connected to other goals.

However, there are two reasons why this perspective is too narrow. The first reason stems directly from the organizational context. Maintaining the healing garden is just one therapeutic approach among many others, and the hospital considers these alternatives in terms of both effectiveness and costs. This broader setting has important implications for the stakeholder analysis of the NBS. Typically, stakeholder

analysis only considers those stakeholders who are directly impacted by the NBS. However, since the maintenance of the garden incurs both initial and ongoing costs, its establishment also affects many other stakeholders who are not directly related to it. In particular, active stakeholders can be completely

Box 6.1: Controversies about healing approaches

Within the Hungarian mental healthcare sector, there is limited practice and knowledge related to nature-based therapies. The sector is dominated by medicalized approaches and more holistic therapeutic methods are marginalized. Some of the medical staff of the hospital are engaged and highly motivated to use such a more holistic approach and participate in the co-design of the healing garden, but their efforts are usually seen as 'complimentary' therapy, a 'nice-to-have' in addition to the mainstream medication practice.

Core group, Healing Garden LL, Pomáz-Kiskovácsi

disconnected from the NBS, such as critics of nature-based therapy and other approaches and try to stop the flow of resources into the NBS.

The second issue relates to the multidimensionality of NBS and to how people think about nature. We can illustrate this point by referencing biodiversity again. The question is how much the therapeutic effects are directly influenced by biodiversity in the garden (Marselle et al., 2021). A healing garden is designed to enhance the mental well-being of its clients. There is a wealth of literature exploring which plant species and types of natural environments are beneficial for treating various mental disorders. However, incorporating biodiversity into these designs can raise important questions. To what extent can the design and maintenance of a healing garden adhere to agroecological principles and nature conservation? For instance, a decayed tree trunk could serve as a habitat for various insects, enriching biodiversity, but might be considered unsightly and therefore removed. Additionally, how should gardens accommodate insects like wasps, which can evoke fear in some people? These

questions present significant challenges in balancing human preferences with biodiversity goals.

Considerations about biodiversity should extend beyond the hospital's organisational setting. To achieve biodiversity objectives, the healing garden must be viewed in relation to its connectivity with the surrounding environment (Zhang et al., 2019). Like urban gardening in general, we often see a single garden as an isolated initiative; however, this approach is insufficient for effectively addressing biodiversity goals. For instance, caring for pollinators within the garden holds little significance if the surrounding area lacks additional spaces that support diverse flora and fauna (Derby Lewis et al., 2019). Therefore, technically speaking, the garden should be regarded as one component within a network of interconnected green spaces.

Box 6.2: Healing garden connectivity

The Boldog Gellért Psychiatric Hospital is surrounded by a protected natural area. Although, the hospital garden currently can be characterized as an urban park with limited biodiversity, there is a great potential to re-design it into a biodiversity-rich place taking into account the surrounding animal and plant species. Furthermore, therapeutic sessions are not limited to the hospital garden, clients are also invited to take walks during guided therapeutic sessions in the surrounding area. Therefore, the hospital garden needs to be considered as embedded in the larger landscape.

Core group, Healing Garden LL, Pomáz-Kiskovácsi

If we generalize our observations, we propose that the healing garden should be viewed as a Nature-based assemblage that entails different levels and complex causal patterns that interact with one another. More exactly, the healing garden is an assemblage of assemblages (figure 6.1). At the core is the healing garden as an abstract concept, defined in terms of properties such as location, design patterns, and organisational structures. Therefore, the healing garden is not a physical entity but rather a potential that can be realized through the interactions of various parties: This is the idea of the NBS. At the same time, the idea of the healing garden directly relates to the physical object, grounded in the primordial semantics: The word “healing garden” refers deictically to what a visitor sees when approaching the site. A gardener may point to the site and says: “This is our healing garden.” However, what we see is not what the healing garden actually is, namely an assemblage of heterogeneous elements on different levels. We refer to the core as a “thing-idea” (which corresponds to Deleuze and Guattari’s concept of “corps sans

organes”). The thing-idea of the healing garden is the elementary assemblage of the idea and the material site to which it refers.

Figure 6.1: The healing garden as assemblage of assemblages

Once the healing garden is launched, it sets the stage for the co-evolving NBA. The core consists of members who engage through embodied relationality. The concept of a healing garden directly relates to this idea, as it suggests that certain emotional and physical experiences significantly impact the mental health of patients.

In this context, we can identify emerging MSAs, which may include patients, specific animals, and soil (of course, plants can also be involved, some patients may develop particular emotional bonds with certain insects). Additionally, some human members, such as medical staff, may also form embodied relationships with the healing garden and potentially experience therapeutic benefits, including stress relief. However, other medical staff may approach this therapeutic measure from a more detached or disembodied perspective (therefore we mention them on two different layers).

The disembodied perspective is integrated into the next level of the assemblage of assemblages, known as the organisational unit. In this context, we encounter various stakeholders, including department management and relatives of patients who may support the therapy but do not actively participate in the garden themselves. Considering the connections related to the health garden mentioned earlier, the next layer involves the environment. This includes the broader ecological setting as well as direct organisational linkages, such as those with the neighborhood surrounding the hospital or the local municipality. The healing garden may serve as a component of the local biodiversity strategy, which can influence stakeholder dynamics.

Finally, we consider the concept of the “world.” This refers to broader trends beyond the immediate environment, such as the development of scientific discourses about therapies or the impact of climate change on local climates. In summary, the healing garden is no longer just a simple idea; it has become a complex entity with no fixed boundaries, where its elements maintain diverse connections to other entities beyond its basic composition. For example, doctors are part of professional networks at the national level.

As we see, crafting a healing garden requires careful consideration of various complex relationships and interactions. For example, as mentioned in Chapter 5, researchers can serve as entrepreneurial brokers and may participate in national meetings of healthcare professionals to discuss their projects. This involvement can ultimately influence the perceptions of medical staff on the ground. On the flip side, developing the garden also involves the practical aspects of the craft of gardening itself. Patients and staff who lack experience may face several challenges and frustrations when it comes to actually tending to the garden.

6.2.2. Crafting the healing garden NBA

The example of the healing garden demonstrates how we can rethink NBS as NBA. When humans create a healing garden at a hospital, they are crafting an NBA rather than implementing a linear NBS. Three aspects are pointed out but as crafting is not a linear process but rather organic, these are overlapping.

First, participation: Crafting occurs when creating a sustainable stakeholder composition within the organisation and among relevant external actors. As discussed in Chapter 2, this stakeholder constellation evolves organically and is not controlled by those who initiate the garden design. However, designers can create settings in which stakeholders engage in discourse and various forms of interaction. This aligns with the conventional meaning of participatory approaches to NBS. However, it is important to distinguish this from current notions of co-production or co-creation, and we avoid the term “co-crafting” here. The idea of co-production implies that all actors are actively involved in the creation of the garden, but this is neither the case nor a requirement. Some stakeholders may be neutral or too busy with their daily work to engage in a participatory process. They may simply accept the garden, thereby contributing to its sustainability by refraining from antagonistic actions. Indeed, many important factors that sustain an NBA are simply neutral, including even natural components (for instance, repeated bad weather during the early stages of garden installation may eventually dampen the enthusiasm of many participants; therefore, its absence is a crucial sustaining factor). The concept of assemblage encompasses all kinds of stakeholder constellations that contribute to the sustainability of the NBS, even those who do not directly co-produce. In other words, crafting focuses on creating a scaffold or arena in which the forces of endogenously assembled NBA can emerge and unfold. This defines the crafting of the healing garden as a deliberative process. For example, on-site experiences with various stakeholders gathering at the garden to discuss the current status and further steps can be crucial events in determining its further development.

Box 6.3: Engaging reluctant stakeholders at the healing garden

Engaging stakeholders from the psychiatric hospital faced several challenges for the LL core group. Engaging in participatory processes is not evident for many people working in the healthcare sector which is characterized by strong and rigid hierarchy. Constraints to the willingness to spend time on co-creation activities might also be affected by past (negative) experiences. Furthermore, health care professionals are exposed to high risk of burnout, particularly because they work in a sector which suffers from a lack of positive political attention and support in Hungary, which limits their capacities to engage in 'extra' activities. Within such a context, engaging stakeholders needs to be planned in a way that the collaborative work is embedded in or even supports the daily work of the targeted stakeholders.

Core group, Healing Garden LL, Pomáz-Kiskovácsi

Second, holistic approach: The garden is a complex mix of humans and non-human beings, reflecting a distribution of agential powers. While humans might aim for complete control over the garden, they could also choose to grant varying degrees of freedom to other beings. If the goal is to enhance biodiversity, it is essential to recognise the agential powers of non-humans, which can lead to unexpected outcomes. The objectives of a "healing garden" are particularly important in this discussion. If the garden is designed solely to meet human needs, it may undermine the goal of enhancing biodiversity. On the other hand, biodiversity itself can be seen as a value that contributes to mental well-being. By considering the needs of non-humans living in and around the hospital garden and acknowledging their agency, we can create a harmonious relationship between human and non-human needs. For instance, planting fruit trees that thrive and provide habitats for birds and insects illustrates how to strengthen embodied relationality, especially when humans harvest and consume what has grown. In this context, the garden becomes an emergent phenomenon where no single actor holds dominant influence. This raises a key question: what ultimate criteria guide how humans interact in this setting? We argue that aesthetic motives primarily govern these interactions. For example, the healing garden can serve as a distinctive marker of the hospital as a place (Raymond et al., 2023).

Third, experimenting with interconnecting humans and non-humans: The human form of relationality in the NBA can be understood as aesthetic in a broad sense. This means that the NBA is perceived as a collaborative artwork that showcases craftsmanship.

In craftsmanship, skill

development is of utmost importance. While many crafting activities may not directly relate to the garden design in a strict sense, they involve nurturing the abilities required

Box 6.4: The healing garden as artwork

Various activities have been co-organized with the professional staff of the hospital and with the core group members of the LL, which did not directly target the re-design of the garden but aimed at enhancing connection between humans and non-humans. Eco-art therapy sessions, in which gardening and visual art experts joined therapeutic employees of the hospital aimed at revealing and emphasizing the potential values of nature through listening plant music or painting with plant-based pigments. Bird feeders and bird houses which were placed in the hospital garden accompanied by discussions about bird life, helped to reveal to current and potential diversity of the hospital garden.

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to foster a caring attitude. Metaphorically, this care translates to "listening." In creating the NBS, various techniques are essential for enhancing the relationships between the parties involved. For instance, developing skills to sense seasonal changes and adopting suitable attitudes and actions in gardening are crucial. The co-design of a healing garden, thus, is not limited to creating garden plans, but it includes revealing the existing values of the hospital garden, and being able to appreciate the living and non-living beings in nature.

It is essential to acknowledge that the therapeutic approach of the healing garden does not rely solely on the care provided by medical staff. In fact, much of the healing process involves nurturing the garden together with the patients, with less emphasis on patients in a traditional sense. Caring for the garden is the aesthetic form of caring for the patients. The therapeutic effects are not solely controlled by the therapists; they are co-created by both the garden and the patients, with support from the medical staff. Thus, therapy in this context is a craft in its own right, particularly from the therapists' perspective. Embodied relationality is a key element of the therapist's ability to provide care, as they must develop sensitivity to the unique circumstances of time, place, and individuals within the garden. Additionally, they build implicit knowledge on how to address changing dynamics and challenges. The garden, as an aesthetic assemblage, serves as the medium through which this knowledge co-evolves.

6.3. Summing up: The NBS-NBA coevolutionary policy cycle

In previous deliverables, we have outlined the concept of NBS as a coevolutionary technology. In this current deliverable, we specify this technology as a "craft." Modern technology is typically seen as a linear process that progresses from idea to realization. Inventors envision a new device, engineers experiment with prototypes, companies develop scalable products, and ultimately make the technology practical for use. All these steps are tightly controlled by humans. However, this sequence cannot be applied to NBS, as they involve "nature," which consists of a complex setting with many autonomous agents that influence the realisation of NBS right from the earliest stages. While NBS represents a idea, it cannot exist as a concrete reality,

even though it is associated with tangible references—what we call a "thing-idea." The "thing" refers to the natural elements that are intended to serve human-defined purposes. When this idea is put into practice, human actions lead to the creation of a nature-based assemblage NBA, where humans initially do not possess complete knowledge about its composition. As we discussed in previous WP 2 deliverables, this occurs because the interventions create affordances for other living beings, which may not be fully understood by human designers. Therefore, the NBA is necessarily co-created by both humans and non-humans. The coevolutionary approach to NBS not only acknowledges this as an inherent truth but also actively encourages co-creation. In Figure 6.2, this observation pertains to the first step in the NBS-NBA spiral. The term "spiral" has been suggested in Figures 1.1 and 1.2., which depict a snail shell. In simple terms, this indicates that once the NBS is implemented, numerous unanticipated developments occur. These developments are intentionally encouraged in the coevolutionary approach, as the human designers aim to trigger cocreative responses from all types of human and non-human stakeholders involved in the emerging NBA. The coevolutionary approach considers the NBS technology itself as a source of knowledge generation that provides feedback to its original concept. Thus, we can conclude that the NBS concept and the NBA coevolve, resulting in evolutionary changes in the original idea. This reflects a spiral-type dynamic as depicted in Figure 1.2. In Figure 6.2, we conceptualize this as the "NBS-NBA policy cycle."

The cycle begins with generating an idea inspired by current narratives and scientific discussions about NBS. This leads to the design and implementation of an intervention in a local ecosystem, aiming to provide specific ecosystem services that meet human needs while taking into account biodiversity. As a result of this intervention, an NBA emerges, creating numerous unexpected affordances for interactions among various species. These interactions were considered during the planning of the intervention. At this stage, the focus shifts from designing interventions to crafting the NBA, where aesthetic considerations become central to human-non-human interactions. The practices that develop from this—referred to as "habits"—help sustain the NBA as a Nature-based governance framework for sustainability and shared flourishing.

Ultimately, the policy cycle prompts a reevaluation of the original design ideas, building upon an expanding knowledge base generated by the NBA experiences.

Figure 6.2: The NBS-NBA policy cycle

A critical element in the NBA is the emergence of multi-species stakeholder assemblages MSAs. These agencies play a vital role in the reproduction of the NBA and its associated benefits, particularly in instances where humans are involved. In an MSA, humans connect with other entities through what is known as embodied relationality. This concept refers to shared and distributed forms of agency; for instance, a human can be part of an assemblage that includes a river and the fish within it. The notion of embodiment is broad and multifaceted. It encompasses various aspects, such as cultural identities that link humans with non-humans, corporeal engagements that range from activities like playing and eating to active cohabitation. If MSA are essential for maintaining an NBA that aligns with the original concept of NBS, it raises the question of how human interventions can foster the development of

MSA. This capability is crucial in crafting NBA. In this report, we have highlighted various LL practices that are relevant to this process. For instance, countermapping the territory where the NBS is intended to be implemented can help establish a connection with other entities in that area. This process has two key aspects. First, countermapping can evoke awareness and feelings about the local environment that are often overlooked or suppressed, enhancing human mindfulness. This heightened awareness can make humans more receptive to understanding different worlds. Second, countermapping allows for a vicarious expression of the experiences of other beings during the human mapping process.

We have previously argued that NBS should be viewed as forms of artwork. We refer to this as “craft” because the Western understanding of art is often limited to activities that serve as ends in themselves, focusing on the expression of human subjectivity. Crafting an NBA is an aesthetic and creative act that aims to promote the shared flourishing of the multi-species community in a specific location. In this context, craft serves a purpose that extends beyond human interests. A fitting comparison can be drawn with the art produced by humans within rituals that connect them with both real and imagined beings. These rituals shape the ways in which communities coexist. Ritual practices often highlight the highest expressions of human craftsmanship, encompassing not only the creation of artisanal ritual objects but also the shaping of human actions themselves. In this context, the concept of “care” is distinct from the idea of justice. Crafting an NBA requires care, meaning that it involves employing embodied forms of aesthetic engagement with others.

We have argued that care differs from multispecies justice in that it is deeply contextualised, embodied, and local. Care is an essential force in the formation of MSAs. In these MSAs, humans learn to recognise the relationships with other beings as acts of mutual care, without imposing the notion of human intentionality onto them. For example, pollinators contribute to human well-being by enabling us to enjoy locally produced fruits and honey, emphasising the importance of their actions for our flourishing. This mutuality represents an embodied form of multispecies justice through the reciprocity of co-produced benefits. Shared flourishing serves as an

aesthetic expression of successful cohabitation, facilitated by the NBA, which is inspired by the NBS as an idea.

Eventually, the spiral movement leads to a reconceptualisation of the NBS within the local community. As we have discussed, this transformation of the original idea is influenced by individual uniqueness that cannot be reduced to generalizations. The complex causal patterns that emerge during this process and sustain its existence over time are too intricate to simplify. The lessons learned can be captured in various aesthetic forms, such as local narratives or inter-species art projects within the community, like local schools or festivals. However, these experiences can also resonate across different locations. A crucial aspect of generalizing the diversity of local experiences lies in creating repositories of narrative case studies that connect to abstract categories of NBS thing-ideas, such as a “healing garden.”

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